

Examining the Relationship Between Corporate
Governance Mechanisms and Financial
Performance of Small and Medium Size
Enterprises Listed in the FTSE-Alternative
Investment Market

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DECLARATION

I declare that the work in the thesis is entirely my own. Where I have consulted the work of others, this is always clearly stated.

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ABSTRACT

Corporate governance (CG) is a system by which companies can be directed and controlled (Cadbury, 1992). This thesis investigates the impact of internal corporate governance mechanisms on the financial performance of 96 listed small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the Alternative Investment Market (AIM) of the UK for the year 2015. The study contributes in the form of recommendations on the effective CG practices that will help SMEs to improve their CG structure while enhancing their financial performance and policymakers to update or review the QCA CG code in the future. Initially, the thesis explores thoroughly the concept of CG, the theoretical background in relation to CG and the financial performance (FP) of companies. Based on the gaps in the previous literature, the CG variables (under the parameters of BOD) and the FP mechanisms were selected to examine their relationship with the sample of listed SMEs in the UK.

The main themes covered by this thesis to achieve the aim involve the emergence of the CG, the overall growth of the CG in various developed and developing countries, multiple theoretical frameworks that further help to develop the conceptual framework. The principles of CG codes of the UK and previous literature assist the researcher to select the independent and dependent variables of this study (BI, BS, BGD, CEO-duality, ACS, ROA, and Tobin's Q). As this study is based on a sample of AIM-listed companies, a detailed discussion has been presented on the submarket of the LSE (London Stock Exchange), the latest amendments in the rules of the AIM market and the CG practices of the SMEs listed in the AIM. Based on theoretical and conceptual frameworks, the researcher developed the hypotheses. In terms of research methodology, the positivist approach has been selected, data collected from the FAME database, website of LSE and the annual reports of the sample companies. Data have been analysed with the help of Gretl software and the main statistical tools selected to analyse the data were correlation, regression and ANOVA analysis.

According to the results, the impact of the board gender diversity (BGD) is significantly positive on the FP of the sample companies and the board independence (BI) were found to be negatively related to the performance of the SMEs. As far as other CG variables (CEO-duality, board size and audit committee size) are concerned in relation to the FP of SMEs, a nominal relationship was found. These results will help the SMEs in the application of different CG principles while stabilising their financial performance. The findings of this study assist the practitioners to enhance the CG codes of the UK concerning SMEs and their CG structure. In addition to that, this thesis will also serve as a guide for those who seek an understanding of the concept of CG.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Definition
CG	Corporate Governance
FP	Financial Performance
SME	Small and Medium Size Enterprises
AIM	Alternative Investment Market
LSE	London Stock Exchange
QCA	Quoted Companies Alliance
FTSE	Financial Times Stock Exchange
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
BOD	Board of Directors
FRC	Financial Reporting Council
HIH	Health International Holdings
CSRC	China Securities Regulatory Commission
CASE	Cairo and Alexander Stock Exchange
KMBC	Kumar Mangalam Birla Committee
SEBI	Securities Exchange Board of India
BS	Board Size
CEOD	CEO Duality
BGD	Board Gender Diversity
NED	Non-Executive Directors
ACS	Audit Committee Size
NAPF	National Association of Pension Funds
UWS	The University of the West of Scotland
UK	United Kingdom

USA United States of America

GCC Gulf Corporation Council

ROA Return on Assets

SOX Sarbanes-Oxley Act 2002

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

Corporate governance (CG) is a way of governing the company from the employee level to board level with its well-defined policies, culture, and customs. The basic concept of CG is to improve accountability in the company. In the words of [Busrai \(2019\)](#), good CG structure in a company works for the advantage of everyone concerned, through the adoption of ethical standards, fair practices and abiding laws. On the other hand, bad CG is considered as an uncertain, non-compliant, and poor structure of governance that could result in damage to the reputation or the financial image of the company. After major collapses such as Enron, Parmalat and so on, corporate governance became a popular topic in the corporate world ([Sharp & Stock, 2005](#)). Upon investigation about the high-profile mismanagement of big, multinational enterprises, it came to light that one of the main reasons for collapses was the inefficient corporate governance structure of the companies. Therefore, in the current business environment, the existence of an organisation is not possible without practising basic corporate governance requirements ([Rehman & Hashim, 2020](#)).

The effect of some of the big scams was intense, because of which the financial economists, academicians, researchers and investors in developed markets begin to address the problems related to the development of CG. Consequently, the literature has grown immensely on the relationship between corporate governance and the financial performance of firms ([Jackling & Johl, 2009](#)). Often the decisions of a firm are inconsistent with the only requirement of the shareholders being the maximisation of their wealth. The reason being, the different objectives of owners and managers lead to the agency problem ([Jensen & Meckling, 1976](#)). Further, agency theory suggested that it is necessary to check on administrative decisions to eradicate conflict between shareholders and managers. Hence, shareholders appoint the board of directors who act on behalf of them to safeguard their interests ([Alexakis, et al., 2006](#)). In addition to agency theory, many theories (stewardship theory, stakeholder theory, and resource-dependency theory) have been developed to understand the concept of CG in depth which is discussed in detail in Chapter 2.

Globally, substantial measures have been taken in the form of corporate governance guidelines and codes to avoid corporate collapses. To ensure accountability and transparency in the firms, significant reforms have been made concerning the board of directors (Naseem, *et al.*, 2017). The UK corporate governance codes paid special attention to board characteristics. An ample amount of literature is available on the relationship between board parameters of CG and the financial performance of firms (Hermalin & Weisbach, 1991; Amar, *et al.*, 2011; Bhagat & Black, 2002). However, there is no consensus result found between attributes of the board of directors and financial performance of even large, well-established companies (Jackling & Johl, 2009). A study to investigate the link between attributes of the board of directors and the financial performance of listed small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the UK will be useful in understanding the nexus of CG practices in SMEs.

1.2 Corporate Governance in SMEs

Nowadays, it has become essential for all enterprises (either big or small) to implement an effective CG structure to gain the trust of investors and to maintain the reputation of a company in the market (Caner, 2010). There is abundant literature about CG with the sample of large companies as some authors believe that only big companies are required to follow an effective CG structure (Abor & Adjasi, 2007; Amar, *et al.*, 2011). As this concept is relatively new, most authors researched CG with a sample of companies established in developed countries only (Ahmadi, *et al.*, 2018). Gradually, this trend has been changing as now many authors also research with a sample of emerging economies as well (Arora & Sharma, 2016). However, the research on CG with a sample of SMEs is still rare (Eisenberg, *et al.*, 1998; Arora & Singh, 2020). Understandably, micro-companies may not require extra measures to maintain accountability and transparency in the firm but in the case of listed SMEs, the attention of authors is required to research a suitable CG structure that will benefit their overall performance.

SMEs play an important role in the growth and development of a country. According to Afrifa (2013b), SMEs are the largest source of employment in most countries. Therefore, the authorities and researchers need to pay attention particularly to the CG practices of SMEs (Edmiston, 2007; Khalique, *et al.*, 2011). In the UK, SMEs provide employment to 16.6m people (PBC Today, 2019), contribute 52% of the overall economy's turnover and 54% of the economic output (Santander, 2018). Given this significance, the CG guidelines will

clarify the benefits of having a good CG structure that helps SMEs to earn investors (Afrifa, 2013b). This study chooses the sample of SMEs listed in the FTSE Alternative Investment Market (AIM) of the London Stock Exchange (LSE). FTSE-AIM is an international submarket of LSE specifically established to provide a platform for SMEs to publicly register and gain public investors (Shah, 2014). On the one hand, it becomes impossible to survive in the corporate world without adhering to CG code or guidelines but on the other hand, the SMEs listed on the international platform (FTSE-AIM), do not have proper CG guidelines to follow (Abor & Adjasi, 2007). Before 2018, according to the rules of LSE, AIM companies were not obliged to follow the CG guidelines because LSE believes that the UK corporate governance code may not be appropriate for SMEs due to the different nature and size of growing companies (Palacín-Sánchez, *et al.*, 2019; Afrifa & Tauringana, 2015c). However, according to the recent amendment in the rules of AIM companies, SMEs are now required to follow a CG code, either the UK corporate governance code or the QCA code (Chambers, 2017). As this is the latest amendment, no empirical evidence has yet been found, hence this study contributes to the body of knowledge.

1.3 Research Problems

The prominent reason behind the fall of corporations was the shortcoming of corporate governance measures in the companies that results in economic and corporate crises. During the period of crises, the board of directors were criticised the most for reducing value for shareholders (Adeyemi & Fagbemi, 2010). It is considered that they were not performing their functions cautiously and that failure was due to weak control over the managers, which meant they got a chance to pursue their self-interest. Moreover, it has been seen that the board of directors escaped from their accountability towards the shareholders (Darko, *et al.*, 2016). As a result of this, numerous reforms have been implemented regarding the measures of CG, the board of directors and their accountability to bring transparency in firms and to protect the investors (Uadiale, 2010). Despite the tremendous development in the concept of CG, the researcher found the following main problems to address in this thesis:

- The research about the concept of CG has been concentrated on large firms only and leading to an expectation that SMEs would voluntarily follow the same measures of CG. In reality, SMEs need guidance about the required structure of CG in their firms according to the nature and size of their businesses for better financial performance, to gain and retain investors. Although there have been several studies conducted about

CG and financial performance, little research has investigated the impact of corporate governance measures on the financial performance of SMEs listed in FTSE-AIM (Mallin & Ow-Yong, 2013). So, there is a problem that needs to be researched. Due to the lack of an appropriate CG code for SMEs, these companies have been advised to voluntarily follow the main UK corporate governance code which may be useless to the different structures of SMEs in comparison to large premium listed companies in LSE (Afrifa & Tauringana, 2015c). The impact of an ineffective corporate governance structure has been seen by the world in the form of business collapses and so guidance is critical. While keeping the overall contribution of SMEs in mind, CG guidance is necessary and needed for their businesses, to avoid any crises in the future.

- Further, this study covers the gap in the literature about those SMEs which are listed in the Alternative Investment Market. This international market launched in 1995 with a set of 10 companies as a sub-market of LSE and showed tremendous growth over 25 years; it now includes 850 companies with a combined market capitalisation of £104bn (London Stock Exchange, 2018). Despite this, nominal research exists about this market (Afrifa & Tauringana, 2015c; Mallin & Ow-Yong, 2013; Mallin & Ow-Yong, 2012). In addition, by addressing this research problem, the respective study will also be able to guide SMEs with their CG structure and explain the influence of CG principles on the financial performance of SMEs.
- Another research problem is related to the recent amendment made by the LSE in 2018 to the rules of AIM-listed companies. These more recent rules state that the UK listed AIM companies must follow any CG code and mention all the details in their annual reports. Consequently, the Quoted Companies Alliance (QCA) published a QCA corporate governance code specifically for SMEs and revealed that their guidelines follow UK corporate governance code (Chambers, 2017). However, they have specified ten main easily followed guidelines for SMEs (Burges Salmon, 2018) and no existing empirical study has yet considered the QCA code and financial performance of SMEs. Therefore, this study is the first to address this gap by evaluating the impact of guidelines of the QCA CG code particularly concerning the parameters of the board of directors on the financial performance of the UK listed AIM companies. Additionally, this study also evaluates the guidelines of the UK CG code (again in the parameters of the BOD) which the QCA did not include in their QCA CG code. Therefore, in the end, based on statistically proven results, this study is providing recommendations to SMEs on how they can enhance their financial

performance by applying CG principles. In the next section, the rationale for this study is discussed in detail.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study is significant because SMEs listed in FTSE-AIM and authorities (QCA and LSE) are working on publishing improved versions of CG codes to enhance the CG structure of the companies. The researcher was personally motivated to conduct this research due to a major Satyam collapse that happened in India. At a very young age, she witnessed the collapse of a company that affected the whole country. During that time, she observed an echo in her surroundings that nowadays in general people become self-centred & selfish, neglecting their responsibilities, performing fraudulent activities, and chasing prestige and money (Niazi & Ali, 2015). However, this was only one side of the coin, and she understood the other side while pursuing her master's degree, discovering the term 'Corporate Governance'. During her studies, she understood the significance of the corporate governance structure and observed that various business collapses occurred due to weak CG structures in the companies. To explore thoroughly the concept of CG, the reason behind the collapses, and how the CG practices influence the financial performance of the SMEs was of deep and profound interest. Hence, this study is both an answer to her curiosity and when disseminated, will help the SMEs to understand the significance of an effective CG structure to enhance their financial performance.

Specifically, SMEs have been chosen for this research because SMEs play a crucial role in the economic development of a country by providing employment and generating income. Although SMEs drive most of the businesses in many countries, their life is like a bubble due to limited financial resources and managerial incapacity. All these factors restrict the growth of an organisation. Due to the globally recognised collapses, investors expect every company, either large or small, to bring transparency in their firms by applying a suitable CG structure (Arora & Singh, 2020). Under such pressure, SMEs had to follow the UK Corporate Governance Code which was originally made for large companies as per their requirement, size and nature. However, there are no consensus results showing that the financial performance of SMEs improves after applying the UK CG code (Mallin & Ow-Yong, 2012). Although, several empirical studies have highlighted the importance of CG structure in a company for better growth and to improve the financial performance of companies (Adesanmi, *et al.*, 2019; Adeyemi & Fagbemi, 2010), there is a dearth of

literature concerning SMEs listed in FTSE-AIM. Furthermore, as explained in the above section, less attention has been provided to the corporate governance practices of SMEs as the area of focus is always large companies (Aggarwal, *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, this study aims to address the gap in the literature by investigating the impact of guidelines provided by different CG codes (under the parameter of the board of directors) on the financial performance of the SMEs listed in the UK (FTSE-AIM). The next section of this chapter will discuss the aim of the study, the set objectives to achieve the aim and the research questions.

1.5 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was: *To investigate the association between internal corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance of the UK-listed AIM companies and provide recommendations to enhance the financial performance of the SMEs.*

Further, to achieve the aim of this study, the following four objectives were formulated:

1.5.1 Objectives of the Study

O1: To elaborate on the emergence of the concept of corporate governance and the development of the corporate governance structure in various developed and developing countries by reviewing the existing literature.

O2: To evaluate the theoretical underpinnings of corporate governance by studying the relevant secondary sources that lead to the development of a conceptual framework for this study.

O3: To examine the association between internal corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance of the listed SMEs in the UK by testing the hypotheses.

O4: To provide recommendations on how SMEs listed in FTSE-AIM can practice the CG guidelines to enhance their financial performance.

1.6 Research Questions

This research was conducted to answer the following four research questions derived from the literature review:

1. How has corporate governance emerged and what measures have been taken to develop the corporate governance structure by countries around the world?

2. What are the theoretical underpinnings of corporate governance that lead to the development of the conceptual framework for this study?
3. Is there any relationship between internal corporate governance mechanisms and the financial performance of the listed SMEs in the UK?
4. How can CG practice be improved while enhancing the financial performance of the UK listed AIM companies?

1.7 Scope of the Research

To conduct this research, the data were collected from the website of the London Stock Exchange, FAME (financial database), website and published annual reports of the sample companies for the year 2015.

1.8 Research Methodology

To answer the research questions, the researcher required a systematic procedure to follow step by step which is called research methodology. According to [Saunders, et al. \(2019\)](#), to solve the research problem, there must be a relationship between the methods selected by the researcher. The research question raised in this thesis is discussed in the previous chapter. To achieve the objectives, initially, the researcher explores the related literature about the emergence of CG, the overall development of this concept in different countries and the theoretical underpinnings of CG, based on the first and second research questions that have been answered. Further, the positivist paradigm has been selected which leads to the selection of the deductive approach. To answer the third research question, a quantitative research design was selected to collect numerical data from the financial database, websites of LSE and a selected sample of companies and the researcher used the annual reports of the companies to collect data about their boards of directors. At the beginning of the research, the researcher was facing difficulty in terms of getting access to the financial database. Therefore, the researcher decided to start collecting data from a raw list of all the listed companies in the LSE (obtained from LSE via email). However, once the researcher got access to FAME (financial database) from the city library, the data of this study were triangulated by using both ways. Further, Gretl software has been used to run the analysis. From the systematic review, the researcher found that not many studies have discussed the need for a proper CG structure for SMEs, in fact not even for listed ones specifically in the FTSE-AIM. The next section of this chapter discusses the originality of this research.

1.9 Originality of the Research

In doctoral theses, the originality of research/study is highly essential. It indicates the development of actual thought or work that does not necessarily mean fresh knowledge (Gill & Dolan, 2015). It can be a researcher's approach methodology, implications, research design or presentation of research itself (Catling & Butt, 2016). The originality of the research is based on the theoretical and practical contributions made which are explained below.

1.9.1 Theoretical Contribution

- This study contributes to the body of knowledge by adding information on the impact of corporate governance on the financial performance of the listed SMEs in the UK.
- This research was conducted on a sample of the UK listed FTSE-AIM companies. This market has been established in 1995, but even so, research conducted with this population is rare.

1.9.2 Empirical Contribution

- This study empirically tested the guidelines of the QCA CG code (under the parameters of the board of directors) in relation to the financial performance of SMEs. As per the knowledge of the researcher, the QCA CG code which directly applied to AIM-listed SMEs has not been specifically tested as this was published quite recently in the year 2018. Hence, this is the first study that empirically tested the principles of the QCA CG code in relation to the financial performance of the AIM-listed companies.

1.9.3 Practical Contribution

- This study is beneficial for AIM-listed SMEs because the benefits of following a CG code are explained. Moreover, SMEs can enhance their financial performance while practising a good CG structure.
- Additionally, this research is beneficial for the CG and SME policymakers in the UK such as the Quoted Companies Alliance (QCA), London Stock Exchange (LSE) and Financial Reporting Council (FRC). Henceforth, when the code is reviewed by policymakers advance knowledge of the impact of principles related to BOD on the FP of the SMEs will be known and improved upon.

1.10 Limitations of the Research

- This study investigated the impact of the QCA corporate governance code on the financial performance of SMEs with the parameters of the board of directors only. In total, ten guidelines have been suggested by the QCA CG code, but this study is restricted to the guidelines related to BOD.
- Another limitation is, the data collection time was limited as the researcher tried for a few months to get access to financial databases. Therefore, the aim was achieved by performing a cross-sectional study.
- Out of the targeted population, the researcher had to reduce the sample according to the availability of all the required data.

1.11 Structure of Thesis

This section discusses the structure of the whole thesis as follows:

Chapter 2 of this study is focused on literature about the concept of corporate governance. Initially, a whole set of definitions was reviewed about CG and a specific one selected. Then the researcher diagnosed the major collapses contributing to an understanding of CG's role in those business collapses. Further, this chapter explores the overall development of CG or measures taken by developed or developing countries in the form of CG codes to safeguard the interests of investors. Furthermore, it covers an interpretation of the theoretical underpinnings of corporate governance. The review continues with the researcher exploring the role of SMEs in the UK, the development of the AIM market and the CG structure in the SMEs listed in the UK. Based on all the information about SMEs and CG, the researcher developed the conceptual framework for this study, clarified the research gap and included hypotheses to test.

Chapter 3 covers the research methodology by explaining the relevant techniques used in this study. Among all the research paradigms, the positivist paradigm was selected and justification was provided for the selection. This leads to the selection of a research approach, design and methods. Moreover, the time horizon, sampling techniques, and issues faced by the researcher while collecting data were also discussed. In addition, the data analysis techniques and ethics of the research were also explained.

Chapter 4 discusses the data analysis and findings of the study. Descriptive and inferential data analysis techniques were used in this research. The researcher describes the variables, performs normality tests, presents validity and reliability tests, analyses the descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, discusses the regression analysis and finally conducts ANOVA analysis. In the end, this chapter discusses all the hypotheses based on the findings of the analysis.

Chapter 5 concludes the main findings and discusses the originality of this research. In general, mixed results were found between the variables of CG and financial performance of SMEs. However, Board Gender Diversity was positively and significantly associated with the financial performance of SMEs and the presence of non-executive directors on the board was negatively related to the financial performance. In addition to this, each research question is answered in detail, recommendations provided for the SMEs, policymakers & future researchers, and the limitations and contributions of this study are discussed.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter systematically reviews the literature related to CG, SMEs and financial performance of companies listed in FTSE-AIM. The whole chapter is mainly divided into eight sections, each with subsections. In section one, the emergence of the concept of corporate governance (CG), its origin and multiple definitions are explored. To fulfil the purpose of this research, the definition provided by Cassidy (2003) has been selected to define corporate governance because this includes both perspectives of CG: agency and stakeholder approach. Further, section two explores the major business demises from 1995 to 2018 and the reasons for these collapses. This section clearly shows that CG structure is still weak as corporate collapses are continuously happening not only in developing countries but in developed countries as well. Section three illustrates the overall development of CG in different countries, specifically the development of major codes of corporate governance in the UK and discusses the UK CG development in detail because the sample of data contains the UK-listed AIM companies.

To gain a deeper understanding of SMEs in the UK, section four explores the role of SMEs in the economic development of the country. Additionally, the international FTSE-AIM market and the CG structure of the companies registered in the AIM market was also elaborated to understand the current regulations of the CG applied to listed SMEs in the UK. Section five identifies the theoretical underpinnings of corporate governance, where the author discusses various theories of CG such as agency theory, stakeholder theory, stewardship theory, and resource-dependency theory informing the selection of the theoretical approach for this research. The conceptual framework of this study was developed after reviewing the literature about CG and the financial performance of SMEs and rules and regulations of different CG codes for various companies, which are presented in section six. The gaps in the literature related to the scarcity of studies in respect to CG structure in SMEs and the impact on financial performance is recognised in section seven. Finally, with the assistance of the theoretical and conceptual framework, section eight formulates the hypotheses for this study to test.

2.2 The Emergence of Corporate Governance

Undoubtedly, the concept of corporate governance is as old as trade itself even in the simplest form of doing business, but the expression is relatively new. The independent variables of this research belong to corporate governance and the whole research will focus on its relationship with the financial performance of small and medium size enterprises. Therefore, it is necessary to understand and examine the emergence and origin of the word corporate governance which also helps to achieve the first objective of this study. CG is made with the bundling of two words: corporate and governance (Jovanović & Grujić, 2016). Henceforth, this section will depict the meaning of corporate and governance individually in detail.

2.2.1 The Corporate Concept in Corporate Governance

Corporate governance is essentially related to those legal and entrepreneurial structures that look after the internal integrity of institutions. The presumption here is that an institution is an organisation and therefore, also known as a corporation. The word ‘corporate’ is an alternative to the word ‘company’ which means a self-imposed entity created and organised to run a business. It is a Latin word that comes from the word ‘corporatus’ traditionally from ‘corporare’ to form a single body (Shah, 2014). Thus, a corporation represents a group of people who act as a single body to carry on the business. Additionally, Chapman, *et al.* (2009) commented on the organisation as per their perspective, that organisations are not only formally constituted bodies, but this term also includes alliances, advisory groups, and so on. An organisation or an institution is bound to act or run its functions under the rules and bundle of contracts. Moreover, corporates are authorised by legal constitutions and protected by legal standards of the land where established or by the government. Hence, the repercussions of such legal constraints or defence may be restricted to the national boundaries or may not, depending upon agreed global regulations. Though there is no specific definition for organisation or corporation, however, Arrow, 1994 cited in Choudhury & Hoque (2006, p.117) defined the concept of corporate or organisation and related it to corporate governance:

An organization is a group of individuals seeking to achieve some common goals, or, in a different language, to maximize an objective function. Each member has objectives of his own, in general not coincident with those of

the organization. Each member also has some range of decisions to make within limits set partly by the environment external to the organization and partly by the decision of members.

Hence, it is clear from the above definition that members of the corporation need to make decisions to achieve personal as well as companies' goals. The corporation needs to abide by the principles of corporate governance to make fair decisions that could provide benefits to the shareholders. This concept also leads this research to find out how the financial performance of the companies can be affected by the acceptance or non-acceptance of guidelines of corporate governance. Additionally, three control forces exist, according to [Jensen \(1993\)](#), that influence the decisions of the members of the companies which are capital markets, product and factor markets and internal control system headed by the board of directors. This study will focus on the fourth control force which is internal control by the board of the companies and its effect on the financial performance of organisations.

2.2.2 The Governance Concept in Corporate Governance

The textbooks of corporate governance often provide the history of a linguistic form of the word 'governance' by tracing its development since its earliest occurrence in classical Latin Greek word as 'gubernare', stated as management or government which again comes from the ancient Greek word 'kybernao', meaning to lead, to direct, to guide, to play the role of a commander or pilot ([Bhattacharyya, 2016a](#); [Dibra, 2016](#)). Initially, [Shah & Napier \(2019\)](#) mentioned the drastic change in the use of the word 'governance' throughout the period. Since the 1980s, the notion of governance has extensively been used to depict strategies and policies nationally and internationally ([Krahmann, 2003](#)). However, in regard to a particular definition of governance, there is no universally accepted definition of governance but a distinct range of points of view exist concerning the meaning of governance ([Singh, 2008](#)).

The World Bank, in 1992, attempted to explain governance according to which there are three different perspectives of governance; (a) the form of the political regime; (b) the regard of countrymen and the state for the establishments which administer the social and economic discussions among them; and (c) the capacity of governments to design, formulate, and implement policies and discharge functions ([Weiss, 2000](#)). On the other hand, the White Paper on governance describes it as a set of rules, procedures, or manner that could influence how privileges or powers are employed, more specifically with regard to openness, participation, accountability, effectiveness, and coherence ([Atkinson, 2002](#)). Nowadays, the

word governance becomes a fashionable and trending term that is frequently used in numerous ways, covering a huge number of public and private organisations.

According to [Stame \(2006\)](#), governance particularly refers to the ways of guiding, or steering the society or an organisation. Further, [Shah & Napier \(2019\)](#) relates the concept of ‘governor’ with corporate governance. It originates from the Latin word gubernator, meaning a pilot who is controlling and managing a ship. In the early days of Britain, the most experienced and senior person of an entity or an organisation is known to be a governor who was held responsible for all the decisions of an executive nature which had been taken through regular general meetings on an annual basis as same as CEOs of companies these days. Therefore, the phenomenon of a governor in early organisations or establishments is quite like the governance system of modern companies. Moreover, [Cheffins \(2013\)](#) reveals that corporate governance itself is captured from a political context by scholars of neoclassical economics.

However, the core of corporate governance is the relationship between the board and management of the company, specifically the board’s relationship with the CEO, and there are loopholes of conflict due to their interests in the company. But that problem could be reduced or eliminated with the clever drafting of contracts rather than implying external regulations ([Chumakov, 2014](#)). Further, governance equates with concepts like justice and law. It never comes naturally or instinctively but involves a human consciousness that sets the objective to achieve creatively made policies and implement plans to obtain the target ([Bhattacharyya, 2016a](#)). Still, governance could be varied from country to country for different cultural values, political, social, and traditional circumstances. In the same way, developed and developing countries can be distinct in terms of their governance due to unlike cultural and economic contexts ([Yusoff & Alhajiv, 2012](#)).

However, the analysis of corporate governance involves the governance of all corporations whether public or private limited companies or profit or non-profit organisations. But this study is specifically focusing on FTSE-AIMs (Alternative Investment Market) listed companies in the UK to analyse the internal corporate governance system of SMEs. As corporate governance depicts the relationship between stakeholders which can be used to determine and regulate the strategic direction and evaluate the performance of establishments ([Anand, 2019](#)), similarly this research examines the relationship between the attributes of corporate governance and financial performance of registered SMEs in the

London Stock Exchange. Further, the following section covers a detailed discussion about the meaning and competing definitions of corporate governance worldwide.

2.3 Competing Definitions of Corporate Governance

Corporate governance appeared as a way of thinking aeons before the formal use of this phrase. This study concentrates on the aspect of corporate governance and how it is related to the financial performance of SMEs. Therefore, it is essential to elaborate knowledge about it, hence a discussion has been provided in this section on the available definitions of corporate governance. It will cover the different points of view of scholarly authors and authorities for corporate governance. To be specific, the term “Corporate Governance” came into existence in the 1980s, and gradually, its importance enlarged in the early years of the 21st century (Jovanović & Grujić, 2016). It is obvious that with the continuous increase in the number and size of enterprises, the requirement for effective and efficient management is also maximised.

In the UK, the term “Corporate Governance” was first used in papers presented by Eells in 1967 at a conference (Mees, 2015); within four decades in July 2010, Google Scholar received 287,000 hits with ‘corporate governance’ as a keyword (Brown, *et al.*, 2011). In respect to definition, several authors have attempted to define the term corporate governance and discuss it from diverse contexts (Wjeeh & Muneeza, 2012). Still, there is no universally accepted definition of corporate governance (Ahmad & Omar, 2016). After numerous corporate failures in 1991, a committee was set up by the Financial Reporting Council, the London Stock Exchange, and the accountancy profession to consider the financial aspects of corporate governance (Cadbury, 1992). The first report issued by the Cadbury Committee contains the highly quoted definition of corporate governance, mentioned in Table 2.1 with the definitions of other authors which provide a comparative understanding of the concept of corporate governance.

Table 2.1: Competing Definitions of Corporate Governance

<i>Author</i>	<i>Definition</i>
Cadbury (1992)	Corporate governance is the system by which companies are directed and controlled
Garvey & Swan (1994)	Governance determines how the firm's top decision-makers (executives) administer contracts
Hart (1995)	Corporate governance issues arise in an organisation whenever two conditions are present. First, there is an agency problem, or conflict of interest, involving members of the organisation – these might be owners, managers, workers, or consumers. Second, transaction costs are such that this agency problem cannot be dealt with through a contract
Shleifer, <i>et al.</i> (1997)	Shareholders are at the centre and the utmost responsibility of the BOD is to provide them with the best returns on their investment.
John & Senbet (1998)	Embrace those devices, mechanisms, and structures which act as a check on managerial self-serving behaviour
OECD (2004)	A set of rules and practices that govern the relationship between the managers and shareholders of corporations, as well as stakeholders like employees and creditors
Charreaux (1996) cited in Bonnafous-Boucher (2005)	Covers all the mechanisms whose effect is to limit powers and influence decisions, or, in other words, which govern the behaviour of companies and define their discretionary boundaries
Choudhury & Hoque (2006)	It means legal constraints, penalties, and rewards, transparency, and disclosures on operations, revenues, and expenditures.
Mallin (2011)	Emphasises the shareholders as well as on the stakeholder groups which contribute to the growth and financial stability of the corporation

Mostovicz, <i>et al.</i> (2011)	CG creates an environment that prompts individuals to act as per their worldviews and stand accountable for their decisions.
World Bank (2013) cited in Ahmad & Omar (2016)	Corporate governance refers to the set of rules and incentives by which the management of a company is directed and controlled. It refers to the way rights and responsibilities are distributed among the board, company management, shareholders, and other stakeholders. However, while policies and documentation are of undeniable importance, these are not enough to ensure good governance. The actions of companies toward promoting corporate transparency and accountability speak louder than words.
Huillier (2014)	The systematic provision of some measure of control over the actions of the agents (managers and subcontractors) to safeguard the interest of the principal (shareholders and investors)
Simpson (2014)	A mechanism to direct and manage an organisation, to be transparent and accountable.
Mees (2015)	Discuss the business reforms with a target to improve the financial performance and calibre of the boards and the executive teams of the top listed companies, afterwards only concentrate to boost the confidence of the investors
FRC (2016)	Related to actions and a set of rules of boards which are different from the day-to-day task of management.
Nerantzidis & Tsamis (2017)	Corporate governance is a system available within the organisation. It defines policies, processes and guidelines
Al-Sartawi (2018)	A system that can develop the ability of organisations towards disclosing appropriate and related information enabling decision-makers such as representatives of shareholders to make well-informed decisions
Cucari (2019)	Corporate governance provides a mechanism to efficiently direct the firm. It deals with the rules

regarding how to govern the rights and responsibilities of the board of directors.

Adedeji, *et al.* (2020)

It is an instrument for sustaining the quality of life of firms based on the needs of the stakeholders such as the management, shareholders, employees, suppliers, creditors, consumers, government and their agencies and the public.

Source: Author

Despite the variations shown in definitions of CG in Table 2.1, they are broadly connected to either agency or stakeholder perspective. Agency theory supports the definition of the [Cadbury Report \(1992\)](#) mentioned above, which mainly focused on two words: directed and controlled; the former one is for the board of directors who are responsible for planning the objectives of the company and directing the subordinates to achieve the set goals; the latter one is for shareholders who appoint the board of directors and auditors to satisfy themselves that an adequate governance structure is in place ([Letza, et al., 2008](#)). This traditional definition is focusing on the return to investors by applying corporate governance mechanisms ([Shleifer, et al., 1997](#); [Simpson & Yaw, 2014](#); [Huillier, 2014](#); [Short, et al., 1999](#)). The requirement of an effective and efficient corporate governance framework originates from the agency problem which can take place in the company when managers pursue their personal goals while ignoring the interest of the shareholders in the desire for power and prestige ([Jensen & Meckling, 1976](#); [Pletz & Upson, 2019](#)).

Whereas, [Young & Thyil \(2008\)](#), specifically, proposed in their research paper to glance within the firms, their environment, labour markets, product markets, and capital markets, basically suggesting looking at corporate governance from the stakeholder perspective. Additionally, in most cases, CG defines in a wide sense, the body of rules, regulations, and principles which either guide the board of directors or limit their actions concerning shareholders or stakeholders ([Bonnafeous-Boucher, 2005](#)). Moreover, an effective corporate governance structure is also required to keep the outsiders and insiders of the corporation in discipline to attain the set objectives and this can be only possible by putting in place the set standards, transparency requirements, monitoring and compliance mechanisms in the company ([Ararat & Ugur, 2003](#)). Hence this study adopts the following definition by [Cassidy \(2003, p.33\)](#) influenced by both perspectives (agency and stakeholder).

“Corporate governance is the creation and implementation of processes adopted by a properly authorized and constitutes board seeking to optimize the return to shareholders whilst satisfying the legitimate expectations of stakeholders who include employees, suppliers, and customers as well as members of those communities with whom their business activities interface.”

Moreover, [Abor & Adjasi \(2007\)](#) have a view that corporate governance can assist SMEs as well by applying better management practices, effective internal auditing, and numerous opportunities for continuous growth. It looks like the research in this field is at an early stage, hence, it is essential to focus much more attention on SMEs, as a result of which this research is specifically paying attention to the listed SMEs in the London Stock Exchange. Further, section 2.4 will elaborate on the major collapses that have occurred due to ineffective CG which discloses the ultimate importance of CG in firms.

2.4 Corporate Collapses

In the world, the main objective of each business is to earn a profit, to grow and expand and for this, businesses need to attract investors for funding. Generally, before investment, investors need to make sure that the company in which they are investing is financially sound, is well managed and profitable for which they'll glance at the published annual reports or the accounts of the company where they expect that they will be able to see the true and clear picture of company's current position ([Mallin, 2019](#)). Imagine what will happen if a company provides false information in its accounts or does not show an accurate picture of its position. Due to the fraudulent activity and demise, the company will breach the trust of the investors, and surely, it will give birth to financial or non-financial strains and hardships to further affect the community, employees, customers, government and sometimes even in big collapses, affect the international community as well ([Marwa & Zairi, 2008](#)).

Initially, it is vital to understand what is corporate collapse. And some examples of corporate collapses will be discussed in chronological order with some of the recent collapses and an analysis of the possible reasons for those demises occurring. This study includes this information as it will provide a deep understanding of the main causes of the failures of major corporations which were the main reason for the development of corporate

governance. Moreover, if the weak CG system in a company affects the financial condition of the company and results in bankruptcy then it is useful to study the major corporate collapses that have happened previously which will contribute to understanding the importance of applying CG principles in the listed companies. Further, the most recent collapse included in this study happened in 2018 in the UK, clearly setting the example that voluntary compliance with principles of CG is unable to restrict companies from fraudulent activities and this shows the gap in the development of CG.

2.4.1 *Understanding Corporate Collapse*

According to [Bonini & Boraschi \(2010\)](#), those incidents which publicise worldwide and report allegations of managerial misdoing, disgrace, or humiliation on the part of one or more members of an enterprise are called corporate failures. Specifically, corporate scandals help to explain the actual managerial activities and accounting practices of the firm in comparison to the false image made by top management or the board of the company before. General instances of misleading information or fraudulent behaviour are accounting frauds, special purpose entities, delay in revealing essential information, corruption, and include all those unlawful activities which risk the investment of the shareholders or hurt them ([Grandori, 2004](#)). In practice, the focus is always on meeting the financial objectives of the company rather than the relationship with those who interact with the business as internal and external stakeholders ([Hurn, 2008](#)). Though investors invest to gain good returns, it is high time to understand that ethical decisions are important to gain a competitive advantage. This is also the view of [Elenkov & Fileva \(2006\)](#) who believe that corporate failures are closely associated with a lack of information about prevailing economic ideology and cultural values.

In the same way, [Louie \(2007\)](#) relates corporate failures with the greed of the management as in the author's opinion, misrepresenting financial information and frauds are their ultimate ways to hide the rapid failings in managing issues related to accounting controls; therefore, the attribute of company demise is their greediness instead of those means (false accounting reports) which they perform to hide their intentions. Meanwhile, some other authors relate corporate destruction with the failure to implement good corporate governance practices and principles: accountability, integrity, efficiency, and transparency ([Mardjono, 2005](#)). On the other hand, [Sheth \(2007\)](#) indicates that a well-established or successful company often attains suicidal manners that harm the prosperity of the company notably

arrogance, greediness, denial, a deceitful attitude, unethical conduct, and volume obsession. Further, this section will include a description of some of the major collapses between the period 1995-2018 which clearly shows that instead of the existing principles of corporate governance, collapses are still happening. This means there must be some gaps left and therefore, we need more development in this area of research.

2.4.2 Examples of Corporate Collapses

As per the above discussion, corporate collapses in one way or another affect us all. For instance, shareholders, employees, suppliers, and leave an economic impact on the national and international community. Therefore, to understand why corporate demises have occurred and are still occurring, despite companies seeming to be doing well, evaluation of some of the previous collapses from 1995 to 2018 are required. Hence, some notorious examples of large and well-known collapses will be discussed with the details of the company's performance at the time of the collapse, weaknesses found in the companies during investigation and measures taken by the authorities to restrict the collapses.

2.4.2.1 Barings Bank

Barings bank was one of England's well established and oldest banks which collapsed in February 1995 and that happened due to the actions of one man, Nick Leeson, who was in charge of the Singapore branch (Tabalujan, 1997; Rodrigues, 2015). Soon it became public that Leeson had speculated away £827 million in Baring's name and the losses were so huge that the oldest merchant bank of the city collapsed (Titcomb, 2015). Nick Leeson took advantage of the weak internal control system of the bank to disguise the fact that it was making losses for a long time (The House of Commons, 1995). Moreover, the experienced staff who had a good understanding of procedures and processes were unable to expose the company to such a massive financial disaster (Herring, 2005; Matthews, 2005). Afterwards, the Singapore International Monetary Exchange (SIMEX) intensified its rules and regulations in the wake of the collapse of Barings (Vanasco, 1998).

2.4.2.2 Enron

Enron was the world's most magnificent company and was ranked as a 10-top company in the list of Fortune in the USA. Before its popular collapse, Enron had a healthy profit of US \$979 million and was worth \$80 billion in market capitalisation (Mallin, 2019). However, today Enron is the largest bankruptcy in US history. This collapse happened due to bad investments, excess leveraging, and disclosure of many debts that were reported in financial

statements but inappropriately (Reinstein, *et al.*, 2006; Grandori, 2004). Inclusive to top management, mid-level accountants, and Arthur Andersen were also equally responsible for the failure of the company as unfortunately, they were unable to question the board due to their benefits as they earned \$700,000 annually to manage the accounts of Enron and immediately after being found guilty this firm also collapsed (BBC News, 2002; Thomas, 2002; Mardjono, 2005). Overall, corporate governance in Enron was incompetent in almost every manner and aspect (Dibra, 2016).

2.4.2.3 *Health International Holdings (HIH Insurance)*

The HIH Insurance disaster was one of Australia's biggest corporate failures (Mak, *et al.*, 2005). Just before the collapse, HIH was the second-largest general insurer in Australia, comprised of 217 subsidiaries, as per the annual reports in 2000 total assets of \$8.0 billion and net assets worth \$900 million (Kehl, 2001) whereas, at the time of collapse a debt worth \$5.3 billion was declared (Allan, 2006; du Plessis, 2003). As per press reports, top management got the information about fraudulent accounting practices, but still did not make any effort to solve the problem. As a result of this, the company collapsed on March 15, 2001 (Reinstein, *et al.*, 2006), and moved towards full liquidation from provisional liquidation on August 27, 2001 (Cheng & Seeger, 2012). The demise of HIH insurance grabs the attention of the accounting profession, in terms of the auditor's role, and the independence of the audit committee (Mirshekary, *et al.*, 2005).

2.4.2.4 *Parmalat*

Parmalat was ranked in eighth position in the list of Italy's largest companies (Melis, 2005; Ferrarini & Giudici, 2006; Bava & Devalle, 2012b). However, in December 2003, the Parmalat group collapsed after recognising non-payment of a bond worth €150 million (besides showing a large number of cash reserves in the accounts of the company) (Marchini, *et al.*, 2019; Hurn, 2008) and the debt was estimated at around £10 billion (Sorensen & Miller, 2017). In 2005, the CEO (Calisto Tanzi) and some independent auditors were found guilty (Reinstein, *et al.*, 2006; Dibra, 2016). This corporate failure brought many changes to the laws, regulations, and corporate governance code in Italy, intending to toughen the governance system in Italy (Bava & Devalle, 2012a).

2.4.2.5 *Satyam*

Satyam computer services limited (Satyam) was the fourth-largest company in the country (India) as per its revenue and was providing services in 66 countries (Singh, *et al.*, 2010). In the year 2003-2004, Satyam generated sales worth ₹25,415.4 million and by 2008, the company's sales revenue had grown three-fold (Bhasin, 2013). However, in 2009, the CEO confessed in front of the board of directors that he had tampered with company accounts for more than seven years (Zhang & Rajagopalan, 2009; Bhasin, 2016), overstated assets and cash by \$ 1.47 and \$1.04 billion respectively that in reality did not exist and understated liabilities as a result of which share price significantly fell (Muniraju, *et al.*, 2011; Sharma, 2015). While running after prestige, Mr Raju violated all the rules and regulations, neglected his responsibilities towards employees, customers, and the community (Niazi & Ali, 2015).

2.4.2.6 *China Forestry*

In the year 2008-2009, the Carlyle group from the USA and Switzerland-based partner group invested in this company (O'Keeffe & Steger, 2011). However, soon the auditors of the company informed the board about irregularities in the books of accounts, false bank statements, irrational documents for the insurance policy and fraudulent logging permits that had the worst impact on business operations and financial results. As a result, the CEO got arrested for the embezzlement of cash (Leung, 2011; South China Morning Post, n.d.; Kirilova, 2018). In 2017, the Securities and Future Commission of Hong Kong handled unspecified damages for market misconduct and sued the company with its two co-founders, and also KPMG (auditor) for \$166 million (Wong & Robertson, 2019).

2.4.2.7 *Olympus Corporation*

Olympus Corporation is a well-established Japanese manufacturer that deals in optics and reprography products. In 2011, Michael Woodford replaced the previous CEO (Tsuyoshi Kikukawa) (Pavlo, 2012) and reported to the British fraud office about the mishandling of accounts (Mckenna, 2012). In the investigation, it became public that accounts were manipulated and money had been used to cover up the losses on investments dating back to the 1990s (Mallin, 2019). In 2012, executives were ordered to pay 700 million yen (Prusa, 2016) and in 2017, again executives were commanded to pay US \$529 million in the form of damages due to their actions (BBC News, 2017). Many authors suggest that this incident in Japan may lead to improve the standards of corporate governance practices (Farrell, 2015).

2.4.2.8 Carillion

Carillion Plc is a multinational facilities management and construction services company (Thomas, 2018). This scandal is one of the most recent scandals that happened internationally with less than £30 million in the bank and more than £2 billion in liabilities (Burgees, 2018). This company grabbed the attention of the critics when, in crisis (write down £845 million), (Morrison, 2018) the remuneration committee paid higher salaries (CEO received £1.5 million) and bonuses (£245,000) to top management and senior staff (Mor, 2018). Besides, the external auditor of the company, KPMG, was also under inquiry by the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) (Neate & Davies, 2020; Thurley, *et al.*, 2018) and sued for £250 million by a government agency in charge of the liquidation of Carillion (Smith, 2020). The stakeholders of the company were deeply affected due to this collapse, such as previous and current employees, and its sub-contractors (Wearden, 2018).

The above-discussed examples of high-profile corporate collapses that happened in the UK, USA, Europe, India, China, Australia, and Japan had and continue to have significant implications nationally and internationally. In addition to this, it also provides a set of shortcomings, in the way that the companies were run and managed. Below is Table 2.2 which summarises the deficiencies in the operating manner of the above discussed corporate collapses.

Table 2.2: Reasons for the Collapse of Companies

<i>Company Name</i>	<i>Year of Collapse</i>	<i>Country</i>	<i>Industry</i>	<i>Reasons for Failure</i>
Barings Bank	1995	United Kingdom (UK)	Bank	Mismanagement of resources An ineffective internal control system Lack of supervision Fraudulent accounting reports
Enron	2001	United States of America (USA)	Utility	Lack of independence in the board Lack of independence in the audit committee Tax evasions Directors of greed Misappropriations Corruption

				False accounting measures
HIH Insurance	2001	Australia	Insurance	Misappropriation Regulatory failures Fraudulent financial reporting Lack of transparency
Parmalat	2003	Italy	Food	Ownership concentration Lack of independent board Delay in disclosing information Corruption Embezzlement
Satyam	2009	India	Information Technology (IT)	Greed for money and power Lack of ethical standards Falsifying accounts Competition Lack of appropriate disclosure of information
China Forestry	2011	China	Forest & Paper Products	Pilfering False accounting measures Lack of social responsibility Ownership and shareholder conflict
Olympus Corporation	2011	Japan	Optics and Reprography	Lack of board independence Inappropriate accounting standards Regulatory breaches Dishonesty
Carillion	2018	United Kingdom (UK)	Construction and Facility management	The greed of fame and power Mis-pricing contracts Higher debt levels High remuneration of top management Dividend payments at no profit Financial difficulties

Source: Author

Consequent to the above discussed corporate failures, in the last two decades, authors have specifically focused on the concept of corporate governance and related it with the reasons

for failure. Specifically, after the Enron scandal, there is more concentration on corporate governance issues such as lack of transparency, lack of independence, and fraudulent financial reports. Governments of almost all the countries are enforcing rules and regulations related to their corporate governance structure. Further, in the next section, the development of corporate governance in different countries will be discussed via examining the codes of multiple countries. Besides other countries, this study thoroughly covers the development of CG codes in the UK as this thesis specifically concentrates on the corporate governance structure in SMEs listed in the UK. Similarly, next section will discuss the measures taken by different countries to develop the corporate governance in the form of codes of CG and regular amendments in those.

2.5 Development of Corporate Governance

The rules and regulations of corporate governance are the outcomes of several high-profile scandals that happened in various countries. Though the companies adjusted the codes according to their requirements, even then the keystones remain the same which are: openness, integrity, honesty, and commitment towards stockholders, employees, the environment, and stakeholders (Awan, *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, this section will cover the overall development of corporate governance codes by dividing the information into three different parts; initially, the overall growth of CG codes in the world is explained, then the four international CG subheadings have been generated which will provide brief information on CG in different countries (a mix of developing and developed countries to eradicate the bias) and there is a detailed discussion about the development of CG codes in the UK as they influenced many countries to develop their corporate governance structure. Additionally, the sample of data for this study belongs to the UK listed AIM companies; hence it is significant to understand the different principles suggested by the issued codes for CG in the UK.

2.5.1 Growth in Corporate Governance Codes

In the 1990s, for the first time, the concept of a corporate governance code appeared. Due to major collapses, governments of various countries were aware of the importance of corporate governance. Therefore, the notion of codes of corporate governance spread immediately at an alarming speed. As a result of which, nowadays, more than 200 codes of CG are in existence and used by several national or international corporations and governments of multiple countries (Oliveira, *et al.*, 2014). In other words, reforming corporate governance regulations is one of the regular issues of government policies in

almost all countries, yet corporate collapses continue to happen (Klettner, 2016; Clarke & Branson, 2012). Nowadays, governments discuss in detail the rules and regulations for the companies by the medium of codes of corporate governance.

Codes contain information about practical aspects of corporate governance which include the composition of the board, its role in the companies, discussing the responsibilities of the board, and necessary communication between the board and shareholders & stakeholders. Hence CG codes have become an important means to motivate companies to enhance their accountability and transparency (Cuomo, *et al.*, 2016). The first country that formally published a code document for CG was the United States in 1978 and then, the UK, in 1992, introduced the influential Cadbury Code that leads to many more codes which are discussed in detail further in this section (Grandori, 2004). After these codes, there was an immense proliferation of corporate governance codes globally. In 1999, around 24 countries issued their codes which rose to 63 countries in 2008, and, in 2015, 93 countries submitted their codes to the European Corporate Governance Institute (Klettner, 2016).

Seidl (2006, p.1) defines the codes of corporate governance as “a non-binding set of principles, standards or best practices, issued by a collective body and relating to the internal governance of corporations”. Hence, codes are providing guidelines or making suggestions to the corporations for maintaining good corporate governance in the business and the adoption of which is voluntary and not mandatory, though encouraged strongly (Seidl, *et al.*, 2009). In many countries, the codes exist in the form of soft law which means there is a “comply-or-explain” rule; however, the legal status of these codes differs from nation to nation. But as a matter of fact, the formation of codes in each country has usually been derived by a desire for more transparency, accountability and to regain the confidence of the investors in the stock market (Lessambo, 2014).

Comply-or-explain is also the most common regulatory mechanism of codes which says that the company should comply with the suggestions of codes and disclose these in the report, otherwise explain the reason for not adopting the recommended practice (Pletz & Upson, 2019). Besides the comply-or-explain approach, there are two more approaches called comply-or-else (a company must comply or face a penalty) and apply-or-explain (explanation on non-compliance) (Bhattacharyya, 2016b). The codes and guidelines of corporate governance have been issued by representatives of the stock exchange, figures from the number of investors group and last but not least committees are also involved in

the formation of codes and this includes respected personalities of the business world, professional and academic bodies and representatives from investor groups and they have all been selected by a government department (Mallin, 2019). Hence, each country tries to make efforts to formalise the codes of corporate governance and make improvements in it regularly and so far, 91 countries have made efforts to issue the codes (Cuomo, *et al.*, 2016). The corporate governance systems of different countries are discussed below, though the codes of corporate governance in the UK have been analysed in some more detail as this country is specifically the research area of this study.

2.5.2 International Corporate Governance System

To organise the exposure of information on CG, the United Nations maintained a guide of good practices on CG which acquires and aligns the knowledge of practices suggested by a wider range of national and transnational institutions such as the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (Oliveira, *et al.*, 2014). In addition to this, those nations who faced the problem of major collapses due to improper corporate governance structures, follow their own published codes or reports of CG; also, local organisations issued codes consisting of good practices for the local companies to follow (Clarke & Branson, 2012). In addition to the brief discussion on CG in different countries, Table 2.3 (on the next page) illustrates the key attributes of codes of CG in various countries:

Table 2.3: Codes of Corporate Governance in Different Countries

<i>Country</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Name of Code</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Nature</i>	<i>Board Structure</i>	<i>Ownership Structure</i>	<i>Legal System</i>
UK	1992	The Cadbury Report	Composition of the board, presence of NEDs and CEO-duality	Comply-or-explain	Unitary	Diverse shareholders, institutional investors, and individuals	Common law
USA	2002	Sarbanes–Oxley Act	Transparency and auditor independence	Comply-or-else	Unitary	Dispersed ownership structure, rise in institutional investors	Common law
Canada	1994	Dey Report	Board responsibility and composition	Comply-or-explain	Unitary	Controlling ownership	Common law
Germany	2002	Cromme Code of Corporate Governance	Mandatory representation of employees on supervisory board	Comply-or-explain	Dual	Financial and non-financial companies	Civil law
Denmark	2000	Norby Commission	Many shares have multiple voting rights	Comply-or-explain	Dual	Institutional investors and foundation ownership	Civil law
France	1995	CG of listed Corporations (from Vienot I Report)	Many shares have multiple voting rights	Comply-or-explain	Unitary (optional)	State; institutional and individual investors	Civil law
Italy	1998	Draghi Reform, Preda Report	Board of auditors required	Comply-or-explain	Unitary	Non-financial/ holding companies; families	Civil law
Russia	2001	Russian Code of CG	Covers dividend payments		Dual	Insiders, though outsiders increasing	Civil law

<i>Country</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Name of Code</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Nature</i>	<i>Board Structure</i>	<i>Ownership Structure</i>	<i>Legal System</i>
Japan	2001	Commercial Code in Japan	Influence of keiretsu	Comply-or-explain	Dual	Keiretsu; but institutional investor ownership is increasing	Civil law
Korea	1999	Code of Best Practice for CG	Influence of chaebol	Comply-or-explain	Unitary	Controlling shareholders	Common law
Malaysia	2000	Malaysian Code on CG	Influence of Bumiputera shareholders	Comply-or-explain	Unitary	Controlling shareholders	Common law
China	2002	Code of CG for Listed Companies	Influence of the communist party	Comply-or-explain	Dual	State	Civil law
Australia	2007	Australian Securities Exchange (ASX) CG Principles	Shareholder rights and Board diversity	Comply-or-explain	Unitary	Individual investors; non-institutional shareholders	Common law
South Africa	2010	King III CG Code	Inclusive approach	Apply-or-explain	Unitary	Individual investors	Common law
Egypt	2005	Egyptian Code of CG	Shariah law	Comply-or-explain	Unitary	State; institutional and individual investors	Civil law
Brazil	2001	Novo Mercado CG BOVESPA Listing Rules	Fiscal councils	Comply-or-explain	Dual	Controlling owners	Civil law
India	2000	Clause 49 of Listing Agreement	Few aspects of code are mandatory	Comply-or-else	Unitary	Corporate bodies; families and institutional investors	Common law

Source: (Lausten, 2002; Puffer & McCarthy, 2003; Bhasa, 2004; Enriques & Volpin, 2007; Liew, 2007; Bhattacharyya, 2016b; Mallin, 2019; Shah & Napier, 2019)

2.5.2.1 Corporate Governance in the United Kingdom

This section portrays the measurements taken by the UK to strengthen its corporate governance system, following the publication of the Cadbury Report in 1992 to the UK Corporate Governance Code issued in 2018. In addition to the specified codes, this section will also cover the Quoted Companies Alliance (QCA) Corporate Governance Code which recommends the CG practices specifically for the smaller quoted companies. This section is valuable to this thesis because the recommendations of the CG codes represent the independent variables of CG in this study, hence it is necessary to study the origin of these variables and why they are suggested (Shah, 2014). The QCA follows the UK CG codes to issue the guidelines and this thesis is going to test whether the recommendations by QCA about the board and committees influence the financial performance of the AIM companies or not. Hence, this section is devoted to study the corporate governance system and CG codes' recommendations & guidance in the UK.

In comparison to most of the countries in the world, the UK has a well-established market along with a base of diverse shareholders that are institutional investors, financial institutions, and individuals (Mallin, 2019). To a great extent, the development of CG in the UK is led by the requirement for transparency and accountability to regain the confidence of the investors that were damaged due to the corporate demises and financial scandals as discussed under section 2.4. The CG system in the UK is reflective of the perspectives of agency theory, hence associated with the separation between the owner (shareholders) and control (managers) of corporations (Pletz & Upson, 2019). However, a key turn came into the history of corporate governance in the UK when the Cadbury Report was published in 1992 by the Cadbury Committee. Even today, the basic framework of the UK Combined Code of Corporate Governance belongs to the Cadbury Report. Moreover, the code of CG in the UK is accepted as the blueprint of 'best practice' in Europe (Veldman & Willmott, 2016). Figure 2.1 (on the next page) demonstrates the growth in the corporate governance system of the UK since 1992.

Figure 2.1: The Development of Corporate Governance in the UK

Source: Author

In the figure above, various reports and codes show the regular process of updating the code to make sure that the CG codes in the UK stay relevant and effective. From 1998 onwards, the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) reviewing the UK Corporate Governance Code and the UK Stewardship Code at regular intervals, both issued in 2010 by the FRC specifically concentrating on the institutional investors (Lu, *et al.*, 2018). The UK CG code contains important guidelines about how a company should be directed, due to which not only premium listed companies but many smaller companies are eager to follow the best practice voluntarily (Institute of Directors, 2019). Furthermore, one by one, various reports of corporate governance will be discussed to shed light on the principles set by the regulators which will enable the author to understand the internal

control variables of corporate governance and use of them while developing the hypotheses.

Cadbury Report (1992) was generated by the Cadbury Committee, chaired by Sir Adrian Cadbury in 1992 (Dedman, 2002; Spira, 1999). The recommendations of this report covered different aspects as the operation of the board, the composition of the board, presence of non-executive directors, the importance of remuneration and audit committees, separation of the role of CEO and chairman, and highlighted the requirement for institutional shareholders (Weir & Liang, 2000). The Cadbury Committee recommended this code to all the listed companies in the UK; therefore, companies need to apply the ‘comply-or-explain’ mechanism (Arcot, *et al.*, 2010).

Greenbury Report (1995) was issued by the Greenbury Committee or study group that was chaired by Sir Richard Greenbury to resolve the issues related to the size of the remuneration packages of executives or directors and their incomplete or inconsistent disclosure in the annual reports (Greenbury, 1995; Connell & Ward, 2020). Moreover, the Greenbury Report was the first formal governance code in the UK addressing remuneration packages in the listed companies of the UK. The Greenbury Report was published in the summer of 1995, its recommendation sanctioned by the government and implemented under the listing rules of LSE-listed companies (Harvey, *et al.*, 2019).

Hampel Report (1998) supports most of the recommendation made by the previous two reports and discusses how companies need to consider the interests of various stakeholders along with safeguarding the interest of shareholders (Hampel, 1998; Short, 1999). Further, this report guided that the nomination committee should be recognised as following best practice but in the case of smaller boards, they may prefer to perform the tasks themselves (Stapledon, 1998). In addition to this, the Combined Code of Corporate Governance reported in 1998 with the recommendation of the Cadbury, Greenbury and Hampel Reports is mainly classified into two sections; one concentrates on companies and the other is aimed at institutional investors (Dedman, 2016).

Turnbull Report (1999) was issued by the Institute of Chartered Accountants in Wales and England (McCrae & Balthazor, 2000). This report was based on the internal control system of the companies and it has been confirmed by this report that the board of directors is required to make sure that a company has a sound system of internal control (The Institute of Chartered Accountants, 1999) which safeguards the company from

uncertain risks (Elliott, *et al.*, 2000) and that they must properly disclose the information in the annual report of the company (Page & Spira, 2004). Besides, a revised version of this report was published by the FRC in 2005, known as ‘Revised Turnbull Guidance’ (Professional Accountants in Business Committee, 2006). The aim of issuing a revised version was to encourage the boards to apply the recommendations regularly in respect to the internal control system and communicate with the shareholders about management of the risks (Financial Reporting Council, 2005).

Higgs & Smith Review (2003) proposed some measurements for more involvement of non-executive directors (NEDs) in the board (Nolan, 2005) as there should be at least one meeting of NEDs in isolation, half of the board members should be independent directors, there should be separation of the CEO and chair person’s post, and a senior independent director should be nominated to share any concerns with the shareholders (Higgs, 2003). After the recommendations of the Higgs report, Laura Tyson steered a group to look into the ways a company might improve the board efficiency by digging into a pool of talent with different skills, experiences, and perspectives (Mallin, 2019). Additionally, in 2003, FRC appointed a group chaired by Sir Robert Smith to guide the important role of the audit committee in the company and the Smith Review declared that irrespective of the executives, it is important for the audit committee to make sure that shareholders’ interests regarding financial reporting and internal control are adequately protected and they are getting a fair picture of the position of the company in its annual report (Smith, 2003). Besides, in July 2003, the revised Combined Code was published containing the revised substance of the Higgs and Smiths reviews (Adelegan, 2005).

The UK Corporate Governance Code (2010), FRC updates the CG Code for companies in the UK. It began in 2003, after the Walker Review which provided 39 recommendations, with an updated corporate governance code published in 2010 previously known as ‘the combined code’ (Nordberg & McNulty, 2013). FRC suggests that each year, directors should be re-elected to enhance their accountability and set new principles regarding board composition, selection of the board and enhancing diversity in the board, especially gender diversity that is also further incorporated by the Davies Report and Hampton-Alexander Review in 2017 (Chartered Institute of Management Accountants, 2010). As per the understanding of Mallin (2019), the UK Corporate Governance Code’s (2010) recommendations provide measures to intensify the performance of the board and made an effort to let the board know about their weaknesses

and strengthens. Furthermore, FRC made improvements in the UK Corporate Governance Code by publishing revised codes in 2012, 2014 and 2016 in respect to remuneration and audit committee changes but the latest code was issued in 2018 (Financial Reporting Council, 2016).

The UK Corporate Governance Code (2018) draws attention to the principles of the board (leadership, distribution of responsibilities, composition, internal control, risk measurements, and audit & remuneration) and proposes a flexible application of these by following the provisions of the ‘comply-or-explain’ approach (Financial Reporting Council, 2018a). Additionally, the UK corporate governance code was also supported by the Guidance on Board Effectiveness. Together with the discussion of the suggested alterations in the UK Corporate Governance Code (2018), the FRC also discussed the future of the Stewardship Code of the UK (Financial Reporting Council, 2018b). This code applies to all the companies listed in the main market of the LSE and premium listed companies follow the recommendations whereas, for AIM-listed companies, the code is optional to follow.

The QCA Corporate Governance Code (2018) was issued by the Quoted Companies Alliance (QCA) which is an independent organisation, specifically paying attention to the issues related to SMSs (The Quoted Companies Alliance, 2018a). The QCA issued guidelines for listed SMEs in 2005 and revised them in 2007 then replaced them in 2010 (Harbottle & Lewis, 2011) and 2018. The QCA published a new edition of the QCA Corporate Governance Code which specifies ten principles for effective CG practice in the SMEs (The Quoted Companies Alliance, 2018b). Broadly, these principles are related to board size, the composition of board and committee, independence of the board, board skills and capabilities appointment of directors (Burgess Salmon, 2018), the separate role of the CEO and chairman, and vision and strategy (Osborne Clarke, 2018). Although, QCA CG code is widely accepted by the listed SMEs as 60% of AIM listed companies adopted the code, still according to the research report (Quoted Companies Alliance, 2019) companies might take it as a box-ticking exercise due to the flexibility of the Code and more disclosure might be a potential danger as per the competitive point of view.

2.5.2.2 Corporate Governance in the United States of America, and Canada

United States of America (USA) is a country where many state and national measurements have been taken over the years in respect to CG such as Sarbanes-Oxley

(2002) (strengthening auditor's independence), Corporate Governance Rules by the New York Stock Exchange in 2003, and an expanded role for private pensions (Alnasser, 2012). Additionally, the USA has numerous fascinating highlights like Delaware General Corporation law, Dodd-Frank Wall Street Reform and the Consumer Protection Act (2010) (Mallin, 2019).

Canada's rules of corporate governance grant several rights to Canadian shareholders. Moreover, the Adams Report, Macdonald Report, and Governing Principles were also issued in Canada to protect the interest of shareholders, to maintain independent audit committees, and to set some principles for the board of directors to act accordingly (Vinten, 1998). Like the UK, Canada also follows a principles-based approach, which means Canadian companies need to disclose the information publicly about the extent of their compliance with best practice guidelines (Lessambo, 2014).

2.5.2.3 Corporate Governance in European Countries

Corporate governance has been developed in Europe despite the fact of diverse legal and ownership structures. Though the unique characteristics of each country influence the development of the CG there seems to be a general opinion on some crucial aspects such as transparency, disclosure, accountability, and independence of the board (Duh, 2017). However, concerning board structure, some of the European countries follow the unitary board structure; at the same time, the majority of countries in Europe also have the option of dual board structure which has been classified in Table 2.3 (above).

Germany operates on a two-tier board structure which means employees are presented as members of the supervisory board and banks also have a strong impact on the corporate governance system of Germany (Bhasa, 2004). In addition to this, regular amendments have been made with the international best practice of CG in the form of the Cromme Code which provides a unified set of a vast variety of laws and regulations, inclusive of recommendations to comply with the good practice of CG and the amended Corporate Governance Code (Cromme, 2005).

Denmark issued the Nørby Committee Report in 2001, with all the guidelines and recommendations for the companies to follow voluntarily for the benefit of their own company (Andersen, 2003). This report has been prepared as per the values of OECD, openness, transparency, equality, and responsibility. Further, the development in CG of Denmark is usually based on the suggestions of the Nørby Committee Report.

France issued the Viénot report and the Bouton report to recommend guidelines and rules for established companies (Bhattacharyya, 2016b). Instead of radical reforms, the latter report suggests some incremental improvements based on the suggestions of the former report. Meanwhile, in October 2003, the regulators published a single document named “The Corporate Governance of Listed Corporations” with all the recommendations in the above said reports as principles of CG in France (Charreaux, & Wirtz, 2007). Likewise, many amendments or updates have been made to these principles.

Italy issued the Preda codes (1 and 2) and the Corporate Governance Code (2006) which provide recommendations and set principles to maintain the best practices of corporate governance (Drago, *et al.*, 2014). Afterwards, authorities made regular updates in the corporate governance code, and significant alterations were made in 2012 regarding the financial sector which specifies no person can hold more than one position in the board of financial corporations working in the same sector or similar market.

Russian Code of Corporate Governance launched in 2001 consists of over 90 pages that have been published by the Federal Securities Commission, which supports the government regulators as well as private groups with the aim of high-level acceptance of and compliance with this code (Yakovlev, 2007). Further, the OECD and the merged Russian Stock Exchange introduced a new project on CG in the Russian Federation by 2011 while considering the remaining challenges and improvements in CG practices.

2.5.2.4 Corporate Governance in the Asia-Pacific Region

In the 1990s, the downtrend started in the financial sectors of the Asia-Pacific countries which led to the enhancement of a developed corporate governance structure. Following the global financial crisis, important steps were to renew the measures of disclosure, transparency, activities of the board, its independence and safeguard the interest of minor shareholders (Jackson, 2002). As above, the ownership structure in the countries of Asia-Pacific seems to be comprehensive either in families or cross-holdings. Some of the countries’ corporate governance approaches are discussed briefly below:

Japan’s CG system often relates to the Germanic CG system due to the relatively important role of banks in the companies of both the countries and deviant behaviour (Dore, 2005). Besides, the major difference in the CG systems of these two countries, the cultural difference, and the shareholding structure as in Japan’s ‘*keiretsu*’ still has its influence which broadly means ‘association of companies with holdings of shares one in

other'. However, now '*keiretsu*' is gradually losing its control over the ownership of companies as recent provisions of corporate governance encourage them to be transparent, independent and offer them more flexibility. Further, the revised version of the Japanese Commercial Code abolished the company auditor system and launched the board committee system (Demise, 2005).

Recently, **Korea** has also been affected by the downfall of the Japanese economy and consequently faced similar challenges. *Chaebol* means big conglomerates with ample cross-holdings of shares that exist in Korea which exercise an immense amount of power (Nam, et al., 2001). In 1999, the Korean code of best practice was issued by the established committee on corporate governance which contains five sections: shareholders, the board of directors, audit systems, stakeholders, and management monitoring by the market (Gupta & Sharma, 2014). Further, the revisions made on the existing code in 2003 and then in 2016 the Korean Stewardship Code Principles have been issued about mid-to-long term investors and their sustainable growth.

Malaysian Code of Corporate Governance was issued by the High-Level Finance Committee in 2000 which mainly focused on four parts: principles of good CG, best practices for companies, the role of investors and auditors in the company and explanatory codes (Morris, et al., 2011). Moreover, numbers of revisions and reforms have been done by the regulators in the form of the revised The Malaysian Code of Corporate Governance (2007; 2012), Corporate Governance Index by Stock Exchange (2009), Corporate Governance Blue Print by the securities commission of Malaysia (2011) and last but not least, The Malaysian Code of Corporate Governance (2017) which mainly gave attention to promote the corporate governance culture in the firms.

China is a social market economy and has launched several alterations to develop its stock market as China's corporate reporting was quite obscure. In 1990, a number of state-owned enterprises shifted to joint-stock companies and then moved to companies listed on one of the stock exchanges in China (He, 2011). In 2001, the China Securities Regulatory Commission (CSRC) introduced a code of corporate governance for the listed companies in China which are completely based on the guidelines (secure the interest of shareholders and moral standards of directors and top managers) of OECD about corporate governance (Jiang & Kim, 2015). Further, the code's recommendation

encourages the listed companies to improve independence in the company and for future developments, China is working with OECD.

Australia has a common law system that is quite developed in accordance with the Anglo-Saxon model of the USA and contains attributes of the UK single board structure. In 1991, the first report on the practices of corporate governance was issued, named The Bosch Report on Corporate Practice and Conduct and it was recommended to all the public listed companies to establish an audit committee (Vinten, 1998). Then, further developments have been made in 1993, 1995 and 2003 with the Principles of Good Corporate Governance and Best Practice Recommendations but the most recent update was in 2017 with the publication of Standard 23: Principles of Internal Governance and Asset Stewardship which behaves as a guide to the asset managers to fulfil their duties (Mallin, 2019).

2.5.2.5 Corporate Governance in South Africa, Egypt, Brazil, and India (SEBI)

In a similar way, other countries were affected by the downfall in the 1990s and with the financial crisis of 2008, the following countries and even the whole world felt the impact of the situation which led the countries to improve their corporate governance structure to regain the confidence of the investors.

South Africa comprehensively, has the most detailed corporate governance code in place, in comparison to the rest of the world (Mallin, 2019). In 1994, the King Report (King I) was introduced by a committee on CG, established in South Africa in 1992 (Ngoepe & Ngulube, 2013). Thereafter, King II (2002), King III (2009) and King IV (2016) have been published while specifically paying attention to ethical activities in the corporate sector (Bhattacharyya, 2016b). While adopting an inclusive approach, ethical and efficient leadership are the essential requirement of the CG structure in this country.

Egypt has gained the first position in developing corporate governance structure among the MENA countries. In the early 1990s, the government of this country ran a programme of economic reforms where some of the state-owned enterprises were privatised due to which the private sector became a major player in the Egyptian economy (Ebrahim & Fattah, 2015). Further, in 2005, the Egyptian Code of Corporate Governance was published and voluntarily applied to all the companies listed in the Cairo and Alexandra Stock Exchange (CASE), to all the financial institutions and to those companies who acquire major finances from the banking sector (Shahwan, 2015). Further, developments

were made in 2006, 2011, and 2016; additionally, the Shariah law of CG needs to be considered in Islamic banking and financial institutions.

Brazil is one of the countries in South America which suffers from the presence of control groups, and faced deficiencies in protecting the environment for minority shareholders (Rhee, 2013). Owners are eligible to elect the members of the fiscal council for themselves as the basic duty of the members is to act on the behalf of minority shareholders who do not have access to the company's information (Gallo, *et al.*, 2020). In 2001, a Code of Best Practice of Corporate Governance was issued by the Brazilian Institute of Corporate Governance. Further, the code has been updated and enlarged in 2004, a revised version issued in 2009 but the latest updated code has been published in 2016.

India launched a programme to bring reform to the economy and promote more dependency on market mechanisms rather than relying on the government. Still, the extensive ownership structure involves controls by families and business groups (Estrin & Prevezer, 2011). However, in further reforms, efforts were made to increase the efficiency of the government sector and encourage divestment of government holdings. Subsequently, banking reforms had also been adopted to align with international norms. In 1998, the codes were published, named the Desirable Corporate Governance in India- A Code by the Confederation of Indian Industry (Black & Khanna, 2007). Afterwards, in 2000, 'The Report of the Kumar Mangalam Birla Committee (KMBC) on Corporate Governance' was issued by the committee established by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) (Dharmapala & Khanna, 2013).

Undoubtedly, each country in the world is adopting measures and issuing guidelines for the corporations to set up good practices of corporate governance; still, there is a long way to go to attain the objectives of transparency, accountability and protect the interests of shareholders. Besides there are several similarities in the CG system of different countries, and some dissimilarities also exist due to different cultural values and individual regulations of each country. Further, this section also provides in-depth knowledge about the practices of CG in developed as well as developing countries which helps the researcher to achieve the first objective. In the next section, this study discussed the role of SMEs in the economic development of the UK because, in terms of the sample of data, listed SMEs have been selected. In addition to this, the information about the

international FTSE-AIM market has been provided as this is the only market that gives a public platform to the SMEs to list themselves and avail of the opportunity to access public funds. Another important aspect that has been covered in the next section is the current corporate governance measures adopted by SMEs.

2.6 Small and Medium Size Enterprises in the UK

The purpose of this section is to provide a thorough understanding of the role of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the economic development of the UK. Specifically, this section will concentrate those SMEs which are listed in Alternative Investment Market (AIM) a lower-tier market registered in the London Stock Exchange (LSE). Additionally, this section will also provide a discussion about the governance structure of the listed SMEs. The whole set of information is essential to consider as the SMEs listed in FTSE-AIM will be the sample data in this thesis and the contribution of this study will help to understand how the corporate governance mechanisms of SMEs are effective to improvise and stabilise the financial performance of the companies. Therefore, in-depth knowledge of the current governance structure and governance guidelines for SMEs is required which will also be covered in this section. Further, the information is organised into three parts: the first part will elaborate the meaning, growth and development of listed SMEs in the UK, the second part covers the explanation of the FTSE-AIM market and the third part reviews the recent governance system and recommendation of the Quoted Companies Alliance (QCA) for the UK-listed SMEs.

2.6.1 *Small and Medium Size Enterprises (SMEs)*

Small and medium size enterprises play an important role in the growth and prosperity of most of the countries worldwide that eventually began in the late 1970s and early 1980s. Since then, SMEs have started to become more innovative and flexible in reducing costs (Caner, 2010). In terms of providing employment, SMEs are the largest contributors in most of the countries as they are capable of creating new jobs in society (Afrifa, 2013a). There is no universally accepted definition of SMEs; however, the most common benchmarks used to define SMEs include firm size, number of employees, annual turnover, total assets and annual balance sheet total (Abor & Adjasi, 2007). The definition provided by the European Commission's recommendation 2003/361/CE of 6th May 2003, includes the following specific requirements: (a) number of employees less than 250; (b) turnover must be less than €50 million; and (c) balance sheet total of less than €43 million

(Department for International Trade, 2021). Out of the stated requirements, a company must fulfil at least two of them; only then a firm is considered as an SME. This definition will be used in this study to select the sample of data from the UK-listed AIM companies (Dasilas & Papasyriopoulos, 2015). Furthermore, due to the presence of features related to management (managed by owners who are influenced by the family members) and the nature of the operation (unrefined management structure and limited resources to manage the risk), a good corporate governance system is highly necessary in SMEs, even more than large enterprises (Ayandibu & Houghton, 2017).

Moreover, the authorities must pay attention to SMEs due to their contribution towards the overall development of the economies of the countries (Edmiston, 2007; Khalique, *et al.*, 2011). Similarly, some of the world's best economies, such as Japan, Taiwan, Korea, China and Hong Kong believe that their SMEs have always played a significant role in the growth of the country (Qureshi & Herani, 2011). In the case of the UK, SMEs employ 16.6m people which is almost 60% of the total employment with a turnover of £2.2 trillion (PBC Today, 2019), 52% of the overall economy's turnover, and contributing around 54% of overall economic output or GVA of the country; thus, it is becoming more important than ever before to support the SMEs to protect the economy of the UK (Santander, 2018). Moreover, every large enterprise started life as an SME sometime (Shah, 2012); therefore, to develop the business environment in the UK or any other country, it is vital to support SMEs in the form of providing finance, a suitable market and measures to improve their corporate governance system (Beck & Kunt, 2006). This study will also help SMEs to understand the influence of corporate governance mechanisms on their financial performance.

2.6.2 *The Alternative Investment Market (AIM)*

In the previous section, the author clearly explained the importance of SMEs in the economic development of a country including the UK. Despite this, limited access to external finance hinders the growth of SMEs and their potential survival (Afrifa, 2013b). However, this problem of SMEs can be resolved by listing in the stock exchange to an extent, but listing might be challenging for SMEs due to the requirements of admission and disclosure regulations (Gupta, *et al.*, 2015). This recognition led to the emergence of stock markets particularly for SMEs with moderate entry requirements and relief in following governance disclosure requirements in comparison to the other main markets

of stock exchanges. A perfect example of this case is set by the London Stock Exchange (LSE) for the world with one of its sub-market known as FTSE- AIM (Shah, 2014). This is a stock market that is designed to help small and medium businesses get access to funds from the public market. In 1995, AIM launched with a set of 10 companies valued at £82m and nowadays the list of AIM companies contains 850 companies with a combined market capitalisation of £104bn (London Stock Exchange, 2018). In 25 years, AIM became the world's most prosperous and established market. At the point of entering into the AIM market, companies are usually small and rapidly growing so they can take advantage of status and credibility through their listing; once they have grown large enough then eventually, those companies shift to the main market of LSE.

The AIM has developed as a globally unique market that provides capital market access not only to national SMEs but to international SMEs as well. So, without any doubt, AIM is an effective platform for the SMEs to join, grow and achieve their aims but it is evident that the money channelled into SMEs is declining and the reason is the loss of institutional investors' interest and trust in them (Mallin & Ow-Yong, 2013). AIM is a highly competitive market; therefore, transparency of governance mechanisms is the key to gaining and maintaining the trust of investors. Though in this market SMEs have an advantage over the codes of corporate governance according to the point of view of the investor, they need some security about the company which can be gained from their governance structure (Parsa, *et al.*, 2007). The existing literature shows quite nominal evidence on the extent of compliance with government regulatory requirements by SMEs and how it affects their financial performance (Mallin & Ow-Yong, 2012). According to the recent amendments in AIM rule 26, all the AIM-listed companies should follow a recognised CG code as per the nature and size of their firms (The Quoted Companies Alliance, 2018b). However, it is still debatable which CG code leads to best practice of CG in the listed SMEs. Therefore, this thesis strives to provide evidence to the SMEs, about how the adoption of the CG principles influences their financial performance.

2.6.3 Corporate Governance in SMEs Listed in AIM

Due to major corporate collapses (as explained in section 2.4), nowadays all companies either small or big need to establish an effective and professional governance system with which they will be able to gain the trust of investors and tackle the new challenges. This is even more significant when SMEs are listed, whereas unlisted SMEs still can choose

to follow or not follow corporate governance regulations (Palacín-Sánchez, *et al.*, 2019). This study is focusing on listed SMEs in the UK; hence, this section will provide brief knowledge about corporate governance rules and regulations for UK-listed AIM companies which have recently been amended by the LSE. Before 2018, the SMEs which are listed in FTSE-AIM are not legally bound to comply with the CG provisions which apply to the main market of LSE. Nevertheless, the investors, specifically institutional investors, expect the companies to voluntarily adopt the CG regulations (Abor & Adjasi, 2007). Therefore, some of the key sources of CG guidelines are available to AIM companies which they may adopt, namely AIM rules and regulations, the Quoted Companies Alliance (QCA) Guidelines and the Corporate Governance and the Voting Guidelines (Mallin & Ow-Yong, 2013). The belief is companies listed in AIMs are not under the obligation of the comply-or-explain rule as the code of CG is not appropriate for small and growing companies due to their different sizes and requirements (Afrifa & Tauringana, 2015c).

However, as per the AIM rule 26, companies need to follow or adopt a CG code as per their convenience. The listed SMEs need to maintain a website to provide complete disclosure about the application of the code, the board of directors, committees, and their responsibilities. On the other hand, LSE supports the use of the QCA CG Code issued by the QCA in 2018 specially for AIM companies as the Combined Code does not apply to them directly; however, the UK CG Code is still an option for SMEs (Chambers, 2017). Moreover, authorities are required to make sure that the companies do not misuse the lighter governance requirements that they have provided. Hence, it is expected that companies should at least abide by the guidelines provided by the QCA otherwise specify the reason for non-application. In addition to this, in March 2007, the National Association of Pension Funds (NAPF) issued its guidelines for AIM companies which were adopted by 3% of the population of AIM companies (Mallin & Ow-Yong, 2012). The main guidelines are associated with the issues related to the combined role of chairman and chief executive officer, the composition of the board, its sub-committees, independence of the board and committees (Burgess Salmon, 2018). After the amendments, it is no longer the choice of listed SMEs to adopt a CG code, but it became a rule now; however, this was quite recently, due to which the author is unable to find any empirical evidence. Hence, this thesis will provide empirical evidence about the influence of corporate governance mechanisms on their financial performance. So, these

guidelines are not just rules for them, but they are in existence for their benefit to gain the trust of new investors and align the interest of principal and agent (Arora & Singh, 2020).

In the above section, a brief introduction has been provided about small and medium enterprises, in which the author also mentioned the importance of the existence of SMEs in the economy of the UK; then the information about the AIM market, its growth and development have been discussed and finally, this section elaborated the governance rules and regulations in AIM-listed companies. This section demonstrates the theoretical knowledge about the sample of data and attempts to provide the reason behind selection. In the next section, the author develops the theoretical framework of this study.

2.7 Theoretical Underpinnings

The following section of this chapter aims to provide an understanding of key theories of corporate governance and their association with the characteristics of the board of directors. Additionally, this study strives to evaluate the application of multiple theories of corporate governance on the corporate structure of small and medium enterprises as limited research has been taken place in previous literature concerning the use of corporate governance theories for SMEs. Moreover, speculation of the theoretical aspect of corporate governance is essential due to the involvement of a variety of disciplines like legal, cultural, structural differences and organisational behaviour (Huillier, 2014). Though the development of corporate governance is happening globally, the stage of development may vary from country to country referring to the factors like an evaluation of the economy, corporate structure and ownership groups which specify how corporate governance will develop in a particular country (Pande & Ansari, 2014). Hence, some theories may prove more adequate for one country in comparison to another or it may also be influenced by different times depending on what stage a specific country is at.

While reviewing the great range of literature on the theoretical foundation of corporate governance, the author observes that agency theory is considered the underpinning theory of corporate governance. However, there is an emerging concern among professional and academic authors regarding the assumption of agency theory as the foundation of CG due to its narrow perspective (Christopher, 2010) which will be further explained in detail in this section. Therefore, this thesis adopts multiple theoretical approaches to explain why variables of corporate governance affect the financial performance of the UK-listed

SMEs. This approach is supported by many authors (Pillai & Al-Malkawi, 2018), to identify other factors (internal and external) in a wider range that influence the organisation, so that, the affecting forces can also be incorporated into the governance structure of the company. Table 2.4 (below) depicts a summary of various theories that may relate to the expansion of corporate governance.

Table 2.4: Theories Influencing the Development of Corporate Governance

<i>Theory Name</i>	<i>Role of Corporate Governance</i>
Agency theory	Identifies separation of ownership and control to maximise shareholder value.
Managerial hegemony theory	Effectively dominates the influence of directors by exerting managerial force from within the organisation.
Stewardship theory	Highlights the principal-steward relationship due to directly or indirectly aligned objectives of both.
Transaction cost economics theory	Under, this theory, a firm represents a governance structure to reduce total cost under the influence of some external conditions.
Stakeholder theory	This theory takes into account the interests of all the groups which can influence or be affected by the activities of the firm.
Institutional theory	Considers social rules and beliefs by which organisations are constrained by that define their structure and practice
Resource dependence theory	Recognises that organisational behaviour depends on the external factors, hence it is believed to control the available vital resources in an exogenous environment.

Source: Author

The above-mentioned theories have contributed to the development of corporate governance in various manners. However, some of the main theories of corporate governance will be discussed in detail further in this section which is directly related to the role of the board of directors in companies. Hence, Agency theory, Stakeholder theory, Stewardship theory and Resource Dependence theory are explained further, inclusive of their theoretical base, their association with the attributes of the board of

governance and their application in the corporate structure of SMEs. The reason behind selecting these few theories to consider further is their theoretical base which is more focused on internal factors rather than external factors of CG. In the same way, other theories are included in Table 2.4 but are not evaluated further due to the nature of the theory which is either focused on external circumstances or managerial force. Therefore, the following theories have been elaborated to understand the theoretical base of the relationship between internal corporate governance mechanisms and the financial performance of the UK-listed SMEs.

2.7.1 Agency Theory

In simple words, agency theory defines the principal-agent relationship based on a contract between management, board and shareholders of the company where shareholders (principal) elect the board (governance mechanism) to act on behalf of them in the decision-making process and electing the management team (agent) to run the business smoothly (Andersen, 2015). Agency theory developed on the belief that agents (managers) strive to pursue their self-interest at the cost of the principal's interests due to the separation of ownership and control; this is also known as the agency problem which occurs due to a deviation of interests between principal and agent (Kusi, *et al.*, 2018). This problem was first recognised by Adam Smith in the 18th century followed by Ross in 1973 and then a detailed description was provided by Jensen and Meckling in 1976 (Abdullah & Valentine, 2009).

It is an assumption by agency theorists that possibly agents will try to achieve their interest in the first place which may differ from shareholders' interest due to their firm-specific knowledge and expertise in managerial skills (Sewpersadh, 2019). Thereupon, it is highly required to propose a governance structure in the company that makes efforts to restrict the agent's self-interest behaviour in circumstances where principal and agent have conflicting targets. In the form of an information system to measure the agent's behaviour, the effective mechanisms may be ownership structure, capital and labour markets, and the board of directors (Hung, 1998). This study will specifically focus on the measures provided by the board of directors to limit the self-centred activities of managers. Furthermore, many authors conclude that different types of governance mechanisms can be effective in reducing agency costs or agency problems (Panda & Leepsa, 2017; Zaid, *et al.*, 2020). This study has taken into consideration the

characteristics of the board of directors including board size, board independence, CEO-duality, board gender diversity, and size of the audit committee which are elaborated further in this chapter.

Besides, agency theory always relates to the large public listed companies as a result of the separation of ownership from control (Kim, *et al.*, 2005). However, in this study, the principals of agency theory will apply to SMEs which are listed in the London Stock Exchange due to the direct link between compensation and individual performance in SMEs as it would be convenient for the board of directors to align the interest of principal and agent with the use of incentives or allowances based on the individual performance of the managers rather than overall company performance so that it would be more motivating for the agents to work for the interests of the shareholders (Shah, 2014). Although the application of agency theory in business is traditional it is still criticised by some authors. Initially, this theory is focusing solely on the interests of the shareholder and completely ignoring the interests of other parties who are connected to the businesses directly or indirectly and to maximise the value of shareholders; this theory constantly pressurises managers which could be one of the many reasons for the corporate demises (Lubatkin, 2005). Hence, this has led to the development of other theories such as stakeholder theory explained further.

2.7.2 Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory was introduced by Edward Freeman (1984) in ‘Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach’ arguing that though the shareholders are the owners of the business, still corporate managers have a much wider responsibility towards those individuals or groups of people who can affect or be affected by the functions of the business (Law, 2011). Collectively these people represent stakeholders of the firm which includes employees, suppliers, creditors, customers, competitors and the community in which a business needs to survive and operate at a large scale (Nwanji & Howell, 2007). Hence, the accountability of the managers is not limited to economic or legal perspectives (interest of shareholders) but covers the ethical and philanthropic aspects (stake of other parties) (Kusi, *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, a firm is unable to maximise the value of shareholders while neglecting the interest of stakeholders (O’Sullivan, 2003).

This wider approach of corporate governance leads to a shift in the traditional role of the board of directors which was to act as only a protector of shareholder values or interests (Smith, 2003). Therefore, being the highest authority in a company, the board of directors needs to set the standards and values within the organisation through effective decision making about an internal control system and strategy while addressing the needs of a diverse range of stakeholders (Jensen, 2001). Academic researchers have focused on various aspects of corporate governance but recently paid more attention to the practical use of guidelines provided by different available codes of corporate governance in various countries (Ayuso & Argandona, 2009). However, this study will only consider the internal mechanisms of corporate governance in the form of board composition while considering the multiple theoretical approaches inclusive of stakeholder theory which are further explained in this section. Besides, the application of this theory on the corporate structure of small and medium size enterprises will also be justifiable due to the small scale of operation and group of individuals as a result of which there will be more concise and clear communication between stakeholders and the board of directors that leads to consensus among all stakeholders and top authorities of business (Corbetta & Salvato, 2004).

2.7.3 Stewardship Theory

Stewardship theory is an alternative to the agency theory which is originally connected with the disciplines of sociology and psychology (Klepczarek, 2017), the human relations school of management (Huillier, 2014) and transaction cost economics theory (Stiles & Taylor, 2010). This theory was introduced by Donaldson in 1997 who represents managers or executives of the company as stewards and unlike agency theory, this theory believes that stewards do work in the interest of shareholders through protecting and making profits for them (Learnmount, 2003). This theory can be divided into two aspects as the first aspect begins from divergence in the interests of shareholders and managers but implies that the agents will still be motivated to pursue the interest of the principal which leads them to attain a higher utility level and opportunities for desired outcomes such as fulfilment, achievement and self-esteem (Camilleri, 2018).

On the other hand, the second aspect assumes that there is no variance between the interests of the principal and agent (Puyvelde, *et al.*, 2012). Hence, both theories, agency and stewardship theory, have taken into consideration the relationship of principal and

agent but with different assumptions (Abdullah & Valentine, 2009). Furthermore, concerning the board of directors, stewardship theory believes that rather than outside directors, inside directors better understand the business as they are essentially trustworthy individuals who spend their lives working while governing the company, hence are capable enough to make superior decisions (Nicholson & Kiel, 2007). In addition to this, there are some more mechanisms of the board of directors which can relate to this theory and be explained further while developing the hypothesis.

2.7.4 Resource Dependency Theory

Resource dependence theory was introduced in 1978 by Pfeffer and Salancik and highlights the quality of the unique resources available to the company, recognising the effectiveness of the coordination processes between the companies and the importance of maintaining the firm's relationship with the business environment (Drees & Heugens, 2013). This theory follows the discipline of sociology and seems like a wider picture of stakeholder theory (Lämsiluoto, *et al.*, 2013). Both theories concentrate on relationships but stakeholder theory focuses on the relationship between a group of people for individual benefits whereas resource dependence theory focuses on the role of the board of directors in providing external resources to the firms whose access could be critical for the companies (Withers, *et al.*, 2009). Thereupon, this theory supports the concept of independence in the board as outside directors will prove as external resources in the form of skills, knowledge, suppliers and buyers to the company (Okpara, 2011). As we explained before, the board of directors is a governance mechanism and this theory depicts that it is the role of corporate boards to manage internal as well as external influences which cover the risk of uncertainty that improves the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the organisation (Simmons, 2012). Therefore, it is essential to use the theoretical grounding of this theory which will help to develop the hypothesis in this study while considering characteristics of boards as the dependent variable and the performance of the firm as the independent variable.

This section attempts to provide a theoretical background of corporate governance which clearly shows that though agency theory is the most traditional theory of CG, still some authors criticise it for only focusing on shareholder value maximisation as with the help of stakeholder theory, stewardship theory and resource dependence theory, this highlights that other parties who might get affected or may affect the organisation are worth taking

into consideration for the effective management system of the company. Hence the second objective of this study is partially achieved and the above discussed theoretical framework leads to the development of the conceptual framework of this study. Therefore, the next section covers the formulation of the conceptual framework which further helps to develop the hypotheses to achieve the aim of the study.

2.8 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework specifically analyses the various variables, the cause-effect relationship between the variables and assists in developing hypotheses. Therefore, this section develops the conceptual framework considering the influence of corporate governance on a firm's financial performance and explores the corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance mechanisms (Haque, *et al.*, 2008). In other words, the conceptual framework lays out the path to achieve the aim of the study which is to examine the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance of the UK-listed AIM companies by moderating control variables. This conceptual framework has been derived from the previous literature (Adedeji, *et al.*, 2020). See the graphical representation in Figure 2.2 (below).

Figure 2.2: Conceptual Framework

Source: Author

To understand the relationship between corporate governance and the financial performance of SMEs, the major corporate governance variables selected are board size, independence of the board, the separation between the role of CEO and chairman, availability of women on the board, and size of the audit committee. The financial performance of companies can be valued based on accounting measures (ROA) and market measures (Tobin's Q); therefore, to review the financial performance of SMEs both measures have been considered. This model also considered the significance of control variables including the main two elements (corporate governance and financial performance) of the conceptual framework which have been discussed in detail in this section. Before that, it is vital to consider those studies which assist in developing the conceptual framework and Table 2.5 (on the next page) covers all the major authors.

Table 2.5: List of Authors Influencing the Conceptual Framework

Authors	Year	Study	Sample Data	Results
Afrifa & Tauringana, 2015c	2004-2013	Corporate governance and performance of UK listed small and medium enterprises	234 SMEs listed on the AIM	Board size, CEO age and tenure and directors' remuneration are significantly related to the performance of SMEs but no association was found between NED and financial performance of SMEs.
Abor & Biekpe, 2007	1998-2003	Corporate governance, ownership structure and performance of SMEs in Ghana: implications for financing opportunities	120 small firms from Ghana	A positive relationship between board size, board composition, managerial skill level, CEO duality, inside ownership, family business foreign ownership and profitability of small companies
Palacín-Sánchez, <i>et al.</i> , 2019	2009-2016	Characteristics and determinants of the board of directors of growing Spanish SMEs going public	43 public companies in the Spanish SMEs market	Supports larger board size at least more than the minimum and that too with the majority of NEDs.
Kyere & Ausloos, 2020	2014	Corporate governance and firms financial performance in the United Kingdom	252 firms listed in the London Stock Exchange	Found mixed results for board size, board independence, CEO duality and audit committee with ROA and Tobin's Q. At the same time believes that CG structure if properly applied then does positively impact the firm performance.

Authors	Year	Study	Sample Data	Results
Peters & Bagshaw, 2014	2010-2011	Corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria: A content analysis	33 Nigerian firms from the manufacturing, financial and oil and gas sector	A high degree of correlation was found between the CG and FP variables but due to voluntary acceptance of the CG code fewer firms followed it.
Haniffa & Hudaib, 2006	1996-2000	Corporate governance structure and performance of Malaysian listed companies	347 companies listed in Kuala Lumpur Stock Exchange	Found significant impact of different board attributes (board size, CEO duality, multiple directorships and managerial shareholdings) on FP of firms.
Darko, <i>et al.</i> , 2016	2008-2012	Corporate governance: the impact of director and board structure, ownership structure and corporate control on the performance of listed companies in Ghana Stock Exchange	20 companies listed in Ghana Stock Exchange	Strong evidence provided for the impact of female representation on the board on the FP of listed companies. Also showed no impact of board size and audit committee size on the FP of firms whereas found negative results for NEDs.
Bhagat & Bolton, 2008	1990-2004	Corporate governance and firm performance	Different indices were used as a sample	The separate role of chairman and CEO is significantly positively correlated to the operating performance measures. No correlation was found between governance measures and future stock market performance.
Sehrawat, <i>et al.</i> , 2020	2010-2019	Does corporate governance affect the financial performance of firms? A large sample of evidence from India.	2,552 non-financial Indian firms	No association was found between audit committee independence, the board size, and CEO duality and firm performance, whereas managerial ownership found a positive impact.

Source: Author

2.8.1 Corporate Governance Mechanisms

Over the past three decades, corporate governance has become a dominant area of study in the field of finance. Much of the research related to the concept of corporate governance is inspired by the idea of agency theory (Fu, 2019). In other words, the requirement of corporate governance arises due to the separation of owners and managers which is also stated as an agency problem (Misangyi & Acharya, 2014; Soobaroyen & Mahadeo, 2012). Due to the enlargement of capital markets in the 1990s, with the continuous rise in the number of listed companies and the globalisation of investors, the need for an efficient corporate governance system in the firm further increased (Cuervo, 2002). Corporate governance comprises the set of several mechanisms to protect the investor's interest against the decisions of the managers. The main two categories of corporate governance mechanisms are further explained in this section and demonstrated in the form of the diagram below.

Figure 2.3: Corporate Governance of the Firm

Source: (Gillan, 2006)

Traditionally, the simple corporate governance structure of the firm includes management (which makes decisions on investments) and the board of directors (monitoring top management) as an internal control system and shareholders (investing capital in the firm) as the element of external governance. But, nowadays, firms opt for a more comprehensive perspective in which, inclusive to boards, managers, shareholders and debtholders, firms also concentrate on other participants as shown in Figure 2.3 (on the previous page) (Gillan, 2006). However, the most general classification of corporate governance mechanisms is: internal governance mechanisms (board of directors and managerial compensation) and external governance mechanisms (the market for products and services and government policies) (Huyghebaert & Wang, 2012).

According to Goodwin & Seow (2002), the presence of the internal governance mechanisms in the firm influence the ability of the company to strengthen controls and prevent and detect fraud and errors in financial statements. Mainly, internal mechanisms are applied by the firm to manage the internal problems associated with managerial opportunism, different objectives of managers and shareholders and misuse of managerial incentives (Filatotchev & Nakajima, 2010). A few internal mechanisms work to align the CEO and shareholder interests through CEO stock ownership and compensation contingent on firm performance. Several mechanisms are thought to be effective for the monitoring role of the board of directors and thus firm performance and default risk (Ballester, *et al.*, 2020); however, previous research found mixed results in this aspect (Misangyi & Acharya, 2014).

Similar to internal governance mechanisms, many researchers have highlighted the importance of external governance mechanisms such as shareholder activism and the market for corporate control (Guo, *et al.*, 2015; Teng, *et al.*, 2020). It is also evidenced that internal governance mechanisms could positively affect the firm's productivity, but the efficiency of the internal governance mechanisms can be affected by tougher external governance mechanisms (Tian & Twite, 2011; Claessens & Fan, 2002). Some scholars indicate that external mechanisms could work as a substitute for internal governance mechanisms. On the other hand, some believe that internal governance mechanisms have a strong impact on the performance of the company either with or without the external mechanisms (Acharya, *et al.*, 2011). Hence this piece of work is focusing on the internal mechanisms associated with the board of directors only as in terms of sources, managerial

incentives could be a challenging internal mechanism for small and medium listed enterprises to rely on.

2.8.2 Financial Performance Mechanisms

The financial performance of the firms has always been a matter of interest for managerial researchers. It reflects the fulfilment of the firm's goals and objectives; in other words, it indicates how well a business uses its assets and investments to generate profit and to provide a return to shareholders (Peters & Bagshaw, 2014). However, there is no harmony regarding the selection of a proper set of financial variables that account for corporate financial performance. Arguably, any one corporate performance indicator could sufficiently capture the dimensions of the financial performance (Azeez, 2015). Hence, different authors are motivated to use different mechanisms of financial performance such as value-based measures, accounting-based measures, market-based measures. However, Onwuka, *et al.* (2019) believes that these financial measures are unable to provide a clear picture of social and environmental benefits resultant from corporate activities. According to the previous literature (Papangkorn, *et al.*, 2019; Buallay, *et al.*, 2017) mechanisms of financial performance fit into two main categories, accounting-based measures and market-based measures and this study also selects the financial variables based on these two measures.

Accounting-based measures are the most historical measures of financial performance which mainly developed as a reporting mechanism. These measures reflect the impact of many factors such as the record of past success achieved with the help of advice given by the board to the management team and the corporate performance indicators (Kyere & Ausloos, 2020). A few of them are used in the literature of governance like return on assets (ROA), sales, return on equity (ROE) and earnings per share (Ntim, 2013). Nevertheless, this study will also include one of the accounting-based measures as a dependent variable, the reason being that these measures are historical, therefore applicable to almost all the industries in the market even the financial institutions and represent the actual results of the actions performed by the firms (Grove, *et al.*, 2011).

However, accounting-based measures are unable to consider the cost of invested capital and might not be able to reflect the actual and real figures due to circumstantial convenience of the management, hence market-based measures intend to state the value of the company in the capital market (Bayrakdaroglu, *et al.*, 2012). In comparison to

accounting-based measures, market-based measures of the firm performance connect with the overall value of the firm placed by the market and these measures may not be related to asset valuation, current operations or even the past profitability of the firm (Kiel & Nicholson, 2003). These measures rely on the valuations of the expected future earnings of the firm, hence are also termed as forward-looking indicators that represent prevailing plans and strategies (Sarhan, *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, along with accounting-based measures to enhance the robustness of the work, this study will also include one of the market-based measures such as market to book ratio and Tobin's Q.

Conclusively, this section represents the conceptual framework of the study in a graphical manner and discusses its two main measures that are: corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance mechanisms. Though the detailed description of the variables will be provided in the next chapter, this section covers the previous literature in terms of different mechanisms which helps to understand the choice of variables. Further, the next section develops the hypotheses to test with the assistance of multiple independent and dependent variables.

2.9 Empirical Literature and Hypotheses Development

The present study aims to examine the relationship between corporate governance variables (internal governance mechanisms) and the financial performance of the SMEs listed on the London Stock Exchange. To achieve the aim, this study has some objectives to fulfil and this section helps to accomplish the third objective which is concerned with examining the existing literature and theories of corporate governance to understand the influence of internal corporate governance on different aspects of the firm, mainly financial performance. In the previous section, the conceptual framework has been developed which covers the internal corporate governance variables and financial performance variables. Similarly, this section will investigate the association between independent and dependent variables by referring to the empirical literature and main theories. Based on this, this study will identify the hypotheses to test.

2.9.1 Board Size and Financial Performance

As per the existing literature, the firms that operate with better corporate governance practices also perform better due to minimal agency costs and more efficient monitoring measures (Zhou, *et al.*, 2018). The effective mechanism of monitoring or controlling the

firm is the board of directors who manage the firm affairs and decision-making on the board (Gaur, *et al.*, 2015). While considering the favourable size of the board, it is essential to acknowledge the size of the corporation which may enhance the performance of the firms (Merendino & Melville, 2019). Moreover, there are several codes in different countries but none of them specifies the exact board size required due to diverse environments and corporate governance structures in different economies and industries (Khan, *et al.*, 2019). The size of the board depends on multiple factors of the firm such as firm size, structure, sector, strategies, and policies (Orozco, *et al.*, 2018).

The relationship between board size and the financial performance of firms was tested by several studies to describe the relationship more appropriately (Karim & Faiz, 2017). According to the perspective of agency theory, large board size negatively influences the financial performance of the firms (Liang, *et al.*, 2013; Aslam & Haron, 2020; Orozco, *et al.*, 2018; Khan, *et al.*, 2019; Amar, *et al.*, 2011; Eisenberg, *et al.*, 1998) based on the argument that it may lead to delay in the decision-making process, could be a reason for agency cost (Kiambati, *et al.*, 2013), lack of proper communication and an ineffective monitoring function on the board (Murtaza, *et al.*, 2020). Meanwhile, resource dependence theory believes that large boards have a positive impact on the financial performance of the business (Merendino & Melville, 2019; Murtaza, *et al.*, 2020; Sehrawat, *et al.*, 2020; Kyere & Ausloos, 2020; Karim & Faiz, 2017; Zhou, *et al.*, 2018) in the sense that the board can be a useful external resource in critical situations for the firm (Sehrawat, *et al.*, 2020) as a board with several directors can take a stand and confront the CEO decision if required (Samaha, *et al.*, 2015).

However, an increase in the size of the board can be beneficial up to a point; after that; unnecessarily large boards become unable to quickly adjust to change (Amar, *et al.*, 2011; Haniffa & Hudaib, 2006), major conflicts may arise and might be expensive for small and medium size enterprises (Kyere & Ausloos, 2020). Additionally, Vaidya (2019) and Sehrawat, *et al.* (2020) are unable to find any association between board size and the financial performance of firms. However, following agency theory and mixed empirical literature, this study develops a hypothesis about board size and the financial performance of SMEs listed in FTSE-AIM. Hence, this paper introduces the following hypothesis:

H₁: The unduly large size of the board may outweigh the benefits and be negatively associated with the firm performance of listed SMEs in the UK.

2.9.2 Board Independence and Financial Performance

The recent corporate scandals have put the spotlight on the active role and functioning of the board of directors (Pathan, *et al.*, 2007). The board of a firm is a mix of executive and non-executive directors (Palmberg, 2015). It assumes that the actions of executives always belong to those on whom they depend, whereas the non-executive directors act on behalf and in the interest of all the shareholders of a firm (Mura, 2007). Therefore, independent directors are considered an important internal governance mechanism to maintain good governance practices in the listed and unlisted firms (Long, *et al.*, 2005). According to the previous literature, the common measure of the independence of board members refers to the inside (appointed within the firm) and outside directors (employed from outside the firm) (Merendino & Melville, 2019). According to the UK Higgs Report (Higgs, 2003), a company requires at least half of the board to be non-executive, meaning independent. In other words, non-executive directors need to stay free from any influence of executives or management (Fuzi, *et al.*, 2016). Many authors have tried constantly to establish a relationship between BI and FP and as per the empirical evidence, there are mixed results available. Some scholars have found a positive relationship, as outsider directors bring external sources to the firm (Nodeh, *et al.*, 2016; Pombo & Gutiérrez, 2011; Gaur, *et al.*, 2015; Muñoz, 2020).

Meanwhile, a few authors have stated a negative or no association due to information asymmetry and the presence of grey directors (who are non-executives but indirectly related to the firm) (Clifford & Evans, 1997; Cheung, *et al.*, 2013; Karim & Faiz, 2017; Murtaza, *et al.*, 2020; Hooghiemstra & Manen, 2004). In accordance with agency theory, the board of directors can be effective in monitoring if they are independent of the management, based on the argument that incentives exist for non-executive directors to safeguard the reputation that encourages them to take decisional control (Amar, *et al.*, 2011; Al-Gamrh, *et al.*, 2020; Aluchna, *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, resource dependence theory also believes that a qualified non-executive member of the board contributes to enlarging the pool of available resources and expertise in the firm (Zattoni, *et al.*, 2017; Zubeltzu-Jaka, *et al.*, 2019; Ullah & Kamal, 2020) which will ultimately assist in enhancing the financial performance of the firm. In contrast, stewardship theory states that in comparison to an outsider, inside directors have in-depth knowledge of the daily affairs of the company due to which they are aware of the available and valuable resources that assist in improving the financial performance of the firm (Kyere &

Ausloos, 2020; Liu, *et al.*, 2015; Borlea, *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, based on stewardship theory, this study develops the following hypothesis in relation to board independence and the financial performance of listed companies in FTSE-AIM.

H₂: The proportion of non-executive directors on the board will be an extra expense for the SMEs and due to limited resources, the high number of non-executives will negatively affect the financial performance of the UK-listed AIM companies.

2.9.3 Audit Committee Size and Financial Performance

The major objective of any company's board is to supervise or monitor managerial activities. Due to several duties of the board of directors, some of the potential responsibilities are delegated to different committees (audit, governance, remuneration and nomination committee) (Dobija, 2015). The audit committee (AC) is possibly the most essential committee among the sub-committees of the board. Due to the financial scandals mentioned in Chapter Two, the importance of AC has gained immense attention (Mallin, 2019). The main role of the AC is to keep an eye on the financial reporting, internal control, external affairs, and business risks that result in sound corporate governance (Avison & Cowton, 2012). According to Jizi, *et al.* (2014), the efficiency and effectiveness of AC relies on the size of the committee and the expertise of the members. In the context of resource dependence theory, large ACs tend to be more efficient and capable of managing complex tasks (Oroud, 2019).

Moreover having more members in AC brings more resources to the monitoring process, a wide range of knowledge and expertise (Mustafa, *et al.*, 2018), and managers are likely to feel reluctant to voluntarily reduce the information asymmetry between management and outsider investors and other stakeholders that helps to stabilise the performance of the company (Dakhlallah, *et al.*, 2020). However, based on agency theory, an unduly large size of AC may become less efficient to perform the devolved tasks due to communication problems, inefficiency and delays in decision-making. There is the possibility that an irrelevantly big size of AC might overwhelm the advantages of gaining more resources and a wider knowledge base (Endrawes, *et al.*, 2018). Accordingly, Aldamen, *et al.* (2012); Al-Rassas & Kamardin (2015); Al-Matari, *et al.* (2014); and Alqatamin (2018) also found a positive association between a smaller size of AC with financial knowledge and financial performance of firms in the market. On the other hand, some scholars found that there is a negative or no significant association between ACS

and financial reporting in the companies listed in Oman (Gebayel, *et al.*, 2018; Al-Najjar, 2011; Chan & Li, 2008; Borlea, *et al.*, 2017). However, adopting the agency theory perspective, this study develops the following hypothesis which believes that the large size of AC will lead to needless extra expense by creating a free member problem with inactive participation in the SMEs (Sultana, *et al.*, 2015). Hence, the hypothesis is:

H₃: A large size of audit committee negatively influences the financial performance of the SMEs listed in the FTSE-AIM.

2.9.4 CEO Duality and Financial Performance

The effectiveness of the board in supervising or monitoring management will decrease if the whole power concentrates in the hands of a single individual (Song & Kang, 2019). UK regulators follow the agency theory of corporate governance, according to which the role of the chief executive officer (CEO) in a company and the role of the chairman of the board should be handled by two different individuals (Dedman, 2016). This board structure where the role of the CEO is different from the chairman helps to reduce the agency problem and protect the interest of the shareholders (Duru, *et al.*, 2016). Due to the increasing awareness and importance of corporate governance, the research in CEO duality (where a single individual hold both the positions of CEO and chairman) has grown significantly and many scholars have attempted to examine the relationship between CEO duality (CEOD) and the financial performance of the firms (Ueng & Ramaswamy, 2019). Though the effect of CEOD on firm performance is a well-researched and debated issue, still the results are inconsistent (Lam & Lee, 2008).

The main two perspectives on the view of CEOD are agency theory and stewardship theory (Naseem, *et al.*, 2020). The former theory is quite straightforward on the CEOD aspect as it clearly states that CEOD is inadequate for the financial performance of firms (Peng, *et al.*, 2007). In other words, as per agency theory, having CEOD in the firm signals the absence of separation of decision management and decision control (Abor & Biekpe, 2007). Ultimately, the CEO will control the board due to which a lack of independence and vigilance will occur and the board will not be able to monitor top management effectively, resulting in poor firm performance and increasing the chances of fraud (Wahba, 2015; Rashid, 2010; Kholeif, 2008). Meanwhile, the latter theory supports the CEOD and believes that the CEOD brings the unity of command at the top of the organisation which helps to evade the confusion among employees about who is

their actual boss and provide efficiency in the decision-making process resulting in better financial performance (Kaur & Singh, 2019; Gupta & Mahakud, 2020). Despite these two notions, some scholars found that CEO duality does not influence the financial performance of the firm (Sehrawat, *et al.*, 2020; Puni & Anlesinya, 2020). However, following agency theory and the previous literature, this study develops the following hypothesis:

H₄: The existence of CEO duality will negatively influence the financial performance of listed SMEs in the UK

2.9.5 Board Gender Diversity and Financial Performance

Many companies around the world are facing the current governance issue of the existence of diversity on the board and its effectiveness (Fernández-Temprano & Tejerina-Gaite, 2020). Board diversity (BD) could be in any form which includes the different backgrounds of the members, their race, religion, skills and experience, and gender (Aggarwal, *et al.*, 2019). It is argued that the presence of BD enhances the performance and value of the organisation by enabling the board with a unique and innovative perception, results in better problem-solving capacity (Vafaei, *et al.*, 2015). This study will specifically focus on board gender diversity (BGD) that refers to the proportion of women on the board and their overall effect on the financial outcome of SMEs. Concerning the theoretical base, agency theory indicates that the female board members may bring fresh and novel solutions to complicated problems which will reduce agency costs (Gordini & Rancati, 2017) and improve the board's efficiency and firm's financial performance (Groening, 2019).

Similarly, resource dependency theory has a belief that a company must be self-sufficient for all the critical resources to eradicate the dependency on third parties (Adesanmi, *et al.*, 2019). Hence gender diversity on the board will provide beneficial resources to the company in the form of their legitimacy, skills, abilities, knowledge, and outside knowledge which again leads to the better financial performance of corporations (Ullah, *et al.*, 2019; Ullah, *et al.*, 2020). Though a company can obtain a lot of benefits from BGD in the opinion of Musa, *et al.* (2020), gender diversity on the board tends to provoke more conflicting suggestions which will lead to ineffective and inefficient decision-making. Mixed evidence has been reported by different authors who have investigated the relationship between BGD and financial performance with different samples of firms in different countries (Xie, *et al.*, 2020). Some studies result in positive association

(Mazzotta & Ferraro, 2020; Li & Chen, 2018), whereas other authors have found a negative relationship and some have found no link between BGD on firm performance (Carter, *et al.*, 2010; Charles, *et al.*, 2018; Bohdanowicz, 2011). However, this study believes that in comparison to other theories, resource dependency theory is the most convincing theoretical base for BD and its influence on the firm's fiscal performance. Hence, the following hypothesis has been developed following the previous literature and resource dependency theory:

H₅: The presence of female directors on the board will positively influence the financial performance of SMEs listed in the FTSE-AIM.

Based on the above discussed empirical literature and theoretical underpinnings, a table has been formulated with the list of key references disclosing factors that are already known or came into light in the form of different authors' findings, some other factors that are yet to be discovered about corporate governance structure in SMEs and finally, those factors which will be explored in this study. This table will further help to identify the major gaps in the literature.

Table 2.6: List of Key References

Authors	Study	Years	Sample	Findings	Limitations	Going to achieve in this study
Parsa, <i>et al.</i> , 2007	Disclosure of governance information by small and medium-sized companies	2002-2004	AIM-listed companies	Stakeholder theory has more explanatory power. Considering large companies, they support the presence of NEDs.	Paid attention to only agency and stakeholder theory. An assumption made in context to the presence of NEDs.	This study covers the gap by selecting multiple theoretical approaches. Examines the impact of the presence of NEDs on the financial performance of the SMEs as factors that might work differently for large and small companies.
Abor & Adjasi, 2007	Corporate governance and the small and medium enterprises sector: theory and implications	Conceptual Paper	Presents the relevant issues related to SMEs	CG can bring a new strategic outlook in the form of NEDs to overcome managerial incompetence.	More on a theoretical side and unable to provide a practical solution.	This study strives to come up with recommendations for SMEs to enhance their financial performance while improving their CG structure.
Qadorah & Fadzil, 2018	The effect of board independence and board meeting on firm performance: Evidence from Jordan	2013	64 companies listed on Amman Stock Exchange	Found positive results for the presence of NEDs; however, insignificant results were found for board meetings.	Only relied on accounting measures as a dependent variable and many other board attributes are yet to be examined.	While considering accounting measures, this study is also paying attention to the market measures of financial performance; also takes into consideration other board parameters such as CEO duality, board size and NEDs.

Authors	Study	Years	Sample	Findings	Limitations	Going to achieve in this study
Dakhlallah, <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Audit committee and Tobin's Q as a measure of firm performance among Jordanian companies	2009-2017	180 companies listed in Jordan	Attributes of the audit committee are significantly negatively related to firm performance.	The narrow approach in terms of selecting variables completely omitted the importance of accounting-based measures.	Widens the approach as with the audit committee variable; board parameters has also been considered; both measures of financial performance are taken into consideration.
Ullah & Kamal, 2020	Corporate governance, political connections and firm performance: the role of political regimes and size	2001-2014	150 Pakistani firms	Found mix results of board size, NEDs and board meetings.	Omitted the importance of board diversity; much attention has been paid to large firms.	Board gender diversity is also taken into consideration with other important variables; listed SMEs were taken as a sample of data; and ANOVA analysis was performed in addition to correlation and regression for the robust results.
Borlea, <i>et al.</i> , 2017	Board characteristics and firm performances in emerging economies. Lessons from Romania	2012	55 companies listed on Bucharest Stock Exchange	No statistically significant relationship was found.	Many other board attributes are yet to be examined and limited statistical tools used.	A wide range of board characteristics considered and in addition to correlation and regression, ANOVA analysis was performed for robust results.
Arora & Sharma, 2016	Corporate governance and firm performance in developing countries: evidence from India	2001-2010	1922 firms listed in Bombay Stock Exchange	Supports agency theory in respect to large board size; however, results in no impact of CEO duality on performance.	Paid attention to large firms only; in case of SMEs results may differ	Specifically, SMEs were selected for this thesis as most of the studies examined the impact of CG on FP of large companies and nominal attention has been paid to SMEs' CG structure.

Authors	Study	Years	Sample	Findings	Limitations	Going to achieve in this study
Al-ahdal, <i>et al.</i> , 2020	The impact of corporate governance on financial performance of Indian and GCC listed firms: An empirical investigation	2009-2016	103 companies out of which half (53) listed in Nifty 100 Index in India and the other half (53) listed in GCC countries	Board accountability and ACS has no significant impact on FP of firms.	Only large companies were considered, and no sample involve SMEs. A limited number of independent variables were used.	SMEs are the main sample for which data need to be collected. A wide range of variables is used under the parameters of the board of directors.
Bhagat & Black, 2002	The non-correlation between board independence and long-term firm performance	1985-1995	934 largest firms in the United States	Found evidence that firms suffering from low profitability respond by increasing the independence of their board; however, no evidence found that this strategy works to improve profitability.	Only the largest firms were considered. Yet to test many other variables of the board of directors.	Besides board independence, this study is also examining the impact of board size, CEO duality, board gender diversity and audit committee size on the financial performance of SMEs listed in the UK.

Source: Author

2.10 Gaps in the Literature

The literature review clearly shows that there are abundant scholars who have researched the association between the corporate governance and financial performance of companies (Abor & Biekpe, 2007; Adedeji, *et al.*, 2020; Black & Khanna, 2007). Despite this, there is no conclusive result about it, and this is considered as a gap in the literature. Further, FTSE-AIM is an international platform for SMEs to get listed and to have access to public funds. This market was established in 1995 with 10 companies and now there are more than 800 UK companies registered as SMEs (London Stock Exchange, 2018). Despite the major growth in a few years, these SMEs do not have clear guidance about the CG structure to follow as they have been expected to voluntarily follow the UK Corporate Governance Code which is mainly formed for main listed companies and due to varied sizes, cultures and requirements of SMEs, the UK CG code may not be beneficial for them. Hence, there is clear room to research further a suitable CG structure for listed SMEs in the UK.

Furthermore, nominal research has been done with the sample of UK listed SMEs, specifically with AIM. Initially, an ample amount of research has been done on developed countries in relation to CG, and since then, scholars have moved to developing economies and now started researching CG in the context of SMEs. But still, there is a long way to go and in terms of AIM-listed companies, only nominal research has been conducted on them (Afrifa, 2013b; Afrifa & Tauringana, 2015c; Shah, 2014). According to the new developments in the research field, LSE made it compulsory for AIM companies to follow the corporate governance code. In respect of this, QCA published their CG code (The Quoted Companies Alliance, 2018b). However, this change is so recent that the researcher could not find any empirically tested research on the impact of the QCA code on the FP of the AIM-listed SMEs. Therefore, this research will fill this gap and will provide recommendations to SMEs that will enable them to enhance their FP by applying the CG code.

2.11 Summary

By reviewing the literature, a deep understanding of corporate governance was gained and its impact on the financial performance of the listed SMEs was explored. The chapter

was divided into eight sections and further sub-sections as required. Initially, the author discussed the emergence of CG in section one of this chapter, concentrating on the various definitions of CG and selecting the appropriate definition for this study which covers both the narrow (agency) and wider (stakeholder) scope of CG, also covered in the previous literature (Mostovicz, *et al.*, 2011; Picou & Rubach, 2006; Adedeji, *et al.*, 2020). The second section of this chapter illustrates the major corporate collapses in chronological order. The overall development of CG has been discussed briefly in the third section that explores the overall growth of the codes of CG worldwide. The growth of CG in different countries (either developed or developing) was examined with the help of the CG codes they have developed. Afterwards, the fourth section discussed SMEs, their contribution to the economic development of the UK and the problems and challenges usually faced by them.

Additionally, a description of the AIM has been given, a FTSE registered market in the LSE. This international market has been specifically created for SMEs to provide them with the opportunities to access public funds (Afrifa, 2013b). Likewise, this section further reviewed the CG guidelines and recommendations for the UK-Listed AIM companies (Mallin & Ow-Yong, 2013). The fifth section was devoted to the theoretical underpinning of CG and analysed the main theories of CG including agency, stakeholder, stewardship, and resource dependency theory as this study has adopted multiple theoretical approaches to support the CG variables and to explain how CG influences the FP of SMEs. The theoretical framework led to the conceptual framework in section six. Further, in section seven, by reviewing the empirical literature, the hypotheses of this study were developed and a table of key references was provided to identify the gaps in the literature revealed in section eight. The scarcity of literature was discovered in relation to CG structure for SMEs particularly. CG codes for large companies were developed but there is no CG code for SMEs according to their size, needs and structure. Moreover, the new rule of following any CG code was applied to listed SMEs in the UK but no study has yet empirically tested the impact of the QCA CG code on the FP of SMEs. Therefore, to address these gaps, this study explores the impact of CG attributes on the FP of the UK listed SMEs. The methods used to collect the data and run the analyses are further discussed in the next chapter which considers the research methodology.

CHAPTER 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, the theoretical underpinnings, conceptual framework and formulation of hypotheses were discussed. This chapter represents the research methodology adopted to accomplish this thesis. The research methodology is a systematic process of solving a research problem or answering research questions. This systematic procedure involves various steps to be followed by the researcher in a logical sequence. To carry out research, the researcher should unambiguously understand which research approach, design and methods need to be adopted? This chapter elaborates on all the tools and techniques used to collect the data along with the justification for the methodological choices made by the author. Initially, this chapter begins with the discussion on the research philosophy that is an epistemology which further leads to the research paradigm of this study.

3.2 Research Philosophy

The research philosophy figured the type of research methodology opted for by the researcher and this selection determines the research tools and techniques which will be used to provide the solution for the research problems (Khalidi, 2017). The term research philosophy refers to the development of the knowledge and the nature of that knowledge (Moon & Blackman, 2014). In other words, it precisely states the actions of the researcher to develop knowledge in a particular field (Saunders, *et al.*, 2019). It does not specifically mean to introduce new theory in that field but the development in knowledge will count even if the motive is to answer a particular problem in an organisation (Saunders, *et al.*, 2016). In natural and social sciences, mainly two types of philosophies are essential: ontology (the study of reality) and epistemology (the study of knowledge) (Holden & Lynch, 2004) which are further explained in Table 3.1 on the next page.

Table 3.1: Research Philosophy

Terms	Meaning
Ontology	Study about something that exists in the world and regarding which, humans can obtain knowledge.
Epistemology	Study about the nature of knowledge, how people know about it and assumptions about how knowledge should be gained and accepted.

Source: Moon & Blackman (2014)

Hence, out of the above two options, this study uses the epistemology philosophy as it describes ‘how’ researchers know about knowledge, acquire and accept it, which is also the scenario of the research question in this study (Pathirage, *et al.*, 2008). Moreover, the selection of research philosophy purely depends on the research paradigm, opted for by the researcher to answer the research questions in the best possible way (Bahari, 2010) and as far as the research paradigm of this study is concerned, the positivist paradigm has been selected. Further, in the next section, research paradigms under epistemology will be discussed in detail.

3.3 Research Paradigm

This section further explores the research philosophy through the concept of research paradigms. The research paradigm is considered to be a set of beliefs or basic assumptions that guide the actions of the researcher (Patel, 2015). Generally, the paradigm selected by the researcher defines the intent, motivation and expectations of the research (Mackenzie & Knipe, 2006). Therefore, the research paradigm is a way of examining social phenomena with the help of which a researcher can get an understanding of these phenomena (Noor, 2008). Following this, the researcher explored the four types of research paradigms in Table 3.2 and then justification has been provided for the chosen one.

Table 3.2: Types of Research Paradigm

Research Paradigms	Meaning
Positivists (Postpositivist) Paradigm	Positivism mainly tests a theory and focuses on the developed knowledge “third-person knowledge” that

	contains measurable qualities (Brennan, <i>et al.</i> , 2011). In this paradigm, quantitative methods (surveys, statistics, and structured questionnaires) are widely used by the researchers as these methods provide superior representativeness, a great sense of reliability and integrity of data (Tronvoll, <i>et al.</i> , 2011). It follows a deductive approach, hence offers to test the hypotheses. By adhering to the positivism paradigm, the researcher is usually involved in the cause-effect study; it also allocates the generalisation of the findings (Patel, 2016).
<i>Interpretivist/Constructivist Paradigm</i>	The respective paradigm generates new and richer knowledge of social worlds and interprets them, due to which it is considered exceptionally subjectivist. Moreover, this paradigm suggests only using qualitative methods with smaller samples.
<i>Transformative Paradigm</i>	The researchers who follow this paradigm believe that there is an undefined reality which exists only in the mind and thoughts of persons (Antwi & Hamza, 2015).
<i>Pragmatic Paradigm</i>	The pragmatic paradigm contains a reflexive process of investigation, which begins from doubt and disbelief. Once the problem is solved it re-creates the belief of the researcher (Saunders, <i>et al.</i> , 2016).

Source: Author

3.3.1 Justification for the Selection of a Positivist Paradigm

The positivist paradigm is based on the view that reality is stable and can be actually observed and described objectively. In social research, this paradigm combines deductive logic with empirical and quantitative methods to normally applying regularities. It focuses on measurements and relies on the facts to discover social phenomena and relationships. A positivist paradigm has been selected by the researcher for this study where the hypotheses are developed based on the notion of the impact of corporate governance on the financial performance of listed SMEs in the UK. Additionally, an emphasis is placed on the facts and seeking causality and fundamental laws. It operationalises the concepts to make them measurable by formulating hypotheses and

testing them, which is adequate to answer the research question of this study (Mangan, *et al.*, 2004). Moreover, the positivist approach is most suitable for this study for many reasons: initially, the researcher can use a large sample of the population to test the hypotheses; secondly, according to previous studies, this paradigm is often adopted by similar research; thirdly, most of the studies related to the relationship between corporate governance and financial performance use the development of hypotheses, a deductive approach, quantitative methods and secondary data types, revealing this methodology is the best possible way to conduct the research (Burrell & Morgana, 1994). Finally, this study intends to test the hypotheses focused on the influence of the internal corporate governance mechanisms on the financial performance of the listed SMEs; hence, after considering the nature of this study, the investigator chose this paradigm.

As far as other types of paradigms are concerned, this study rejects the interpretivist paradigm as it mainly focuses on qualitative methods and because of their inability to test the hypotheses. In addition to this, the constructivist paradigm works on small samples whereas a large sample is the requirement of this study. Also, to answer the research question of this study, the theory is required at the beginning of the research, whereas interpretivism inductively develops theory at the end of the study. Furthermore, the transformative paradigm has not been considered by the researcher because this paradigm provides sole attention on one truth and also denying testing the hypotheses (Saunders, *et al.*, 2019). The pragmatic paradigm was rejected as unsuitable because this study strives to answer a few questions and interpret the particular effect of one context on the other (Henderson, 2011) proving a positivist approach is most suitable to answer the research questions.

3.4 Research Approach

Generally, every study begins with a question, whether it is research based on a theory or the theory itself will be the result of the research. Hence, Gray (2004) mentions a criterion that enacts the scientific approach. Traditionally, research has taken place based on mainly two approaches: deductive proof and inductive discovery. However, nowadays an abductive approach has also been introduced that is based on the principles of both the approaches (deductive and inductive) (Alrajeh, *et al.*, 2012). An inductive approach results in the creation of the theory where the researcher observes the findings for the

whole population. Meanwhile, the deductive approach concludes based on the theory for the selected sample of the population.

In response to the present study, a deductive approach has been selected to answer the research questions which is also following the previous selections in this chapter. The reason behind the selection of this approach is the nature of this study which is testing hypotheses based on existing knowledge and theoretical underpinnings (Saunders, *et al.*, 2009). On the other hand, the inductive approach has been rejected because: initially, it will lead to qualitative methods which are not required in this study; afterwards, it only works with small samples and a large sample is required in this research; and this approach does not allow for testing but this study develops hypotheses to test that can be only tested with a deductive approach (Goel, *et al.*, 1997). Therefore, the deductive approach assists the study to eliminate unnecessary components and leads to generalising the context from common to specific.

3.5 Research Design

The previous sections of this chapter show the continuous selection of the research methodology. Initially, an epistemology philosophy has been selected which leads to the selection of the positivism paradigm and the deductive approach. Having selected all these options, it is necessary to choose an appropriate research design to collect the required data. A research design is considered to be a conceptual structure within which research is conducted and it clearly defines and explains the methods that the researcher applied to obtain the results (Kumar, 2018). There are three types of research design: quantitative, qualitative and mixed design and the selection of one of these is entirely dependent on the nature of the study adopted by the author. Concerning a quantitative research design, it develops out of a strong academic background that places confidence in numbers which states suggestions for the research problem. This is also a way to differentiate between quantitative and qualitative data as quantitative data contain numbers and qualitative consist of non-numerical data.

3.5.1 Justification for Selecting the Quantitative Research Design

This research selected the quantitative research design on the basis of various reasons: initially, this design can be fast and economical; it is suitable for a large data sample and more relevant to policymakers because of statistics which will be less complicated to

understand and make decisions (Saunders, *et al.*, 2009). In addition, the chances of biased data collection were also eradicated due to the distance between the researcher and the subject (Kothari, 2004). The previous researchers in the field of corporate governance and financial performance conducted their studies with quantitative methods, hence this study also takes into account the existing literature (Abor & Adjasi, 2007; Adesanmi, *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, this study starts with a closed question which also leads to the quantitative method where hypotheses play an active role. On the other hand, this study rejects the qualitative design as according to the nature of the study, complications may occur to control the pace, progress and endpoints of the research process. According to Amaratunga, *et al.* (2002), policymakers would give low credibility to results from a qualitative research design. As far as mixed methods are concerned, it can be rigorous, expensive and time-consuming to apply both methods. Besides, that could be considered if the nature of the study demanded it. Further, in this chapter a discussion will be included on the selection of a sample, the size of the sample and resources approached to collect the data.

3.6 Research Strategy

Generally, the strategy stands for a plan of action to achieve a goal. Hence, in the context of the research field, it may be defined as a plan of a researcher to achieve the objectives of the study. According to the principles of the research, quantitative research is associated with explanatory and survey research strategies. However, several research strategies are available for selection according to the demands of the study, such as experiment, survey, archival research, case study, and action research and so on (Catherine, 2009). This study will mainly focus on an explanatory research strategy that has also been adopted by many previous researchers (Afrifa, 2013b; Awan, *et al.*, 2020; Sehrawat, *et al.*, 2020). The purpose of this study is inclined to the nature of the explanatory strategy as the aim of this strategy is to study the probability of a change in a dependent variable due to the change in an independent variable (Saunders, *et al.*, 2009). To test the cause-and-effect relationship, an explanatory strategy develops predictions known as hypotheses which are divided into two types: the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis. This strategy uses exploratory and descriptive research to answer questions that start with “what”, “how” and “why”.

Under exploratory research, the focus of the design is to discover ideas and theories where there is still potential to explore. The nature of this type of research can be knowledge enhancing. Another aspect is that nobody knows what is about to come or what will happen next. Therefore, this kind of research strategy is not suitable for this study as the nature of this study is the opposite (Sahu, 2013). On the other hand, a descriptive type of research is prominently used to describe the different aspects of a problem or phenomenon. The main aim of the descriptive research is to describe the situation with multiple points of view to shed more light on the current problems through a process of data collection while having no control over the variables (Kothari, 2004). Meanwhile, the current study completely differs from the descriptive research because the aim is to prove a cause-and-effect relationship between the variables instead of describing the behaviour or features of the sample population.

3.6.1 *Justification for Selecting an Explanatory Research Strategy*

This study strives to test or verify the hypotheses with respect to several objectives which are identical to hypothesis-testing research. The explanatory design was selected because: initially, the simplicity of this design can apply adequately, is easily understandable by the policymakers, and provides more control for the researcher to use sophisticated statistical analysis tools (Sahu, 2013). Moreover, this explanatory research allows the researcher to perform one-way analysis of variance, two-way analysis of variance, analysis of covariance and so on. Further, this chapter will discuss the selected time horizon during which this research was conducted.

3.7 Time Horizons

Another important aspect to consider in preparing the research design is which time horizon is suitable for this research. In the words of Saunders, *et al.* (2019), a researcher can collect data at a particular time that could be a year with a long list of phenomena to analyse (cross-sectional studies), otherwise, a researcher can choose to collect data for a range of years for a single component (time series data) and the last option is to collect data for a range of years with multiple components (longitudinal studies). In this respective study, the researcher selected the cross-sectional time horizon as this is one of the most conventional research designs and also backs up the whole selection of the research methodology (Kanchanaraksa, 2008; Qadorah & Fadzil, 2018). Moreover, in comparison to the available options regarding time horizons, a time-series study has not

been considered for this research because of the requirement of the study to use a large sample and time series does not allow a number of phenomena to be examined.

As far as longitudinal studies are concerned, a doctoral candidate does not select this option due to time constraints, absence of in-depth knowledge of software or the available resources. One of the reasons for not selecting a longitudinal study was the unavailability of access to the financial database due to which the researcher had to consider a short period for collecting data for 96 companies (Olsen & St George, 2004). Moreover, this research was selected for a specific year (2015), immediately after the companies recovered from the financial crisis that happened in 2008. This type of study has another benefit of providing evidence of the relationship between the variables which will be helpful for the policymakers to make decisions about investments (Supino & Borer, 2012). Accordingly, cross-sectional research is considered to be the best option for conducting this research (Mann, 2003). Therefore, as per the cross-sectional time horizon, this study will monitor the change in Y (dependent variable) due to the position of X (independent variable) that occurred at some point in time. Further, the research methods selected for this research have been discussed in detail.

3.8 Research Methods

Often, research methodology and research methods are used interchangeably; however, as explained earlier in this chapter, research methodology considers a whole plan for research whereas research methods are the ultimate choice made by the researcher about specific contents. Similarly, sampling technique will be used to draw the sample from the target population and techniques will be selected by the researcher to evaluate the data (Sanders, *et al.*, 2014). In this section, the researcher will discuss the several research methods available to conduct quantitative research, such as sampling techniques and various statistical tools to run the analysis (Williams, 2007).

3.8.1 Population

In research, the population is considered to be a large collection of well-defined objects or entities. The objects or entities could be anything that depends on the research question such as which field a researcher wants to investigate (Sahu, 2013). This study focused on the companies which are listed in the FTSE-AIM All-Share market, a subsidiary market of LSE. This study selected the AIM market of the LSE as it specifically contains small

and medium enterprises which are the main target of this research. According to the list of all the listed companies in the LSE, after scanning through for AIM companies, it came to light that the population of this study is 857 which includes:

- all the listed companies in FTSE-AIM
- Involving nationally and internationally
- With several sectors

3.8.2 Targeted Population

After obtaining the list of the whole population, the next task for a researcher is to narrow down the area of the population to the targeted population. This is also an important step that leads to the group of SMEs. Although this market contains only the SMEs, it is essential to redefine the population because initially, the above population consisted of national and international firms which cannot be investigated based on the same standards and after that, while reading about companies, the researcher came to know that being listed as SMEs, many firms do not actually fit the definition of SMEs mentioned by the European Commission's recommendation 2003/361/CE of 6th May 2003 (Afrifa & Tauringana, 2015c). Therefore, after applying the definition, the researcher got a list of 150 firms. The specific requirements are mentioned below, out of which SMEs need to fulfil at least two:

- The number of employees in each SME should not be more than 250.
- The annual turnover of each SME should be equal to or less than €50 million.
- The total assets of each SME should be equal to or less than €43 million.

3.8.3 Sample and Sampling Techniques

Usually, to answer the research questions and to achieve the stated objectives, a researcher must consider whether the study needs sampling or not. When a researcher chooses to examine the whole population, it is known as census and for some research, it might be possible due to the small size. But for those who have a large population to investigate, drawing a sample as an alternative to the census is a useful option (Kothari, 2004). A researcher needs to make sure that a sample must represent the whole population. Moreover, investigating the whole population is expensive and time-consuming. Therefore, this study also draws a sample out of the targeted population by applying sampling techniques.

Sampling techniques are classified into two parts: probability sampling methods and non-probability methods. The former one makes sure that each entity of a population has an equal opportunity to get selected in the research. There are a further four types of probability sampling: simple, stratified, systematic and cluster-based (Veal, 2017). And in the case of the latter one (non-probability methods), the probability of each entity is unknown to get selected in the sample from the targeted population. Non-probability sampling techniques are also further classified into four types: convenience, purposive, quota and snowball sampling.

Justification for the selection of the sampling technique

To draw a sample of the study, a simple probability technique and purposive non-probability sampling technique are selected. Initially, the simple probability technique makes sure that each entity gets the same chances of being drawn in the sample (Sanders, *et al.*, 2014). Hence, this technique has been applied that facilitates the researcher to select the participants from a whole set of the population to the targeted population that is the number of companies reduced from 819 to 150. By applying a purposive non-probability sampling technique, the researcher is entitled to select the sample as per the knowledge which is according to the researcher reflects the true picture of the required sample with the available information of 96 companies (Sahu, 2013).

3.9 The Sample Size of the Study and Research Hypotheses

3.9.1 Sample Size of the Study

Generally, sample size denoted by (n) refers to the number of entities with which the sample is constructed. The sample size is usually determined by a number of factors. In this study, a few assumptions have been made to eradicate the possibility of bias and to show the true picture of the sample. Assumptions are also backed up with the previous research (Adam, *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, the population of data that refers to this research is small and medium enterprises listed in the FTSE-AIM market of the LSE. The sample size was drawn from the targeted population which was 150 as per the following criteria that further left with 96 companies as an actual sample size:

- Financial and investment firms or banks have been eliminated from the sample due to different accounting standards and requirements from the rest of the industries (Mathew, *et al.*, 2016).

- Companies that are inconsistent in their accounts have been removed.
- In addition to this, those companies which are unable to provide a significant amount of information required in the research have also been rejected for the actual sample size.

Please refer to Table A.1 for the list of sample companies listed in FTSE-AIM.

3.9.2 Research Hypotheses

Hypotheses have been developed in the previous chapter in accordance with the existing literature and the latest amendments in the rules of listed AIM companies. According to this, all the AIM-listed companies must follow either the main corporate governance code or QCA corporate governance code ([The Quoted Companies Alliance, 2018b](#)). However, H1, H2 and H4 hypotheses have been developed to test the effect of the QCA corporate governance guidelines on the financial performance of the listed SMEs and as per the knowledge of the researcher ([Quoted Companies Alliance, 2019](#)), the QCA guidelines do not include the concept of board gender diversity and audit committee size which are being followed by the main listed companies as these are included in the UK Corporate Governance Code. H3 and H5 have been developed to test the effect of the presence of women on the board and the recommended size of the audit committee on the financial performance of the companies when they were recovering from the effect of financial crises.

H₁: The unduly large size of the board may outweigh the benefits and be negatively associated with the firm performance of listed SMEs in the UK.

H₂: The proportion of non-executive directors on the board will be an extra expense for the SMEs and due to limited resources, a high number of non-executives will negatively affect the financial performance of the UK listed AIM companies.

H₃: A large size of audit committee negatively influences the financial performance of the SMEs listed in the FTSE-AIM.

H₄: The existence of CEO duality will negatively influence the financial performance of listed SMEs in the UK.

H₅: The presence of female directors on the board will positively influence the financial performance of SMEs listed in the FTSE-AIM.

3.10 Data Collection

Data collection plays a vital role in the execution of the research. A researcher is always looking for reliable and suitable mechanisms to collect data or information. Different methods or ways are available to gather relevant information to achieve the aim and objectives. Mainly, two types of data can be collected: primary and secondary. The data which are collected only for the study are known as primary data and secondary data are made up of those considered to be in existence already (Kothari, 2004). It can be in any form, it refers to the data that have been collected and analysed by someone for different purposes. This research is collecting various forms of secondary data to answer the research questions. In addition to this, with the use of structured data, this study develops the variable which is only generated for this study, named Tobin's Q (Abor & Biekpe, 2007). Further, this section justifies the use of secondary data in this study and explains the reasons for not opting for primary data to conduct this study.

3.10.1 Secondary Data

Secondary information consists of extant sources of data in the form of government reports, industry studies, syndicated information, customised information, traditional books, periodicals and journals that are available online and within libraries. Although secondary information offers relatively quick and inexpensive answers to many questions, access to existing data requires knowledge of its existence and the available means to the knowledge. Moreover, to access the sources, networking is required, time investment and efforts are necessary (Stewart & Kamins, 1993). In addition, all this information is not easily identifiable. After carefully developing the research questions and analysing the requirements of the aim and objectives, the researcher decided to use multiple secondary methods to collect the data. This study is focused on historical data which can be only available by secondary methods. The quantitative nature of the study demands data that can be obtained by multiple methods of secondary data collection (Veal, 2017). Following this, there is more discussion on the available options to obtain secondary data and issues faced in getting access to secondary sources.

3.10.2 Types of Secondary Data

Initially, secondary data can be used in both numeric (quantitative) and non-numeric (qualitative) data and fundamentally used in both types of research, descriptive and

explanatory research. In this research, multiple types of data have been used to collect data (Sahu, 2013). Two types of data that were mainly considered in this research are compiled data and structured data. Compiled data are gathered in the form of a list from LSE which contains information for thousands of companies in one place. It was genuinely time-consuming to scan through the whole list and collect data that were relevant for this research. Afterwards, research required structured data which exists on the web world in an organised format (Sanders, *et al.*, 2014). Whenever the cost of obtaining the data is high and that information is useful for multiple users then most users involved pool resources to get the information. The commercial firms may charge fees to provide that information to the user. However, this type of data is standardised and collected regularly and then syndicated to several users (Stewart & Kamins, 1993). To answer the questions of a specific firm or person, this syndicated service may not be effective. Therefore, it is often essential to use customised data in the studies to fulfil the need for specific information. They may also include pooling of resources but the data are mostly collected to answer a set of specific research questions (Kothari, 2004). Similarly, this study uses customised data to answer specific research questions. Below are some of the secondary databases that were considered by the researcher for use in this study.

3.10.3 Multiple Sources to Collect Secondary Data

Nowadays, databases are available internationally according to the different requirements of research studies such as to conduct financial research; the researcher can get access to specific financial databases to find the information, and several of the better-known examples are listed under Table 3.3. Most of these guides are quite general but provide a lot of standardised information about the companies. In addition to that, detailed financial information is available about millions of companies. Such information is often used by investors, competitors and by researchers in finance, accounting and economics (Adams, *et al.*, 2007). Concerning database producers, it can be any organisation including government, commercial firms, non-profit-organisations and academia. However, commercial enterprises are the leading database producers as 68% of all databases are produced by organisations (Stewart & Kamins, 1993). This is also the reason that it is quite expensive for an individual researcher to subscribe to these databases.

Getting access to these databases from libraries or non-profit-organisations will be cost-effective. For the same reason, the researcher took time to collect data as initially, the researcher spent time to gain knowledge of how and from where to collect the data. Afterwards, access to the database was quite expensive to gain but finally, when some libraries were ready to provide access, they were closed (due to pandemic) and there was no remote access to the financial databases at the libraries. In the end, the researcher tried to collect data from the LSE where a list of thousands of companies was provided by LSE with all the listed companies. Somehow, the researcher got a subscription to the FAME database just three months before the thesis submission date with the help of which the researcher triangulated the data. The information about the board of each company has been gathered using their annual reports (Adedeji, *et al.*, 2020). Despite all the difficulties, the researcher made efforts to gain access to the following databases mentioned in Table 3.3 (on the next page). Eventually, the researcher was able to access one invaluable financial database, named FAME.

Table 3.3: Financial Databases About Commercial Organisations

Name	Established	Type of Database	Description	Access/Denied	Reason
Bloomberg	1981	Financial Database	In addition to being a global news and financial information company, invests in important philanthropic programmes to improve the quality of life around the globe and have a diverse and inclusive workforce	Denied	No access to the University of the West of Scotland. Other universities do not allow external students. Public libraries have no access. Cannot be self-funded as very expensive.
DataStream	2008	Financial Database	Data-Stream is an expert in E-commerce and small business websites. Also, provides a simple way to get your business online and provides all the help. In addition to that, keeps all the required information of millions of companies	Denied	No access to the University of the West of Scotland. Other universities do not allow external students. Public libraries have no access. Cannot be self-funded as very expensive.
Amadeus	1989	Financial Database	Amadeus specialises in analytics and data science. Services and expertise include independent guidance and advice; analytics platform deployment; ongoing managed services; training and placing SAS certified graduates.	Denied	No access to the University of the West of Scotland. Other universities do not allow external students. Public libraries have access. Cannot be self-funded as very expensive.
FAME	1991	Financial Database	Comprehensive company databases. that specialise in private company data, corporate ownership including beneficial owners, M&A data and financial strength metrics. International	Access allowed	No access to the University of the West of Scotland. Other universities do not allow external students. Public libraries have access.

			data is standardised so one can compare companies wherever they are in the world.		Self-funded, paid £189 to the city library to get remote access.
Orbis	2002	Financial Database	With information on close to 400 million companies in all countries worldwide, Orbis is the resource for private company data.	Denied	No access to the University of the West of Scotland. Other universities do not allow external students. Public libraries have access.
BoardEx	1999	Company information	The BoardEx proprietary Relationship Mapping Algorithm identifies the most actionable connections for new business opportunities, more than 350 analysts verify, and maintain millions of profiles, ensuring that the data are collected from credible, public sources.	Denied	No access to the University of the West of Scotland. Other universities do not allow external students. Public libraries have no access.
Thomson's & Reuters	1851	Financial Database	The global network of labs explore new business opportunities for Thomson Reuters, working with customers and partners to create quick, agile and collaborative experiments and proofs-of-concept	Denied	No access to the University of the West of Scotland. Other universities do not allow external students. Public libraries have no access.

Source: Author

3.10.4 Challenges Faced During Data Collection Procedure

The study collected the secondary data for the year 2015-2016 to examine the new normal for SMEs after financial crises. Whether a researcher wants access to primary sources or secondary sources to collect the data, the access can be difficult in both types of research methods especially when the researcher lacks support and is facing exceptional circumstances. However, it has been regularly stated that secondary data is easy to collect, beneficial in terms of cost and time (Stewart & Kamins, 1993). But nowadays, on the one hand, there is ample data revolving around the world that can be accessed through the web; on the other hand, any valuable information from a reliable source that is relevant to the study is difficult to access as there are a number of gateways such as subscription charges, standardised information, and fewer options for customised data. There are plenty of challenges when collecting either secondary or primary data, which is time-consuming and expensive too as for this study, the researcher paid £189 to a public library to get access to one of the financial databases. Meanwhile, public libraries are considered one of those resources which are inexpensive for researchers. However, the whole process of secondary data collection and the challenges faced by the researcher are further discussed in this section.

To collect the data, the initial resources available to the researcher were those provided by the University of the West of Scotland. After exploring every database, the researcher realised that there is no access to the financial databases. Then the researcher attended several meetings with librarians to get knowledge about access to relevant databases. In this regard, mails were sent to the librarians of five approachable universities asking for access to any financial database (all universities have multiple financial databases). Two of them rejected the request as the databases of their universities can be accessed by their current students only and the remaining three librarians did not respond. However, for the other three universities, the researcher visited but access was denied as a non-fee-paying student. This was a situation that also applied when asking for supervisory support in gaining access.

The next step taken by the researcher was to contact the British Library. Initially, the researcher contacted them through e-mail. However, the researcher did not receive any reply from them for five working days. Then on a phone call, they confirmed that the only business resource they have is Orbis. Although Orbis is a well-known business database,

exporting data from it was another challenge as there is a restriction in terms of the amount of data one can extract from the database. This restriction made it difficult to collect customised data. However, by then the researcher was also in contact with the LSE to obtain the raw list of listed SMEs ([London Stock Exchange, 2018](#)). After two weeks, the researcher received a response from the LSE with an attachment of all the listed companies in the London Stock Exchange. To extract 96 sample companies from thousands of companies listed in the LSE was very time-consuming and repetitive in nature.

However, the researcher took more than two months to achieve the sample size for the study from the raw list obtained from the LSE. In addition, another two to three months were invested to collect data from each SME's annual report or website. Moreover, to triangulate the data, the researcher subscribed to the FAME database through the city public library which provided remote access to this database due to national lockdown. Besides, the QCA publishes a corporate governance code for the AIM-listed companies which is directly related to this study but here again, the researcher could not get access as this organisation asks for a subscription which was unaffordable for the researcher ([Quoted Companies Alliance, 2019](#)). All the above-said hurdles clarify that obtaining secondary data is not always easy as though the information is available online, it is not necessarily affordable for the individual researcher. Besides these hurdles, the researcher was able to collect secondary data and the justification for selecting secondary is explained below.

3.10.5 Justification for the Selection of Secondary Data

Before embarking on a primary research effort, it is essential to identify whether useful data is already available or not. Otherwise, the time, resources and effort of the researcher and the candidates who participated in the primary research will be of no use. The extant data may have been collected for some other purpose or may be for a completely different research study; however, it is possible to use it in quite distinct ways in some other studies ([Stewart & Kamins, 1993](#)). This research chooses secondary research methods to collect data as these have some distinctive advantages over primary data collection methods and efforts. The most significant out of all the advantages are related to time and money. Moreover, during the pandemic, secondary data had other advantages over primary data in terms of health & safety and to follow government guidelines such as social distancing.

These unusual circumstances come under the category of sensitive situations which emphasise the significance of secondary research (Saunders, *et al.*, 2009). In addition to this, if stringent budget and time constraints are imposed on the primary research then secondary research may provide higher-quality data than could be collected with a new research project. The secondary research data may also lead to further unforeseen discoveries or unexpected new insights.

Secondary research is often done with permanent data and in this study, this is the case as annual reports or business data are more likely to be permanent which gives the advantage of public scrutiny in the future. Therefore, data for the study were obtained from the archival data in the form of annual reports of the listed companies or the websites of the sampled companies. Listed SMEs were selected because listed entities provide ready-to-access information in an appropriate usable form (Lang & Lundholm, 1993). Moreover, it may not have been possible to collect the data required for this study from unlisted SMEs because they are not obliged to follow those CG principles investigated in this study. Mandatory and voluntary information is generally provided through the annual report which could be business, financial or non-financial information and compromise either qualitative or quantitative research. For this research, both qualitative and quantitative data were used and then coded to upload into the Gretl software. The resources used were secondary but are considered to be the most original, reliable, practical and free from any bias (Stewart & Kamins, 1993). Secondary methods are most suitable and relevant in the era of a pandemic when companies are providing data online for interested investors, audiences and researchers.

3.11 Rationale for Research Methodology

This section discusses the significance of the chosen research methodology. The data-set used in this empirical analysis was derived from the financial statements of listed SMEs in the UK for the year 2015. The study sampled 96 SMEs with equal to or less than 250 employees and equal to or less than €50 million turnover in 2015. The raw list of the selected population with 150 small and medium enterprises was obtained from the FAME database which further reduced the sample size to 96 companies according to the filters mentioned above and the availability of the data. However, the information about corporate governance measures and accounting-based measures was manually collected. Sources were annual reports and websites of the respective companies for the year 2015

and information about the market-based measures was collected from the official site of the London Stock Exchange. To achieve the target, the researcher used a useful general model (see Figure 3.1). The following diagram illustrates the steps followed to achieve the aim of the study.

Figure 3.1: Research Process

Source: (Walker, 1997)

As shown, the researcher began with a rather vague idea of a potential research problem which was looking at corporate governance and its relationship with the financial performance of the firms. After thorough research about the concept of CG within the literature, the researcher was able to identify the research problems and literature gaps related to the underdeveloped CG structure of SMEs. The fourth step of the process shows the researcher chose the theoretical framework for the study that is a multiple theoretical framework with the help of which the conceptual framework of the study was formulated. These frameworks assisted the researcher in clearly identifying the essential variables to answer chosen research questions. Then, to examine the relationship between CG and FP, hypotheses were formulated with different combinations of variables. The next step was one of the most important steps of the whole research process which was the choice of

the most applicable research methodology for the study where the researcher decided the research approach, design and method.

The positivist approach has been selected for this particular study because a positive approach seeks facts or causes of social phenomena. It combines deductive logic with empirical analysis and mainly quantitative methods to identify social phenomena and relationships (Payne & Payne, 2000). Hypotheses testing and measurements are the elements of the positivist approach and the same has been adopted by this study to examine the relationship between corporate governance and the financial performance of SMEs. Basically, the research philosophy of this study is informed by the fact that there is no need to produce a new theory but to test the existing ones based on the analysis of quantitative data. A deductive approach is therefore most suitable for this research. Quantitative methods are referred to for this research to deal with longer periods and larger data samples increasing the generalisation capacity (Adesanmi, *et al.*, 2019). In addition to these attributes, quantitative methods provide statistical results which are less complicated and more relevant to policymakers as these methods are free from bias. Moreover, it helps the researcher to start with closed questions where hypotheses play an active role as this is another important reason to select this method.

The study employs the use of secondary data for gathering and analysing the data to address the research aim and objectives. The secondary data-set has two classifications of data that are compiled and structured and both have been used to collect the data for this study. The researcher thinks carefully beforehand about what type of data is required and which methods are going to be appropriate (Kothari, 2004). Data collection also depends on the variables of the study. In this study, the composition of the board of directors and the indicators of financial performance are the selected variables to achieve the aim of this study. The sample companies are listed companies in LSE requiring adherence to the basic rules of transparency and accountability. According to this, each listed company needs to publish information about their board and financial figures annually and all this information needed to be gathered to achieve the aim of this study.

Though the information collected from annual reports and websites of the company is secondary, however, this is the most original, reliable and practical source to collect the required information. Further, this information has been used by the researcher to obtain the financial variables with the help of a few calculations that are further explained in this

section. Moreover, secondary methods are the most suitable data collection methods in the era of a pandemic. The seventh step leads the researcher to analyse the collected data and that has been done with the help of Gretl software. After analyses and interpretation, the final and last chapter of this study provides the answers to the research question in detail and discusses whether the hypotheses have been accepted or rejected. Further in this section, Figure 3.2 clearly shows how the data about corporate governance variables have been collected and coded as per the requirement of the software.

Figure 3.2: Data Collection Procedure for Corporate Governance Measures

Source: Author

The sample companies have been selected from the FTSE-AIM market which is a market for international SMEs only. The raw list of all the companies listed in FTSE-AIM has been collected from LSE by requesting them through email. However, the complete sample size has been gathered from the FAME database after applying numerous filters with a list of 150 listed SMEs. However, the sample size was further reduced to 96 companies due to the non-availability of information; as shown in the above figure, the researcher proceeded to collect the information if a company provided all the required information about the independent and dependent variables. After obtaining the final list of 96 SMEs, the researcher began to visit each company's website or their annual reports for the year 2015 to hand collect the information about mainly five corporate governance

variables that are board size (BS), audit committee size (ACS), CEO duality (CEOD), board gender diversity (BG), and board independence (BI).

BS was measured as per the total number of current members on the board. For some companies, the researcher found this information in their annual report and for some others, the researcher needed to explore their website. While gathering the information about BS, the researcher was able to collect information about other variables as well, namely BI, BG and CEOD. BI was measured by the number of non-executive members on the board and BG was calculated by the number of female members on the board. CEOD is a dummy variable for which the researcher coded the data, where data denotes ‘one’ if the company is following a separate leadership structure and recorded ‘zero’ if the same person is chairing the board who is also the CEO of the company. Meanwhile, in the case of ACS, the total number of members in the audit committee was recorded. Although the source was secondary, it is an original and reliable source that is completely free from bias because distance exists between the researcher and the entity. This set of information is customised and hand-collected by the researcher for this specific study. In the same way, information was gathered for dependent variables and data were primarily calculated by applying the formulas as shown in Figure 3.3 on the next page.

Figure 3.3: Data Collection Procedure for Financial Performance Measures

Source: Author

The information about financial performance measures was also gathered from the same list of 96 companies which were used to collect the information about corporate governance variables. Mainly two dependent variables were collected in this study, namely Return on Assets (ROA) and Tobin's Q. In the case of ROA, the revenue and total assets of the company were recorded for the year 2015 and then the researcher calculated the percentage of it by dividing the net profits by the book value of total assets. Further, to calculate Tobin's Q, the information gathered from the annual report was total market value, total assets and total debts of the company. To get the ratio of it, the formula used was total market value added to the total debts and the whole sum divided by total assets of the company. The formulas used to derive the data were obtained by following the previous literature (Kamal Hassan & Saadi Halbouni, 2013; Rehman & Shah, 2013; Tayeh, *et al.*, 2015) but the values of both the variables for each company were specifically calculated by the researcher for this study only. In this way, the researcher made an effort to interpret the data collected from secondary sources in a unique manner because the exact data of dependent variables were never used before for any similar study. Further, this chapter discusses the data processing and analysis techniques to answer the research questions.

3.12 Data Processing and Analysis

After completing the data collection procedure, further, the researcher must make sure that data are processed and analysed, according to the purpose of the research. [For scientific research, it is more essential for a researcher to make sure that the relevant data have been collected for making comparisons and analysis. Further, Kothari (2004) makes it simple to understand the data processing and analysis procedures. A process to follow certain steps for editing, coding and classifying the collected data is known as data processing; this step amends the data so that they can be analysed. On the other hand, when a large amount of data has been collected, data are analysed with the help of software (Saunders, *et al.*, 2009). In this research, the researcher followed these steps and data have been edited, coded as per the requirement and classified before proceeding towards the analysis of data.

3.12.1 Data Processing

After gathering the data for the selected companies, the researcher edited and coded the data in MS Excel. Initially, the multiple structured data need to be edited and bring it to

reality to understand it. Out of the list of 150 companies around 54 companies have been rejected due to multiple reasons, lack of information belongs to the financial industry, and got liquidated by the end of the year 2015. This procedure helps to reach a set of homogenous companies based on common factors. And finally, a sheet is prepared with the data that can be analysed. Further, the next chapter discusses the processing in detail.

3.12.2 Data Analysis

After carefully processing the data, the next step was to analyse the data. Either quantitative data or qualitative data have to be analysed by using statistical or logical techniques to reach the results and answer the research questions. Data analysis is a process of identifying the relationship between variables by testing the developed hypotheses. Though MS Excel is also sufficient to run the analysis, in this study, Gretl software has been used to analyse the data. The statistics which have been used to do the analyses are descriptive, inferential, and ANOVA tests.

3.12.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics involve describing and comparing the data in numeric form by using central tendency and dispersion which has been clearly explained in the next chapter.

3.12.2.2 Inferential Statistics

By performing these statistics, the researcher was able to find out the association between the corporate governance variables and financial performance variables. Before performing the inferential statistics, the assumptions have been made for homoscedasticity and the normality test of residuals has been performed by the researcher. Further, in these statistics, Ordinary least square (OLS) regression was applied to the cross-sectional data (Elsayed, 2011). Moreover, when both (dependent and independent) variables of the study are in numeric form, the researcher can use Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient (PMCC) that defines the degree of association between two variables.

3.12.2.3 ANOVA tests

Under this test, the researcher made two or more distinct groups of data on the basis of descriptive variables to run the ANOVA test (Adkins, 2014). This is an analysis of variance in which different ranges of data values will be analysed in their respective

groups and the researcher, in the end, will be able to analyse which range of group shows the best results by comparing the mean.

3.12.3 The Credibility Test of Data

The credibility of research work is essential to consider as it is a way to show that a phenomenon selected for research has been honestly represented. Moreover, when the researcher appropriately selects the research methods, the credibility of his/her work is automatically enhanced. The credibility of this study has been maintained by adopting various methods.

3.12.3.1 Methods Inclined with the Existing Literature

This thesis has adopted secondary resources to collect the data by using financial databases, government sites and the published annual reports of the listed AIM companies. The same methods have been used by many authors who have looked at the influence of corporate governance on the financial performance of the companies, with which the credibility of this thesis intensified.

3.12.3.2 Triangulation of Data

Further, triangulation of data is another most significant method to test the credibility of research. To triangulate the data various sources need to confirm the findings. Therefore, after collecting the data manually, the researcher tried to gain access to one of the databases with the help of which the data have been triangulated and then various analysis methods were adopted by the researcher to triangulate the findings.

3.12.4 Validity Checks for Quantitative Research

Validity checks are normally done to ensure that the variables represent the measure for which they have been selected. This study made validity checks with the help of two validity measurements. Initially, a convergent measure diagnoses the similarities between the variables supported by Pearson's correlation matrix (Sürücü & Maslakçı, 2020). Further, a predictive validity check was made by performing OLS regression analysis which assists in predicting future effects. Moreover, robust results were cross-checked using ANOVA analysis. A description of the different types of validity tests is given in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Validity Tests Employed in this Research

Validity Tests	Description
Convergent Validity Tests	It measures the similarities between the independent and dependent variables with the help of Correlation (r).
Predictive Validity Tests	It predicts the outcome in the future, shown with the help of a Regression value.

Source: (Sürücü & Maslakçı, 2020)

3.12.5 Reliability Checks for Quantitative Research

Reliability tests were performed in quantitative research to measure the consistency of the variables. The internal consistency can be measured by Cronbach's Alpha (Drost, 2011). All the variables that were grouped were found to be statistically acceptable. Most of the researchers believe that a reliability coefficient or Cronbach's Alpha of 70% or more than that is considered to be acceptable (Sürücü & Maslakçı, 2020). The results of the various reliability tests for independent and dependent variables are shown in detail in Chapter 4.

3.13 Access and Ethics in Research

After the literature review, the most important part of the whole research is the access to the available resources and ethics approval to complete the studies. Initially, access was required to gain information and to obtain the data. To complete the studies, the researcher needed to gain access to the financial database to obtain information about the AIM-listed companies, a list of companies under the criteria of the definition of SMEs, financial information, historical market values and information about board members. As per the previous studies, financial databases are reliable sources to gain this type of data. In addition to that, by using contacts through emails with the LSE, British Library, City Library and personal contacts, the researcher would be able to collect the data.

As far as ethical issues are concerned, this study made every effort possible to maintain the basic ethics level as, due to the selected methods, the researcher was not required to file for formal ethics approval. This has also been confirmed by the DOS (Dr Julia Fallon) and Programme Leader of the DBA London campus (Dr Bobby Mackie). However,

considerable efforts were made to maintain the ethics of the research even while striving to get access to the financial databases through web communication. Wherever required researcher made contact that too without any emotional or physical harm and discrimination.

3.14 Summary

The researcher made choices to plan the research methodology of this thesis. This chapter explains all the selections made by the author to conduct the research. Initially, the epistemological research philosophy was selected which leads the researcher to choose the research paradigm and according to the requirements of the research questions, a positivist research paradigm was selected as this allowed the researcher to develop the hypotheses and use large samples of data. Further, there was another question of selection in front of the author regarding the research approach. In this case, the deductive approach was selected to achieve the aim and objectives which further facilitates the researcher to test the hypotheses. Then a quantitative design was decided to collect data suitable for research containing the large sample, basically where entities or objects >30 that sample considered as a large sample and qualitative methods will not be that efficient to collect data. Further, an explanatory research approach was chosen to investigate the relationship between corporate governance guidelines and the financial performance of 96 AIM-listed companies. The secondary data were collected for this research with the help of the LSE and annual reports of the companies themselves. Further, it was decided to conduct three analyses (descriptive, inferential and ANOVA) which interpret the results in an easy and understandable way for the researcher, decision-makers and SMEs. The data were analysed with the help of MS Excel and Gretl software. Further, the next chapter will discuss the findings and analysis of the data collected.

CHAPTER 4: Research Analysis and Findings

4.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, the research methodology of this study has been discussed in detail while explaining the different types of research approaches, design, strategy and methods, the choices made by the researcher to conduct this thesis and provide justifications for the selection made. Based on the research methods, this chapter will discuss the research analysis and findings of the study. The objective of this chapter is to provide a structure to the collected data so that it can be easily understandable and then analyse it with the help of Gretl software and present it in the form of tables which were created in Excel. This chapter begins with the descriptive analysis of the data where the researcher discusses the variables, the respective formulas to measure them and the basic regression model followed by the researcher. Further, the study will discuss the descriptive statistics which were again produced by Gretl and presented with the help of Excel. In addition to that, validity and reliability tests were performed to ensure the internal consistency of the data. Furthermore, the inferential analysis was discussed while explaining normality tests, Pearson's correlation matrix, multiple regression analysis and finally analysis of variance (Darko, *et al.*, 2016). The relationship between the corporate governance and financial performance of the AIM-listed SMEs are well described by both descriptive and inferential analysis and further lead to testing of the hypotheses. In the end, a summary has been provided of this chapter.

4.2 Description of Variables

To recognise the importance of various factors of corporate governance, several researchers test different variables. Some pay specific attention to ownership concentration, remuneration of the directors, directorship, and attributes of the board of directors. Similarly, in this study, the attributes of the board of directors and the factors of the audit committee have been considered as independent variables. In the same way, dependent variables have also been selected in a wide range, depending on the research problem. This study is striving to find a relationship between corporate governance factors and the financial performance of the listed SMEs. Therefore, the dependent variables in this research are financial performance measures and two types of measures

have been selected: one based on accounting measures and the other based on market measures. A detailed description of the variables is shown in Table 4.1 (below):

Table 4.1: Description of Variables

Variables	Acronym	Measurement
<i>Measures of Financial Performance</i>		
Return on Assets	ROA	Ratio of Net Income to Total Assets
Tobin's Q Ratio	QRATIO	Ratio of [(Market Value of Equity + Book Value of Debt) / Book Value of Assets]
<i>Measures of Corporate Governance</i>		
Board Size	BS	Total number of Directors in the Board
Board Independence	BI	Total number of Non-Executives members in the Board
Size of Audit Committee	ACS	Total number of members in Audit Committee of the firm
Board Gender	BG	Total number of Women in the Board
CEO-Duality	CEOD	Binary measure that equals to 0 if CEO is also the chairman of the company, otherwise 1.

Source: Author

In the above table, the researcher describes the dependent and independent variables used in this research. With regard to the dependent variable as per the knowledge of the researcher, there is no specific set of firm performance measures suggested. It can be valued with different aspects according to the requirement of the researcher. As the dimension of firm performance, researchers have focused on both 'hard' performance measures and 'soft' performance measures (Thanos & Papadakis, 2012). The former relates to the financial outcome such as return on assets, return on capital employed, turnover, profitability, and other ratios. Whereas the latter measures relate to innovation, learning and customer satisfaction. However, this study is mainly focused on objective measurements of financial performance represented as financial data. A great range of literature presents mainly two types of financial performance measures: accounting-based measures and market-based measures. Mostly, researchers use accounting-based measures as a dependent variable as these measures are easy to control compared to market-based measures (Abor & Biekpe, 2007). Moreover, these measures are the actual

figures obtained based on actual performance whereas market-based measures are predictive values. This gap has been filled in this research as both measures have been considered by the researcher which enhances the robustness of the study.

4.2.1 Measures of Financial Performance

4.2.1.1 Return on assets (ROA)

Generally, the profitability status of each firm is demonstrated by the accounting-based measures which can be evaluated in numerous ways. The variable which represents the accounting measure in this study is the return on assets (ROA), which has been gathered from the annual report of each company. Specifically, ROA has been selected by the researcher as it represents the performance of a company in both a subjective and objective manner (Tayeh, *et al.*, 2015). Being a profitability ratio, ROA shows the capability of the management to make profits by using assets of the company that will provide a good return to the value invested by the shareholders. The formula used to derive the ROA for each company has been mentioned below:

$$\text{Return on Assets} = \text{Earnings after Interest and Tax} / \text{Total Assets}$$

- Net Income = Earnings after interest and tax for the year 2015
- Total Assets = Book value of assets for the year 2015

4.2.1.2 Tobin's Q (QRATIO)

Another variable selected by the researcher to demonstrate the firm performance of the companies is Tobin's Q. It is a market-based measure that shows the growth opportunities of the firm in the market. In 1969, James Tobin developed this significant indicator of performance which predicts the value of the intangible assets of the company such as goodwill, market value, and efficiency of the management (Rehman & Shah, 2013). While following the assumptions of agency theory, researchers prefer to examine the financial performance of the firm based on accounting measures as these measures are more controllable than market measures. However, by only considering accounting measures, the chances of bias or false representation of research may occur as management can manipulate the accounts. Hence, it is highly necessary to consider market measures that are less manageable by the authorities of the companies due to the

involvement of external factors (Kamal Hassan & Saadi Halbouni, 2013). Data for calculating the Tobin's Q ratio has been obtained from the LSE site and annual reports 2015-2016 of the companies. The formula which has been used to calculate the QRATIO of all the companies is stated below.

$$QRATIO = (MVE + BVD) / BVA$$

- QRATIO = Tobin's Q
- MVE = Market Value of Equity
- BVD = Book Value of Debt
- BVA = Book Value of Assets

The selection of all the variables and the formula has been done in accordance with the previous literature (Ahmed & Hamdan, 2015; Leung, *et al.*, 2014; Mahadeo, *et al.*, 2012). As explained earlier, QRATIO is a growth measure that indicates with its results whether there are chances for a company to grow or not. It is defined as the market value of assets of a firm to replacement cost of these assets. According to Afrifa & Tauringana (2015c), if the value of QRATIO for any company is less than 1, it means that there is no indication of growth for that firm but if it is greater than 1 then there are growth opportunities for that firm.

4.2.2 Measures of Corporate Governance

4.2.2.1 Board Size (BS)

Overall, this study paid attention to five variables of internal corporate governance. Out of all the CG variables, BS has been discussed in this section with the information of how it has been measured for use in this study. The focus on board size has been raised by Fama & Jensen (1983). The debate is what is the optimum size of the board as one size for the board cannot be suitable for all firms as it also depends on the size of the firm. To measure the variable, this study considers board size as per the seats in the board which include non-executives (externals), executives (internals) and CEO (only if sitting on the board). Below is a measure to collect the board size in numerical form.

Board Size (BS) = Number of directors in the board

4.2.2.2 Board Independence (BI)

Board independence refers to the level of presence of non-executive directors in the board in comparison to executive members in the board. It also refers to the percentage of the total number of non-executive directors to the total number of directors on the board (Zabri, *et al.*, 2016). According to the UK corporate governance code, at least half of the board needs to be independent or a large company's board must contain three non-executive members and small companies must contain at least two members. This study measures the board independence of the boards of AIM-listed companies in the following way:

Board Independence (BI) = Total number of non-executive directors in the Board

4.2.2.3 Size of the Audit Committee (ACS)

An audit committee is another important corporate governance mechanism that consists of the board members but not the members of top management. Those members of the board are considered as independent members and are selected based on their knowledge and skills (Zraiq & Fadzil, 2018). Their main responsibility is to help the auditors of the firm. The reason behind selecting this variable was because accounting frauds was one of the main reasons for the collapses. The way the size of the audit committee has been measured is mentioned below:

Size of Audit Committee (ACS) = Total number of members in audit committee

4.2.2.4 Board Gender Diversity (BG)

The presence of women on the board is considered to be a new source of ideas, knowledge and experience with better communication. Many firms are hiring female directors as board gender diversity seems like an asset to a company as the presence of a female on the board enhances the image of the company and the company is able to attract investors (Ahmadi, *et al.*, 2018). Some authors have measured the board gender diversity as a percentage of female directors on the board to the total board of directors (Li & Chen, 2018). However, some measured in number as mentioned below:

$$\text{Board Gender Diversity (BGD)} = \text{Total number of female directors on the board}$$

4.2.2.5 CEO Duality (CEOD)

It is believed that the CEO will be more powerful when the same person holds the position of CEO and board chairman and there will be more chances that the CEO may optimise his power at the expense of the shareholders (Jackling & Johl, 2009). Therefore, a separate leadership structure offers separation of the role of the CEO from the chairman of the board. In this study, it has been considered as a dummy variable which is measured as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{CEO Duality (CEOD)} \\ &\text{If CEO is chairman} = 0 \\ &\text{If separate leadership structure} = 1 \end{aligned}$$

This section attempts to describe the measures of independent and dependent variables with the justifications for choosing specific formulas to calculate the different variables. The selected methods to measure the variable are inclined with the previous research. Further, in this chapter, descriptive statistics of the selected data have been discussed.

4.3 Frequency Distribution of Variables

Before descriptive and inferential analysis, it is vital to understand the variables of the data individually and then in a group. Variables can be analysed by: univariate statistics

and multivariate statistics. Analysis of a single variable is called univariate analysis of a variable and when some variables are analysed as per a “single” variable, this is multivariate analysis (King & Eckersley, 2019). Additionally, this study used a histogram as a visualisation technique that provides a better understanding of the data collected by the researcher.

Histograms are one of the most common visualisation techniques for data-sets. Most of the data-sets observed in the form of histograms look the same in shape. These are specifically used for continuous and discrete data types. A normal histogram often reaches a peak and then reduces from both sides in a bell-shaped symmetric way (Ramachandran & Tsokos, 2021). The data will be skewed if the data-set is not approximately symmetrical. Further, it is considered that data are skewed to the right if there is a long tail on the right side of the histogram. Similarly, data are skewed to the left if there is a long tail on the left side of the histogram.

4.3.1 Univariate Data Visualisation

4.3.1.1 Histogram of Board Independence

The histogram of board independence shows that the data for this variable are normally distributed as it follows the symmetry of the normal histogram. Therefore, the mean and median of this data-set will be nearly equal. According to the graph (on the next page), it can be understood that every firm has non-executive directors on their board; however, the range is fluctuating as the approximately same number of companies between 25-30 are having two as a minimum and four as maximum non-executive directors in the board. Please refer to Table B.2 in Appendix B for the numerical presentation of the frequency distribution of BI.

Figure 4.1: Histogram of Board Independence

Source: Author Analysis

4.3.1.2 Histogram of Audit Committee Size

Like the previous histogram, the histogram of the audit committee size data sample is also normally distributed. The peak of the histogram lies at the top and approximately in the middle, so the mean and median of this data-set are also nearly equal. The graph on the next page shows that most of the companies have an audit committee with three members. However, still a fair range of companies have an audit committee of fewer than two members. Please refer to Table B.3 in Appendix B for the numerical presentation of the frequency distribution of ACS.

Figure 4.2: Histogram of Audit Committee Size

Source: Author Analysis

4.3.1.3 Histogram of Board Size

The data-set of the board size variable is approximately normally distributed and according to the graph on the next page, the highest number of AIM-listed companies, approximately half of the companies, have a board size of between six to eight members overall. A very few companies have more than ten members and less than three members on the board. Please refer to Table B.4 in Appendix B for the numerical presentation of the frequency distribution of BS.

Figure 4.3: Histogram of Board Size

Source: Author Analysis

4.3.1.4 Histogram of CEO Duality

According to the histogram of CEO duality, there is no symmetrical distribution found. Therefore, the distribution is skewed to the left. The graph on the next page also represents that a high number of AIM-listed companies are following the guidelines and it is found that more than 80 companies in a sample are following the separated leadership structure. Only a few companies still have CEO duality in their board structure. Please refer to Table B.5 in Appendix B for the numerical presentation of the frequency distribution of CEOD.

Figure 4.4: Histogram of CEO-Duality

Source: Author Analysis

4.3.1.5 Histogram of Board Gender Diversity

The histogram of board gender diversity is slightly skewed to the left as the left tail of the bell shape is stretched. The graph on the next page also shows that around 65 SMEs listed in AIM do not have any female directors on their board. Only 25-27 companies have only a woman on their board. Please refer to Table B.6 in Appendix B for the numerical presentation of the frequency distribution of BGD.

Figure 4.5: Histogram of Board Gender Diversity

Source: Author Analysis

4.3.1.6 Histogram of Tobin's Q

Tobin's Q is a dependent variable, the frequency distribution of which is not normal, and it has been skewed to the left. Further, it can be analysed from the graph (on the next page) that around 30-35 companies have opportunities to grow as their Q ratio is less than one. According to the market evaluation, all those companies that have a Q ratio of more than one have fewer growth opportunities. Please refer to Table B.7 in Appendix B for the numerical presentation of the frequency distribution of QRATIO.

Figure 4.6: Histogram of Tobin's Q

Source: Author Analysis

4.3.1.7 Histogram of Return on Assets

The histogram graph of return on assets (on the next page) is also asymmetrically distributed as it has been skewed to the left. It is clear from the graph that most of the companies have no return or a negative return on assets. A very few companies show slight returns on their assets. Please refer to Table B.8 in Appendix B for the numerical presentation of the frequency distribution of ROA

Figure 4.7: Histogram of Return on Assets

Source: Author Analysis

This section shows the frequency of distribution in a univariate form. Further, the multivariate data visualisation is discussed in the next section with another test, known as the normality test of residuals.

4.4 Normality Test of Residuals

To present the normality of residuals, the researcher discussed a few more tests such as the Jarque-Bera test, Shapiro-Wilk test and Chi-Square test. These tests were performed with the help of skewness and kurtosis of the least square residuals to determine whether the residuals used in the models are normally distributed or not (Schoder, *et al.*, 2006). Similar to the previous section, this section also shows the normality of residuals with the help of a histogram; however, this time, a multivariate data visualisation technique has been used. As explained earlier, skewness reveals the deviation of the distribution of residuals from the symmetry. If the distribution is skewed to the right or the graph shows bunching to the left, then it is positively skewed and if skewed to the left or there is bunching of residuals to the right then it is negatively skewed (Górecki, *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, kurtosis has also been discussed in this section as whenever the residuals are asymmetrically distributed, it entails some skewness or kurtosis. Skewness has

already been discussed and as far as kurtosis is concerned, it shows the level of peskiness or flatness of the distribution in comparison to the normal distribution. Further, two models have been tested, one with QRATIO and another with ROA. In addition to this, the results have been presented in the form of histograms for a better understanding and the normal Q-Q plot of standardised residuals presented the graphical test for the distributions of the residuals.

4.4.1 *QRATIO Model*

Under this test, all other variables have been analysed as per only one variable that is QRATIO. The results below show that the Jarque-Bera normality test is 152.047 with significance of 9.63E-34 and the Shapiro-Wilk W test and chi-square test are both positive and highly significant as the significance of both the tests is less than a 5% level of confidence. Therefore, the null hypothesis of the QRATIO model that the residuals are normally distributed is rejected. Please refer to Table B.9 in Appendix B for the Gretl file of this data as the following table has been made in Excel for better understanding.

Table 4.2: Normality Test Results (QRATIO)

	<i>Jarque-Bera test</i>		<i>Shapiro-Wilk W</i>		<i>Chi-square tes</i>	
	Statistic	Sig.	Statistic	Sig.	Statistic	Sig.
Standardized Residuals	152.047	9.63E-34	0.804669	6.04E-10	88.035	0.000

Source: Author

4.4.1.1 *Multivariate Data Visualisation*

The histogram of the QRATIO model has been presented on the next page, according to which the distributions of residuals are asymmetrical as it is skewed to the right, according to which it is positively skewed. Similar results have been provided by the above normality tests.

Figure 4.8: Histogram of Residual Distribution (QRATIO Model)

Source: Author

4.4.1.2 Q-Q Plot Graph

The Q-Q plot has been presented below which shows the sample quantiles plotted against the expected quantiles. Expected quantiles represent a straight line for the normal distribution. As per Figure 4.9 (on the next page), the sample quantiles are not extended far from the expected ones though revolving around which shows the asymmetrical distributions of residuals.

Figure 4.9: Q-Q Plot of Standardised Residual (QRATIO Model)

Source: Author

4.4.2 ROA Model

Similar to the QRATIO model this section is examining the normal distribution of the data collected for the variable ROA. Mainly three tests have been performed and all the tests were highly significant as the p-value < 0.05 . However, it seems like the distribution is slightly skewed to the left. Therefore, there is a negative relationship between ROA and other variables. Please refer to Table B.10 in Appendix B for the Gretl file of this data as the following table has been made in Excel for better understanding.

Table 4.3: Normality Test Results (ROA)

	<i>Jarque-Bera test</i>		<i>Shapiro-Wilk W</i>		<i>Chi-square test</i>	
	Statistic	Sig.	Statistic	Sig.	Statistic	Sig.
Standardized Residuals	130.2	5.34E-29	0.906783	4.46E-06	24.844	0.000

Source: Author

4.4.2.1 Multivariate Data Visualisation

According to the histogram below, there is a bell-shaped curve; however, it seems like it has been slightly skewed to the left which concludes that the histogram is negatively skewed.

Figure 4.10: Histogram of Residual Distribution (ROA Model)

Source: Author

4.4.2.2 Q-Q Plot Graph

The Q-Q plot of the ROA model represents that the sample quantiles are almost inclined with the estimated quantiles for normal distribution. Therefore, the distribution of the residuals was not significantly deviated as shown in Figure 4.11 (on the next page). However, slight deviation can be found that could be possible due to the outliers in the data.

Figure 4.11: Q-Q Plot of Standardised Residual (ROA Model)

Source: Author

The above section includes normality tests, multivariate data visualisation and a Q-Q plot graph of the standardised residuals. Mainly the QRATIO model and ROA model has been examined based on the mentioned tests and this is represented in the tables and graphs for a better understanding of the results. It has been concluded that the residuals for both models were asymmetrical. Usually, non-normal distribution occurs due to the presence of outliers in the data. This could be reduced by eliminating a few observations in the data but as the sample was already reduced to make it homogeneous, the research cannot avail of this option (Schumacker & Tomek, 2013). Further, it is assumed that the data for large samples is usually considered normal if the distribution is closer to the normal distribution. Moreover, a reduction in the sample would question the reliability of the results (Oppong & Agbedra, 2016). In this study, the distribution is slightly asymmetrical; therefore, the collected data are considered to be normally distributed. Further, the next section shows the reliability and validity tests performed by the researcher.

4.5 Reliability and Validity Tests

As described in Chapter Three, three types of validity tests were computed. Convergent validity was measured through Spearman's rank correlation that is further mentioned in this chapter. Predictive validity was identified through regression analysis that predicts significant relationships between independent and dependent variables. A final analysis was incorporated to be sure of the internal consistency of this study using Cronbach's Alpha. A suggestion has been made by the previous literature that a score of 70% is considered to be a good indicator of internal consistency (Sürücü & Maslakçı, 2020). The results for Cronbach's Alpha are detailed in the following sub-sections.

4.5.1 Cronbach's Alpha for Corporate Governance Variables

To measure the reliability of corporate governance variables, Cronbach's Alpha was computed in Gretl software that included corporate governance practices used in this study as shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Corporate Governance Practices Statistics

Particulars	Mean	Standard Deviation	Number
Board Size	6.2708	1.7136	96
Board Independence	3.4688	1.4360	96
Audit Committee Size	2.6458	0.8581	96
CEO-Duality	0.0729	0.2614	96
Board Gender Diversity	0.4688	0.6951	96

Source: Author

The results of the tests have been presented in the following Table 4.5 that signifies a test score of 72% which lies within the threshold of 70% or above.

Table 4.5: Corporate Governance Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
0.725	5

Source: Author

4.5.2 Cronbach's Alpha for Financial Performance Measures

To measure the reliability of corporate governance variables, Cronbach's Alpha was computed in Gretl software that included corporate governance practices used in this study as shown in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: Financial Performance Measures Statistics

Particulars	Mean	Standard Deviation	Number
Return on Assets	-0.0981	0.2385	96
Tobin's Q	2.5517	2.4368	96

Source: Author

The results of the tests have been presented in the following Table 4.7Table 4.5 that signifies a test score of 78% which lies within the threshold of 70% or above.

Table 4.7: Financial Performance Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
.783	2

Source: Author

4.6 Descriptive Statistics and Analysis

In the previous section, the researcher has discussed the frequency distribution of all the variables and performed normality tests. Similarly, this section denotes understanding of the characteristics and distributions of the data which further helps to conduct the analysis and elucidate the findings (Lee, 2020). To be more specific, the purpose of this section is to provide an understanding of the distribution of the data and discuss the descriptive statistics. Initially, it is vital to understand the variable itself can be a characteristic, number or classification that is measurable. A variable can be of two types: continuous and categorical. A variable that can take any value between two numbers is continuous whereas if it can take one limited number of variables then it is categorical. Further, it has been divided into two types: nominal and ordinal (Herbst, et al., 2020). Concerning the nominal variable, the order of it does not matter, such as in the case of collecting information about gender. Conversely, in the case of an ordinal variable, the order of the variable does matter. This study has selected a mix of continuous and categorical variables and the selection has been made according to the requirement of the research

questions. And the data type is nominal as in the collected data; the order for this is irrelevant.

Further, to understand the characteristics of the data, this section analysed the descriptive statistics. It refers to the measurement of numerical characteristics of the data sample (Adkins, 2014). In this study, various characteristics of the variables are considered, such as the range of data from the minimum value to the maximum, average value of the data of each variable (mean), the middle value of the data-set (median), the extent of spread of data from the mean value of the data-set (standard deviation), the degree of normal distribution of the data (skewness) (King & Eckersley, 2019). These variables were calculated with the help of Gretl software, so the outcomes from the software have been attached in Appendix C as Descriptive Results and Pearsons Correlation Matrix

and the following table has been prepared in Excel to present the information in a less complicated manner that is also easy to understand. Therefore, descriptive statistics of the collected data for corporate governance variables and financial performance measures of AIM-listed companies for the year 2015 are as follow.

Table 4.8: Summary Statistics, Using the Observations 1-96

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Skewness</i>
<i>Independent</i>						
NED	3.4688	3.0000	1.0000	7.0000	1.4360	0.3417
ACS	2.6458	3.0000	0.0000	6.0000	0.8581	0.0435
BS	6.2708	6.0000	2.0000	11.0000	1.7136	0.1544
CEOD	0.0729	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	0.2614	3.2853
NOOfwmm	0.4688	0.0000	0.0000	3.0000	0.6951	1.3406
<i>Dependent</i>						
TobinsQ	2.5517	1.5450	0.2200	14.6600	2.4368	2.2733
ROA	-0.0981	-0.0283	-1.2020	0.4080	0.2385	-1.4382

Source: Author

The above table represents the summary statistics of the variables. Each variable has the respective mean, median, minimum, and maximum value, standard deviation, and skewness. In this section, the researcher discusses the results by referring to the above table according to which, on average, each board has three non-executives which are half of the mean of BS (Mathew, et al., 2016). As seen in the histogram data visualisation, BI, ACS and BS were normally distributed according to which the mean and median of these

variables should be the same as can also be confirmed from the above table. Further, dispersion refers to how the scores are spread out around the mean. In this case, the highest dispersion came for Tobin's Q (2.4368) and the lowest for ROA (0.2385). Moreover, the skewness of BI, ACS and BS is close to zero, which means there is another clarification that observations of BI, ACS and BS are normally distributed (Darko, *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand, while paying attention to the skewness of the rest of the variables, it became clear that they are not normally distributed.

Further, the ratio of male members in the board to female members in the board is 5.8:0.4 which makes it clear that there is a lack of board gender diversity in the boards of AIM-listed companies. The overall sample of this study is following the separate leadership structure as the researcher found no CEO duality in 93% of sample firms, only 7% of firms listed in AIM had CEO duality with a mean of 0.07 and this variable is highly skewed among all the variables that can also be seen in the graphic representation in the form of a histogram (Ujunwa, 2012). Further, in the case of dependent variables, it has been mentioned earlier that the QRATIO was highly dispersed with an average of 2.55 which specified that according to the market valuation, there are opportunities for SMEs to grow. Meanwhile, ROA is the lowest dispersed variable (0.2385) with a mean of -0.0981 which reveals the negative performance of SMEs in the UK (Shukeri, *et al.*, 2012).

4.7 Inferential Statistics and Analysis

Inferential statistics have been used in this study to test the hypotheses. In addition to the descriptive statistics, inferential statistics assist the researcher to understand the characteristics and relationships of different variables (Hair, *et al.*, 2019). The researcher performs the correlation matrix analysis and multiple regression analysis. Regarding the correlation matrix, this study has adopted Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficients (PMCC) as both the variables (independent and dependent) of the data-set are in numerical form. Moreover, it is helpful to perform correlation analysis before regression analysis as it provides an estimate to the researcher about the relationship between different variables (Elsayed, 2011). Further, regression analysis has been performed in this study to examine the strength of a cause-and-effect relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables, and the regression coefficient is used to analyse the regression analysis. To analyse the cross-sectional data, the basic regression model has been mentioned below which has been derived from the

previous literature (Shan & Xu, 2012) and further expanded to include all the indices covered in this study.

Regression Model:

$$Y_{i(Y)} = \alpha + \beta x_{i(Y)} + \varepsilon_{i(Y)}$$

- Y = Dependent variable
- X = Independent variable
- α and β = Coefficients
- i = Stands for 1 to 96 firms
- Y = Year to investigate
- ε = Error term

Source: (Rawlings, et al., 2001)

The various models are defined as follow:

$$QRATIO = \alpha + \beta BS + \beta BI + \beta BG + \beta ACS + \beta CEOD + \varepsilon$$

Source: Author

$$ROA = \alpha + \beta BS + \beta BI + \beta BG + \beta ACS + \beta CEOD + \varepsilon$$

Source: Author

After performing the regression analysis with the help of the above-said equations, the data-set will be divided into two or more groups to perform the two-way ANOVA analysis and simultaneously interpret the findings.

4.8 Correlation Matrix

A correlation coefficient is an efficient tool to evaluate the strength of the linear relationship between pairs of numerical variables. Usually, the letter (r) denotes the correlation coefficient and measures between -1 and +1. It is assumed that there is an absolute relation between two variables when the value measured is +1. In other words,

the variables are believed to be positively correlated, which means if there is an increase in or rise in one variable then the other will also reflect in the same direction (Rawlings, *et al.*, 2001). Conversely, if 'r' is calculated as -1 then the variables are negatively correlated, and then the variables behave oppositely. If the independent variable increases, the dependent variable will decrease in reaction to that or vice versa. However, if the values lie between -1 and +1, then it is considered a weak correlation between the variables. Further, variables are believed to be completely independent if the correlation coefficient value is zero, which according to Saunders, *et al.* (2009) is highly impossible in business research. Further, the Pearson's correlation matrix is presented in the form of a table which is created with the help of Excel (refer to Table C.12 in Appendix C for the original file of Gretl).

Table 4.9: Correlation Matrix

<i>Correlation Coefficients, using the observations 1 - 96</i>							
<i>5% critical value (two-tailed) = 0.2006 for n = 96</i>							
	<i>NED</i>	<i>ACS</i>	<i>BS</i>	<i>CEOD</i>	<i>BG</i>	<i>QRATIO</i>	<i>ROAYI</i>
<i>NED</i>	1						
<i>ACS</i>	0.512	1					
<i>BS</i>	0.778	0.474	1				
<i>CEOD</i>	0.204	0.071	0.115	1			
<i>BG</i>	0.315	0.069	0.369	0.132	1		
<i>QRATIO</i>	-0.069	0.005	-0.022	-0.182	0.006	1	
<i>ROAYI</i>	-0.141	-0.012	-0.015	-0.040	0.060	-0.415	1

Source: Author

The above table presents the Pearson's correlation matrix for all the variables in the study which reflects the relationship between independent (corporate governance) variables and dependent (financial performance measures) variables for SMEs. while analysing the relationship between variables, it is essential to pay attention to the multi co-linearity problem. Initially, it is vital to recognise if the multi co-linearity error affects the correlation matrix. It is a phenomenon that is believed to exist in the correlation matrix when the two or more variables are highly correlated (more than 0.9) (Shukeri, *et al.*, 2012). The presence of multi co-linearity affects the accuracy of the multiple regression

model as it depicts the bias relationship between the variables. As far as the correlation matrix of this study is concerned, the above table shows that this correlation matrix is free from the error of multi co-linearity as no variable is correlated to another variable at a degree of above 0.9, hence the multiple regression of this study will not be influenced.

The highest correlation found in this matrix is between BS and NED (BI) which is at the degree of 0.778. Hence, this result clarifies that the presence of NEDs is positively and highly correlated with the BS. This implies that most of the sample companies listed in AIM follow the guidelines of QCA as half of the board members must be non-executives. Therefore, if the board size increases, the number of NEDs automatically rises (Higgs, 2003; Fuzi, *et al.*, 2016). The next highest correlated variables are ACS and NED and this is again justified in line with the guidelines of the UK corporate governance code or QCA guidelines that AIM companies follow, namely in the sense that the size of an audit committee is positively and highly correlated with the presence of non-executive directors. Again, it is suggested by the CG guidelines that the audit committee must contain at least two non-executive members (Amar, *et al.*, 2011; Al-Gamrh, *et al.*, 2020; Aluchna, *et al.*, 2020). Concerning each dependent variable, the relationships of all the independent variables are discussed below:

4.8.1 Findings of Correlation with QRATIO

This section initially examines the relationship between QRATIO and all the independent variables based on the correlation coefficient. Initially, NED is negatively (-0.069) correlated with Tobin's Q; however, this result is not significant. This result is inclined with the previous literature (Murtaza, *et al.*, 2020); one of the reasons behind this could be the presence of grey directors (Clifford & Evans, 1997; Cheung, *et al.*, 2013). Similarly, BS (-0.022) and CEOD (-0.182) is also negatively but insignificantly correlated with the QRATIO; this result is aligned with the findings of Arora & Sharma (2016), however, it contradicts the findings of Shukeri, *et al.* (2012). On the other hand, QRATIO is positively correlated with ACS and BGD which means that to some extent, with the increase in the number of audit committee members, QRATIO also improves (Mustafa, *et al.*, 2018). In the same way, as the number of women increases in the board, the QRATIO also rises as ultimately QRATIO shows the market opportunities of the company and by hiring female directors, the reputation of the company improves leading to the growth in the market (Ahmadi, *et al.*, 2018).

4.8.2 Findings of Correlation with ROA

Concerning ROA, NED was found to be negatively (-0.141) correlated which is also identical to QRATIO correlation with ROA. In fact, except for BGD (0.060) every other variable: ACS (-0.012) (Endrawes, *et al.*, 2018); BS (-0,015) (Liang, *et al.*, 2013); and CEOD (-0.040) (Wahba, 2015) is negatively correlated with the ROA, though not significantly. Moreover, almost all the companies listed in AIM had negative returns on assets which indicates that in 2015 most of the sample companies were bearing losses and heading towards the 2016 financial crisis. However, identical to QRATIO, BGD is positively related to the overall financial performance of the companies listed in AIM (Vafaei, *et al.*, 2015). Further, the significance of the correlation matrix is also shown in the above table which has a p-value of 0.2006. In accordance with the 5% significance level of 96 observations, the correlation matrix table does not show a significant correlation between the variables. The further section will discuss the regression analysis.

4.9 Multiple Regression Analysis

In the previous section, the researcher discussed the correlation between the dependent and independent variables which indicates if there is either a positive or negative relationship existing between them. Further in this section, the regression coefficient facilitates us to examine the strength of the relationship between a numerical dependent and one or more numerically independent variables. As explained in the previous chapter, the researcher has selected a multiple linear regression model (OLS) for the evaluation which is an extension of a simple linear regression model. The only difference between these two regression models is that with a multiple linear regression model, researchers can evaluate more than one independent variable against one dependent variable (Adkins, 2014).

4.9.1 Multiple Regression Models 1 & 2 (QRATIO)

Generally, the regression model measures the extent of the variation in a dependent variable in reaction to change in the independent variable that a researcher can explain further statistically. Table 4.10 shows the results of the multiple linear regression model with QRATIO as the dependent variable and corporate governance (NED, BS, ACS, CEOD, BGD) as independent variables.

Table 4.10: Multiple Regression Model 1: (QRATIO)

Model 1: OLS, using observations 1-96
Dependent variable: QRATIO

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value	
const	3.88363	1.37899	2.816	0.0060	***
NED	-0.172959	0.294639	-0.5870	0.5587	
ACS	0.135712	0.348917	0.3890	0.6982	
BS	0.0555036	0.243404	0.2280	0.8201	
CEOD	-1.62976	0.991059	-1.644	0.1036	
BG	0.153146	0.396118	0.3866	0.7000	

Mean dependent var	2.551667	S.D. dependent var	2.436770
Sum squared resid	542.3824	S.E. of regression	2.454887
R-squared	0.038492	Adjusted R-squared	-0.014926
F(5, 90)	0.720584	P-value(F)	0.609668
Log-likelihood	-219.3360	Akaike criterion	450.6720
Schwarz criterion	466.0581	Hannan-Quinn	456.8913

Excluding the constant, p-value was highest for variable 3 (BS)

Source: Author

Although, the least square estimator can be used to evaluate the linear model even when the errors have heteroskedasticity with good results, the issue with this is that the usual estimator of precision is not as consistent as Model 1. The simple way to handle the problem is to use the least square method to determine the constant and slopes and to use an estimator of least square covariance that is consistent with the errors of heteroskedasticity. The least-square covariance known as heteroskedasticity robust estimator of covariance is used by Gretl (Adkins, 2014). Heteroskedasticity is an issue in the results, but it may affect only the standard error of the coefficients and with which it might be able to reduce the efficiency. The reliable solution is to use the OLS in regression analysis; however, it is also vital to report the heteroskedasticity robust standard errors (Elsayed, 2011). Therefore, the heteroskedasticity problem in the regression analysis of this study has been managed by re-running the model while checking the ‘robust standard errors’ option. It can be viewed, by comparing Table 4.10 and Table 4.11, that the coefficient estimates are the same but the change can be seen in the estimated standard errors. In fact, the robust standard error for the slope is smaller than before.

Table 4.11: Multiple Regression Model 2 with Robust Standard Error Checks: (QRATIO)

Model 2: OLS, using observations 1-96
 Dependent variable: QRATIO
 Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors, variant HC1

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value	
const	3.88363	1.81574	2.139	0.0352	**
NED	-0.172959	0.283199	-0.6107	0.5429	
ACS	0.135712	0.288069	0.4711	0.6387	
BS	0.0555036	0.184402	0.3010	0.7641	
CEOD	-1.62976	1.91618	-0.8505	0.3973	
BG	0.153146	0.378294	0.4048	0.6866	
Mean dependent var	2.551667	S.D. dependent var	2.436770		
Sum squared resid	542.3824	S.E. of regression	2.454887		
R-squared	0.038492	Adjusted R-squared	-0.014926		
F(5, 90)	0.465809	P-value (F)	0.800756		
Log-likelihood	-219.3360	Akaike criterion	450.6720		
Schwarz criterion	466.0581	Hannan-Quinn	456.8913		

Excluding the constant, p-value was highest for variable 3 (BS)

Source: Author

The above table depicts the ordinary least regression results and the robust standard error has been checked for the QRATIO as a dependent variable and all the CG variables as the independent variable. According to the results obtained from Model 2, it was apparent that the presence of NEDs is negatively (-0.172959) correlated with the QRATIO; however, the result is not significant as the p-value (0.5429) is greater than 5%. Therefore, relatively fewer non-executive members in the boards tend to improve the QRATIO of listed SMEs in the UK. This result is identical to the findings of [Afrifa & Tauringana \(2015c\)](#) who also chose the sample of AIM-listed companies and found the same results that NED is negatively but not significantly related to the market-based measure of financial performance. Further, as per Model 2 of regression analysis, ACS (0.135712) is positively related to the performance of QRATIO; however, it is not significantly (0.6387) positively related. This suggests that the rise in the number of AC members will also positively influence the financial performance measures of listed SMEs, but not at the significant level of 5% as even according to the previous literature, ACS has no significant influence on the financial performance of SMEs ([Gebayel, et al., 2018](#); [Al-Najjar, 2011](#); [Chan & Li, 2008](#)).

In addition to audit committee size Table 4.11 also proved a positive (0.0555036) but insignificant (0.7641) relationship between BS and the financial performance of the company. It implies that with an increase in the number on the board of directors, the financial performance of AIM-listed SMEs will also improve. Based on resource dependency theory, many authors proved that the large board size, up to an extent, can influence the financial performance of the companies in a positive manner as BOD are an essential and critical resource for the companies (Merendino & Melville, 2019; Murtaza, *et al.*, 2020; Sehrawat, *et al.*, 2020; Kyere & Ausloos, 2020; Karim & Faiz, 2017; Zhou, *et al.*, 2018). At the same time, these findings contradict the results of Azeez (2015) as in support of agency theory, it is a financial restriction for the SMEs to retain a large board size.

Further, detecting the relationship between CEOD and QRATIO, it became apparent that CEOD negatively (-1.63) but insignificantly (0.3973) affects the QRATIO. This result is in support of agency theory such that if CEO duality exists in the company, it will have a negative effect on financial performance (Wahba, 2015; Rashid, 2010; Kholeif, 2008). Therefore, based on this result, SMEs should follow a separate leadership structure; this is also in accordance with agency theory. As far as the presence of women on the board is concerned, this study found an insignificant positive coefficient (0.153146) between BGD and QRATIO. Hence, if the number of women increases on the board, it also positively influences the financial performance of SMEs (Mazzotta & Ferraro, 2020; Li & Chen, 2018).

4.9.2 Multiple Regression Models 3 & 4 (ROA)

In this section, the relationship between CG variables and ROA has been analysed with the help of multiple regression analysis which means all the independent variables (BS, BI, ACS, CEOD and BGD) have been examined against the dependent variable (ROA). The following table shows the results of the regression analysis:

Table 4.12: Multiple Regression Model 3: (ROA)

Model 3: OLS, using observations 1-96
 Dependent variable: ROA

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	-0.124777	0.133953	-0.9315	0.3541
NED	-0.0597258	0.0286207	-2.087	0.0397 **
ACS	0.0203737	0.0338933	0.6011	0.5493
BS	0.0271385	0.0236439	1.148	0.2541
CEOD	-0.00628709	0.0962698	-0.06531	0.9481
BG	0.0331897	0.0384783	0.8626	0.3907
Mean dependent var	-0.098136	S.D. dependent var	0.238515	
Sum squared resid	5.117845	S.E. of regression	0.238464	
R-squared	0.053038	Adjusted R-squared	0.000429	
F(5, 90)	1.008156	P-value(F)	0.417649	
Log-likelihood	4.499409	Akaike criterion	3.001182	
Schwarz criterion	18.38727	Hannan-Quinn	9.220490	

Excluding the constant, p-value was highest for variable 4 (CEOD)

Source: Author

However, the initial model of multiple regression is not free from the effect of heteroskedasticity error. The results below are able to find the constant and the coefficient slopes but may not be efficient in terms of standard errors. Therefore, the multiple regression model was run again with a check for robust standard errors as the standard error slopes had been reduced, which can be seen while comparing the results, as the standard error slopes have been reduced in Table 4.13 compared to Table 4.12.

Table 4.13: Multiple Regression Model 3 with Robust Standard Error Checks: (ROA)

Model 4: OLS, using observations 1-96
 Dependent variable: ROA
 Heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors, variant HC1

	coefficient	std. error	t-ratio	p-value
const	-0.124777	0.111923	-1.115	0.2679
NED	-0.0597258	0.0290552	-2.056	0.0427 **
ACS	0.0203737	0.0217573	0.9364	0.3516
BS	0.0271385	0.0192250	1.412	0.1615
CEOD	-0.00628709	0.0820146	-0.07666	0.9391
BG	0.0331897	0.0267906	1.239	0.2186
Mean dependent var	-0.098136	S.D. dependent var	0.238515	
Sum squared resid	5.117845	S.E. of regression	0.238464	
R-squared	0.053038	Adjusted R-squared	0.000429	
F(5, 90)	1.457542	P-value(F)	0.211655	
Log-likelihood	4.499409	Akaike criterion	3.001182	
Schwarz criterion	18.38727	Hannan-Quinn	9.220490	

Excluding the constant, p-value was highest for variable 4 (CEOD)

Source: Author

According to the table mentioned above, overall, more than half of the variables are positively related to the ROA; however, the results are insignificant. On the other hand, the presence of the non-executive board of directors is significantly (0.0427) and negatively (-0.0597258) related to the performance of ROA (Karim & Faiz, 2017; Murtaza, *et al.*, 2020). This finding contradicts agency theory but supports stewardship theory according to which in comparison to executive directors, NEDs are less aware of the valuable and available resources, due to which, the decisions of NEDs will not effectively enhance the financial performance of companies (Kyere & Ausloos, 2020; Liu, *et al.*, 2015). Further, CEOD is also negatively (-0.00628709) associated with ROA as 90% of the sample companies follow a separate leadership structure; still, there is no significant (0.9391) association between CEOD and ROA (Kaur & Singh, 2019; Gupta & Mahakud, 2020). Furthermore, the remaining variables are positively related to the FP of the companies: ACS (0.02037) is insignificantly (0.3516) related to the ROA as the p-value is less than 0.05. However, it might be possible to some extent and further, in the ANOVA analysis, it will be more transparent which size group is positively related (Aldamen, *et al.*, 2012; Al-Rassas & Kamardin, 2015; Al-Matari, *et al.*, 2014; Alqatamin, 2018). Similarly, BGD (0.03319) and BS (.02714) both insignificantly (0.2186) (0.1615),

respectively, but positively influence the ROA of the firm which is in line with the results of the previous literature and supports resource dependency theory (Kyere & Ausloos, 2020; Karim & Faiz, 2017; Zhou, *et al.*, 2018).

In this section, the researcher investigated the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables with the multiple regression tool of analysis. In accordance with previous research, this study also found mixed results. However, there is another analysis to make which is the ANOVA analysis covered in the next section. In addition to that, it covers the ultimate decision with the acceptance/rejection of the hypotheses.

4.10 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA Analysis)

After regression analysis, this study proceeds towards the ANOVA analysis. To perform this analysis, the numerical variables of the data-set have been divided into two or more groups by using descriptive statistics. The data have been compared on the basis of mean and F-statistics representing a good fit between the groups. Additionally, significance has been presented with a p-value of less than 5%. The researcher has paid attention to fulfilling the two assumptions that need to meet, to conduct this analysis: the data values should be independent and the data in each group should be normally distributed; however, slightly asymmetrical data can be used if the sample is large enough i.e. > 30 (Saunders, *et al.*, 2019).

4.10.1 ANOVA Analysis of Board Size

The following Table 4.14 represents the impact of BS on both the dependent variables. The evaluation or analysis is performed by comparing the mean values of both QRATIO and ROA against the specific group of BS. The data-set of total board members has been divided into three groups: less than six members in the board; between six and nine and more than nine members in the board. According to the table, the averages of QRATIO in all the groups were higher than the average of ROA. The BS had a significantly (at 1%) positive influence on QRATIO (2.20; 2.80) until the BS was less than nine, as the QRATIO falls to 0.78 directly when the ANOVA analysis is performed on the group with more than nine members. Therefore, it is essential for companies to maintain an adequate size for the board as this analysis proves that overly large boards do have a negative impact on the financial performance of companies. However, this is not specifically the case about ROA as though slight insignificant improvement can be seen in the mean

values. Please refer to Appendix D from Table D.13 to Table D.18 for Gretl files of ANOVA analysis of BS.

Table 4.14: Impact of BS on QRATIO and ROA

<i>Board Size</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Tobin's Q (Mean)</i>	<i>ROA (Mean)</i>
Less than 6	30	2.20333	-0.109067
F-statistics (p-value)		0.126303 (0.9437)	0.868101 (.4701)
Between 6 to 9	63	2.80175	-0.094283
F-statistics (p-value)		0.750404 (0.5265)	0.673451 (0.5717)
More than 9	3	0.783333	-0.0697249
F-statistics (p-value)		56.3333 (0.0843)	1.45956 (0.4402)

Source: Author

Discussion:

H₁: An unduly large size for the board may outweigh the benefits and be negatively associated with the firm performance of listed SMEs in the UK.

According to H₁, an extra-large board size in companies outweighs the advantages of the board and may leave a negative impact on the financial performance of the companies. To test the hypothesis, the researcher performed a correlation matrix, regression analysis and ANOVA analysis. As per the correlation, there is a negative correlation between BS and both the dependent variables (QRATIO & ROA). Further, it has been proven by ANOVA analysis that after a certain limit, if the size of the board continues to increase, it will begin to impact the FP of SMEs negatively (Kiambati, *et al.*, 2013; Murtaza, *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, as per the findings, by using different tools of analysis, the researcher accepts the hypothesis and believes that large boards might be an option for large companies but in the case of small and medium size enterprises, there has to be a limited number of boards of directors (Liang, *et al.*, 2013; Aslam & Haron, 2020; Orozco, *et al.*, 2018; Khan, *et al.*, 2019; Amar, *et al.*, 2011; Eisenberg, *et al.*, 1998).

4.10.2 ANOVA Analysis of Board Independence

The data for BI has been divided into two groups: one with NED less than or equal to three and another with NED more than three. The mean value of QRATIO decreases as the number of NEDs increases to more than three on the board. It means the presence of

NEDs is negatively related to the QRATIO of the companies. Similarly, ROA's mean values also decreased when the NEDs totalled more than three on the board. Moreover, according to the correlation and regression analysis as well, NEDs were significantly negatively correlated with the FP. Please refer to Appendix D from Table D.19 to Table D.22 for Gretl files of ANOVA analysis of BI.

Table 4.15: Impact of BI on QRATIO and ROA

<i>Non-Executive Director</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Tobin's Q (Mean)</i>	<i>ROA (Mean)</i>
Non-Executive Director <= 3	51	2.69608	-0.0752869
F-statistics (p-value)		1.0112 (0.3714)	0.162421 (0.8505)
Non-Executive Director > 3	45	2.388	-0.124031
F-statistics (p-value)		0.580154 (0.6314)	1.7103 (0.1799)

Source: Author

Discussion:

H₂: The proportion of non-executive directors on the board will be an extra expense for the SMEs and due to limited resources, a high number of non-executives will negatively affect the financial performance of the UK-listed AIM companies.

Based on stewardship theory, H₂ suggested that there should be a minimum number of NEDs on the board who can maintain the independence of the board. The findings of this research agreed with stewardship theory as SMEs usually have limited resources and therefore, hiring an extra number of NEDs on the board will affect their financial performance negatively (Kyere & Ausloos, 2020; Liu, *et al.*, 2015). However, the findings contradict agency theory which believes that the presence of NEDs will provide a check on the activities of the executives (Murtaza, *et al.*, 2020). According to the analysis conducted by the researcher, the presence of NEDs on the board is negatively related to the financial performance of the companies. Inclusive of this, the results are highly significant in relation to NEDs and ROA. Therefore, this hypothesis is accepted.

4.10.3 ANOVA Analysis of Audit Committee Size

This section covers the two-way analysis of the ACS on the FP measures (QRATIO and ROA) of the SMEs listed in AIM. Overall, the sample of companies contains 96 companies and for the ANOVA analysis, these companies have been divided into two

groups: ACS less than or equal to three and ACS more than three. The first group contain 86 companies and the second group contain 10 companies. Further, the findings show no relationship between ACS and FP of the SMEs. The following table represents the average mean of the QRATIO and ROA concerning the groups of ACS. It has been evidenced that up until ACS remains to 3 the financial performance was positively related to the ACS. Once ACS grows to more than three, the FP starts getting affected. However, the results are not significant as the p-values are less than 5%. Please refer to Appendix D from Table D.23 to Table D.26 for Gretl files of ANOVA analysis of ACS.

Table 4.16: Impact of ACS on QRATIO and ROA

Audit Committee Size	Frequency	Tobin's Q (Mean)	ROA (Mean)
ACS <=3	86	2.5986	-0.0937013
F-statistics (p-value)		0.260078 (0.8539)	0.309977 (0.8181)
ACS >3	10	2.148	-0.13627
F-statistics (p-value)		1.54723 (0.2488)	0.640231 (0.4467)

Source: Author

Discussion:

H₃: A large size of audit committee negatively influences the financial performance of the SMEs listed on the FTSE-AIM.

This study develops the hypothesis concerning audit committee size as a large size of audit committee affects the financial performance of SMEs negatively. However, this study rejects this hypothesis as after using all the tools of statistical analysis, the researcher noticed that there is no specific relationship between ACS and the FP of SMEs (Gebayel, *et al.*, 2018; Al-Najjar, 2011; Chan & Li, 2008). To have at least two to three members in the audit committee is a basic requirement of the UK Corporate Governance Code which is following by almost whole sample companies (Mallin, 2019). A slight decrease has been found in the ANOVA analysis when the ACS grow to more than three. However, no evidence was recorded for a negative relationship between ACS and both the FP variables (QRATIO and ROA). Therefore, this hypothesis has been rejected.

4.10.4 ANOVA Analysis of Board Gender Diversity

The following Table 4.17 shows the ANOVA analysis of BGD and FP (both variables) of the listed SMEs. According to the sample of the study, few companies only hire women in their boards and maybe this is because the authorities of the CG regulations promote the involvement of women in every field. According to the sample, only ¼ of the companies have women on their board, so ¾ of the sample companies have no women on their board. Further, to conduct the ANOVA analysis, the sample companies have been divided into two groups; the first group defines the number of women less than two and the other group defines the number of women equal to or more than two. The results of the analysis show that BGD is positively related to the QRATIO and ROA. In addition to this, the positive relationship of BGD is highly significant with QRATIO as the p-value is 0.0001 and the F-statistics is 58.1865 which is a good fit between BGD and QRATIO. However, BGD has no significant impact on the ROA. Please refer to Appendix D from Table D.27 to Table D.30 for Gretl files of the ANOVA analysis of BGD.

Table 4.17: Impact of BGD on QRATIO and ROA

<i>Number of Women in Board</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Tobin's Q (Mean)</i>	<i>ROA (Mean)</i>
No. of women < 2	87	2.19425	-0.103587
F-statistics (p-value)		0.446992 (0.5056)	0.001154 (0.9730)
No. of women >= 2	9	1.89667	-0.0454387
F-statistics (p-value)		58.1865 (0.0001)	0.119217 (0.7400)

Source: Author

Discussion:

H₅: The presence of female directors on the board will positively influence the financial performance of the SMEs listed in the FTSE-AIM.

This study accepts the above-mentioned hypothesis as the evidence reveals that the BGD is positively related to the variables of financial performance of the sample companies. The relationship has been tested with three main tools (correlation, regression and ANOVA analysis) and all the tests prove that there is a positive correlation between BGD and QRATIO. However, the results obtained from the correlation matrix and multiple regression model were not significant. In the case of ANOVA analysis, both groups were positively related to the QRATIO and there is not much difference in the mean value

which is approximately two for both groups. However, the difference occurs when the increase in the number of women shows a positive and highly significant (p-value 0.0001) relation between BGD and QRATIO (Mazzotta & Ferraro, 2020; Li & Chen, 2018). Based on this, the researcher accepts the hypothesis. This result is in support of resource dependency theory which believes that the rise in the number of women on the board will bring more resources in terms of experience, legitimacy, skills, abilities, and knowledge that will ultimately enhance the performance of the companies (Ullah, *et al.*, 2019; Ullah, *et al.*, 2020).

In addition to the above analysis and explained hypotheses, there is one more hypothesis whose acceptance/rejection is yet to be decided, and that hypothesis is:

H₄: The existence of CEO duality will negatively influence the financial performance of listed small and medium size enterprises in the UK.

The ANOVA analysis of this variable has not been performed as it is a dummy variable, the data for which has been collected based on yes/no with a value 1/0. In this scenario, this variable cannot be divided into two or more groups. However, the hypothesis has been accepted as there is a negative relationship found between the CEO duality and FP of the SMEs listed in AIM, though the results were not significant. The hypothesis has been accepted based on the findings in the correlation matrix and regression analysis where a negative association has been seen but is not significant even at the 1% level. Therefore, it has been considered that there is a negative impact of CEOD on the financial performance of the registered SMEs (Wahba, 2015; Rashid, 2010; Kholeif, 2008).

4.11 Conclusion

This chapter thoroughly discussed the findings and analysis of this study. Following the choices made in the previous chapter, the researcher collected the data as per the selected methods of collection and then analysed and discussed the data in this chapter. This chapter began with an introduction that explains what the researcher is going to achieve in this chapter. Further, it discussed the description of all the variables to understand the characteristics of the selected variables and ultimately explained how each variable has been calculated. Furthermore, the frequency distribution of the variables is defined and has been explained with the help of univariate and multivariate data visualisation. Majorly, all the data was normally distributed; however, the slight asymmetrical

distribution can be ignored as the sample of the data is large enough (required > 30 phenomena) (Saunders, *et al.*, 2009). The next section, evaluates the normality tests of residuals with the help of the Jarque-Bera test, Shapiro-Wilk test and Chi-Square test. All these tests were performed under the model based on two dependent variables (QRATIO and ROA) which were further presented with the histograms and Q-Q Plot graph. Additionally, this chapter performed validity and reliability tests to ensure the internal consistency of the quantitative research data.

After that, a section was provided to discuss the descriptive statistics and analysis in which central tendency (mean, median, range, standard deviation and skewness) was discussed in detail which shows the attributes of the collected data and how they are related to each other. Further, the analysis leads to the inferential statistics and analysis that involves the basic regression model that further involves Pearson's correlation matrix that shows the correlation that exists between the independent and dependent variables. In addition to this, a multiple regression model has been performed to recognise the extent of the variation which depicts a negative association between NED and ROA; the result is significant at a 5% level. Last but not the least, ANOVA analysis has been performed to analyse the variance of the data. Further, the data-set has been divided into two or three groups to analyse the data, according to which the researcher decided to accept or reject the hypotheses. In the next chapter, the researcher will conclude the study while answering the research questions, stating the recommendations and the limitations.

CHAPTER 5: Conclusion, Recommendation and Limitations

5.1 Introduction

There is a dearth of academic studies or research on the implicit impact of good corporate governance practices on the financial performance of small and medium enterprises listed on an exchange, such as FTSE-AIM companies listed on the London Stock Exchange. This study is contributing to fill this gap in our knowledge. Until 2018, the companies listed in AIM were not required to follow the UK CG code (2012), although most of the companies were practising minimum guidelines recommended by the QCA. In order to bring transparency within the structure of the AIM companies, QCA guidelines were highly contributed. However, to make it flexible for the SMEs, the QCA also applied the ‘comply-or-explain’ concept. AIM is a market where a mix of companies is available as some entered as SMEs and now do not fit the definition of SMEs; these companies follow the UK CG code (2012) and those who are still SMEs can barely adhere to guidelines of QCA. But in 2018, there was an amendment in the rules of AIM companies as now each company must follow one code, either the UK corporate governance code (2018) or the QCA corporate governance code (2018). Small companies are still trying to adjust to the new rules. Currently, the respective study is essential for SMEs to have a clear picture of how their financial performance reacts to changes in their corporate governance structure. The whole thesis has been conducted for this purpose only. After completing each chapter, in this chapter, the researcher concludes the whole study.

5.2 Discussion about the Aim and Objectives Achieved

The aim of this study is: *To investigate the association between internal corporate governance mechanisms and financial performance of the UK-listed AIM companies and provide recommendations to enhance the financial performance of the SMEs.* Four objectives and research questions were formulated to achieve the target. This section discussed the extent to which each objective and research question has been achieved. Broadly, the first two objectives were achieved by following explanatory research. The third objective was set to identify if there is any relationship between CG practices and the financial performance of the listed SMEs which has been achieved with the use of many statistical tools. To accomplish the last objective, the researcher provided

recommendations to SMEs and policymakers which are discussed in detail further in this section.

O1: To examine the emergence of the concept of corporate governance and the development of the corporate governance structure in various developed and developing countries by reviewing the existing literature.

As demonstrated in Chapter Two, to understand the significance and development of corporate governance, various corporate collapses were investigated and different measures taken by multiple countries to develop their CG structure were also examined. Initially, to examine the emergence of CG, major business collapses were discussed which happened in different countries from 1995 to 2018 and left an unforgettable impact on the world. Out of all the reasons behind the financial collapses, one common reason that was discovered in all the discussed collapses was weak internal corporate governance structure. After determining the reason for various business collapses, many countries started paying attention to their respective corporate governance structures. The UK published the Cadbury Code in 1992 and the USA introduced the Sarbanes-Oxley Act in 2002 (Ahmed & Hamdan, 2015). These codes were ideal examples for other developed or developing countries to enhance their CG structure as per their requirements, culture and customs. Undoubtedly, different measures have been taken to develop the CG structure all over the world as shown in Chapter Two. Despite all the efforts, the most recent collapse of a company (Carillion) recorded in this thesis happened in a developed country (the UK) in 2018 (Burgees, 2018). This clearly shows that the measures taken so far to improve corporate governance are not sufficient and collapses are still happening. Therefore, effective measures are required specifically for listed companies to make sure that the investors' interests are safe. Overall, Chapter Two will serve as a guide to beginners in the context of corporate governance where a complete discussion has been provided about the reason behind the emergence of corporate governance and after that, what measures have been taken by different countries to develop it further.

O2: To elaborate on the theoretical underpinnings of corporate governance by studying the various developments made in the previous literature that leads to the development of a conceptual framework for this study.

The second objective of this study was to analyse the theoretical underpinnings of the CG for which agency theory, stakeholder theory, stewardship theory and resource-

dependency theory were explored. Each theory was equally important and offered different perspectives about the principles of the CG codes. As agency theory is considered the ideal theory of CG, however, it is narrow in concept, only paying attention to the shareholder (Arcot, et al., 2010). Meanwhile, stakeholder theory incorporates all aspects, stating that shareholders and other stakeholders are equally important. On the other hand, stewardship theory believes that there is no need for the board of directors as the interests of managers and shareholders are aligned with each other which helps to understand the significance of the presence of non-executives on the board. In the multiple theoretical frameworks of this study, the last theory which was involved is resource dependency theory which considers the BOD as a resource for the company. The conceptual framework of this study was developed with the help of a chosen theoretical framework. To understand the association between corporate governance practices and the financial performance of SMEs, the main CG variables selected are related to the board of directors because the first objective revealed that at the time of collapses, boards were criticised the most and they are directly related to the CG structure of companies. The accounting measures and market measures were both selected to measure the financial performance of SMEs because nowadays, investors pay attention to both historical performance and future market value of the companies (Adedeji, et al., 2020). Based on the conceptual framework, the researcher developed the hypotheses to achieve the third objective.

O3: To inspect the association between internal corporate governance mechanisms and the financial performance of listed SMEs in the UK by testing the hypotheses.

With regard to the third objective of this study, the developed hypotheses have been tested for which an appropriate research methodology has been selected to achieve the aim of this study. The positivist paradigm has been selected for this research with a further selection of the deductive approach. The sample of 96 listed SMEs in the UK was selected and accordingly, the data were gathered from different sources on their board size, number of non-executives in the board, number of women on the board, the separation of the CEO and chairman role and the size of the audit committee. In addition to these variables, some financial variables have also been gathered from the FAME database, annual reports of the sample companies and the LSE website. The statistical analyses showed the mixed results as a significant relationship was found between board gender diversity & board independence and the financial performance of the SMEs. However,

the rest of the variables did not show a significant impact on the FP of SMEs. Hence, the measures of the CG do impact the financial performance of SMEs. Therefore, developing the CG code for SMEs will guide them on how to practice an effective and efficient CG structure while enhancing their FP. The recommendations in respect to SMEs and policymakers have been elaborated in this chapter. However, broadly, the recommendations for the SMEs and policymakers are also explained in this section which represents the fourth objective that has also been achieved.

O4: To provide recommendations on how SMEs listed in the FTSE-AIM can practice the CG guidelines to enhance their financial performance.

According to the results obtained from the statistical analysis, the presence of women is significantly positively related to the financial performance of the listed SMEs in the UK. This result is supported by resource dependency theory with a belief that gender diversity is a source of several skills and experience (Aggarwal, et al., 2019; Darko, et al., 2016). Therefore, the recommendation for SMEs is to raise the number of women on the board to a limited extent. In relation to the presence of NEDs on the board, the results revealed that after a certain limit, NEDs were negatively associated with the financial performance of the listed SMEs. Therefore, SMEs should consider having a limited number of NEDs on the board. In this respect, the QCA CG Code seems preferable for SMEs where a minimum of two NEDs are required on the board and this is supported by stewardship theory (Ayuso & Argandona, 2009; Black & Khanna, 2007). According to the statistical analysis, a nominal relationship was found between the other CG variables (board size, CEO duality and the audit committee size) and the financial performance of the SMEs. Although no significant impact was found, it was discovered that the CG variables do have some relationship with the financial measures of the SMEs (Abor & Biekpe, 2007; Adedeji, et al., 2020; Al-Rassas & Kamardin, 2015). Therefore, it is advisable to SMEs that these companies should follow the minimum required guidelines provided by the QCA.

Research Questions Answered

Theoretical Questions:

RQ₁: How has corporate governance emerged and what measures have been taken to develop the corporate governance structure by countries around the world?

To answer the research question, initially, this study explored the concept of corporate governance by discussing the emergence and the definition of CG. On the basis of previous literature, the researcher came to know that corporate governance is not a new concept as it has existed in the system since the 1980s. However, it became highlighted after major business collapses; consequently, investors showed an interest in improving the CG structure of the firm (Jovanović & Grujić, 2016). After analysing the corporate scams, the researcher understood that basically, for every collapse, the boards of directors were mostly criticised (Mallin, 2019). Based on this, the researcher selected the parameters for the board of directors among the QCA CG code and the UK CG code to investigate the relationship between CG and the FP of SMEs. Further, the researcher explored the overall development of CG structures in various developed and developing countries. These explorations revealed that the main contribution in CG development was made by the USA and the UK with their Sarbanes-Oxley Act (2002) and the Cadbury Code (1991) respectively, as nearly all other countries, refer to the development of codes in these two countries to develop their own CG code (Oliveira, et al., 2014). However, as financial collapses happened in almost all countries, the measures were also taken by all nations, though at their own speed. But the matter is of concern and worth researching because scams continue to happen which reveals that loopholes are still in the system. Therefore, the first research question has been answered by exploring the emergence of CG and measures taken so far by all the nations to develop CG.

RQ₂: What are the theoretical underpinnings of corporate governance that lead to the development of the conceptual framework for this study?

After referring to the previous literature, the main theory that almost all the researchers applied to the concept of CG is ‘Agency Theory’ (Christopher, 2010). However, this theory has been criticised because of its narrow approach which is limited to the shareholder context. Therefore, multiple theoretical approaches were selected to conduct the research or to answer the research questions. The reason for this is the nature of the selected sample companies that are SMEs, as there are fewer chances for agency problems to occur in SMEs unlike in large companies. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the other valuable theoretical underpinnings such as stakeholder theory (wider concept), stewardship theory (believes that the interest of principal and agents are aligned) and resource dependency theory (considers the board of directors to be a resource for the

company). Moreover, according to the empirical results, the mixed results support all these theories. Therefore, with the sample of SMEs, it is important to explore the concept of corporate governance with the help of more than one theory. As per the understanding of theories, the conceptual framework of the CG has been developed, in which the independent variables were the parameters of BOD (in accordance with the assumptions of multiple theories) and the dependent variables were measures of FP. Hence, the second objective has been achieved and the second research question has been answered.

Empirical Questions:

RQ3: Is there any relationship between internal corporate governance mechanisms and the financial performance of the listed SMEs in the UK?

To investigate the relationship between internal corporate governance mechanisms and the financial performance of listed SMEs, the researcher developed the hypotheses to test in Chapter Two based on the theoretical underpinnings and conceptual framework. In addition to that, the guidelines provided by the UK corporate governance code and the QCA corporate governance code (under the dimension of the BOD) also directed the researcher to choose the independent and dependent variables. Overall, this thesis found mixed results which shows that there is a negative association between board size and the FP measures that are in support of agency theory as large board sizes may outweigh the benefits of BOD; therefore, in the case of SMEs, it is suggested not to have a large board size (Aslam & Haron, 2020; Orozco, *et al.*, 2018; Khan, *et al.*, 2019). Initially, it will reduce the cost of SMEs, and may lead to better and prompt decision making, and better understanding about an adequate size for the board.

According to the results, irrespective of the agency theory assumptions, this study found that the presence of NEDs in the board is negatively related to both the measures of financial performance. Moreover, the result was highly significant in relation to the ROA. This result may contradict agency theory but on the other hand, it is in the support of stewardship theory which believes that the extra proportion of NEDs in the board will be an extra expense for SMEs (Kyere & Ausloos, 2020; Liu, *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, in SMEs, mostly owners sit on the senior management team which does not lead to an agency problem and therefore, stewardship theory is acceptable as it believes that there is no variance between owners and agents.

This study found no significant relationship between ACS and both FP measures (QRATIO and ROA). This result supports many previous studies (Gebreyel, *et al.*, 2018; Al-Najjar, 2011; Chan & Li, 2008). However, the ACS was positively related to the FP measures, until the ACS was limited to three members as in the ANOVA analysis, it was apparent that as soon as the size of AC increases (more than three) the performance of the company reacts negatively.

This study found no association between CEO-duality and FP measures. First of all, most of the companies adhere to this guideline of the QCA, according to which most of the companies follow separate leadership structures. Still, if CEO-duality exists in a company, it has a negative impact but is not significant, in comparison to an SME following CEO non-duality (Wahba, 2015; Rashid, 2010; Kholeif, 2008).

Finally, this research found a positive and significant impact of BGD on the financial performance of SMEs. The results were highly significant (0.0001) concerning QRATIO and positive with ROA but no significance was found. However, gender diversity will bring a different range of skills, experience and may lead to issues being handled in a different manner which may impact positively on the performance of SMEs (Ullah, *et al.*, 2019; Ullah, *et al.*, 2020).

Therefore, this study found mixed associations between corporate governance variables and financial performance measures.

RQ4: How can CG practice be improved while enhancing the financial performance of the UK-listed AIM companies?

Financial limitations or scarcity of resources are the main problems of SMEs and due to these issues, they have to be specific with the investment of their money. Many small companies feel burdened by specific corporate governance rules. Therefore, they have the freedom to choose either to practice the CG guidelines or to choose the ‘comply-or-explain’ approach where, if they cannot follow a guideline, they must explain ‘why’ in their annual report. However, the rules changed in 2018 and now SMEs listed in AIM must follow a code; hence, the QCA published a CG code specifically according to the requirements of SMEs. Based on the results, the following measures have been suggested to the SMEs to enhance their financial performance.

It is advisable to increase the number of women on the board as the statistical results show a positive significant impact on the FP of the SMEs.

However, a significant negative impact on the FP of the SMEs observed if the number of non-executives on the board increases more than half of the board size. Hence it will be beneficial to have the minimum number of NEDs on the board.

The board size, CEO duality and the size of the audit committee did not show any significant impact on the FP of the SMEs. Therefore, it will be good for SMEs to preserve their resources and perform the minimum required application of the respective variables.

Further, this chapter provides the essential recommendations for SMEs and authorities of the CG codes to improve the CG structure of the SMEs while enhancing their financial performance.

5.3 Recommendations for SMEs and Policymakers

Below are some major recommendations that have been provided to SMEs and the authorities who are working to improve the CG structure of SMEs. These recommendations provide them with a clear picture of how the application of a few of the principles of the QCA CG code impacts the financial performance of the FTSE-listed SMEs. In addition to that, SMEs will be able to understand the QCA CG code, the UK CG code and the NAPF guidelines, which is more beneficial for them to follow.

- It is only necessary to maintain an adequate size of the board as large boards are negatively associated with the financial performance of the board. Therefore, the QCA CG code is more suitable for listed SMEs in comparison to the UK CG code because, unlike the main UK CG code, the QCA CG code states the board should be of appropriate size as per the convenience of the SMEs. Moreover, authorities should pay attention to this principle and must investigate and apply a minimum range of board size separately to micro, small and medium companies.
- SMEs should have NEDs on the board, but it is not essential for half of the board to be independent. As per ANOVA analysis, if there are more than three NEDs on the board, the researcher has noticed a significant negative impact on the financial performance of the SMEs. Therefore, in this regard as well, the QCA CG code is

more suitable for SMEs in comparison to the UK CG Code as, according to the QCA guidelines, a minimum of two NEDs are required on the board.

- As per the QCA CG code, an audit committee must help the board in the decision-making process by providing accurate and significant information on time. No specification has been made for the ACS in the QCA CG code and in this respect, the author found no significant impact of ACS on the FP of the SMEs. Therefore, the suggestion is that SMEs should maintain a minimum size of audit committee and pay more attention to the expertise, knowledge and experience of the audit committee members.
- A separate leadership structure has always been recommended and most of the companies listed in AIM are following this guideline but for those who are not following it, the results indicate that separate roles for the chairman and CEO are beneficial for the FP of SMEs. This guideline is provided by both codes.
- Another suggestion for SMEs to enhance the market-based measures of FP is to increase the presence of women on the board. Initially, recommendations by both codes are that the board needs to be diversified in terms of skills, education, and gender. In addition to this, this study found a significant positive impact of BGD on the financial performance of the board.

The Practicality of Recommendations for Action in a Possible Post-Covid Era

This is the time where everyone is managing their lives with the post-covid effect on their businesses, jobs, career and opportunities. As covid has a major impact on our lives and decisions, it is also essential to assess the practicality of the recommendation provided by this study for actions in this post-covid era. These recommendations are for BOD, where essentially, directors are not required to come into contact to make decisions. All the senior management tasks and decisions are nowadays taken through online conferencing. Therefore, in the case of enhancing board gender diversity or maintaining the required minimum number of NEDs, that can easily be done by either maintaining social distancing or through online measures. Like all other decisions, these recommendations can also be applicable with thorough discussion between top management and the BOD through several different online measures. Further, this chapter will discuss the research contributions, recommendations for future research and some limitations of this research.

5.4 Research Contributions

The originality of work is one of the important requirements of the doctoral thesis. This thesis is mainly contributing in the following manner:

Theoretical Contribution

- Besides a large amount of research, there is no consensus result achieved on the potential impact of corporate governance guidelines on the financial performance of SMEs. Therefore, this study contributes to the body of knowledge by adding information on the concept of the association between corporate governance guidelines and financial performance of SMEs listed in the Alternative Investment Market.
- Further, the corporate governance or the influence of CG guidelines on the FP of the companies is a well-researched topic in the context of FTSE main companies in LSE, though there is ample research available on the relationship between CG guidelines and the FP of companies. However, rarely has any author used AIM-listed companies as a sample of study (Afrifa & Tauringana, 2015c). It is an emerging market and a reliable platform for SMEs to get listed and reach public investors. It has become a difficult task to retain investors without practising an effective and efficient corporate governance code. Hence this study, provides a clear picture to SMEs about which CG code is more beneficial for them. Hence, those SMEs confused between the UK CG code or the QCA CG code have a clear picture now related to the parameters of the demography of the board.
- Before 2018, AIM-listed companies could voluntarily opt for the practices of the UK CG code or choose the ‘comply-or-explain’ approach to justify the reason for not following guidelines or a set of guidelines. However, the LSE has made amendments to the rules of AIM-listed companies, as now every company must follow the CG code; however, they can select the code which they want to follow: either the UK CG code or the QCA CG code. As it is clear from the sample that a mix of companies are registered in the AIM, so some of the large companies are following the UK CG code whereas small companies are not necessarily aware of the impact of the QCA CG code on the FP of their companies. Therefore, this study is a reference for those companies as the results of this study provide them with a clear picture of the impact of the QCA CG code on the FP of their companies.

Empirical Contribution

- Further, this study made an empirical contribution by testing the relationship between the QCA CG code and the FP of SMEs listed in AIM. As the QCA CG code was published in response to the new rules of AIM companies and the amendment is quite recent, the researcher could not find any study testing the impact of QCA CG code practice on the financial performance of the listed SMEs in the AIM. Therefore, at the time of writing, this is the first study providing empirical evidence about the positive impact of the QCA CG code on the FP of the listed SMEs in AIM.

Practical Contribution

- This study is beneficial for AIM-listed SMEs because it will help them to see the benefits of following a CG code as, if they know that having a good CG structure is beneficial for them, then they will not feel burdened while following a CG code. The recommendations provided in the last chapter for SMEs assist them to follow a good and efficient CG structure while enhancing their financial performance.
- Additionally, this research is beneficial for the CG and SME policymakers in the UK such as the Quoted Companies Alliance (QCA), London Stock Exchange (LSE) and Financial Reporting Council (FRC). Historical evidence reveals that authorities review the CG codes at regular intervals. So, when the QCA reviews the CG code, the recommendations of this study will help them to update the principles for SMEs according to their requirements.

5.5 Research Limitations

Despite making every effort, this study does have some limitations which are further mentioned below:

- The study was restricted in terms of corporate governance variables as only those variables were selected by the researcher which lie under the demographic boundaries of the board of directors. The reason for this was the development in the field of studies as when the researcher submitted the proposal of research, there was no corporate governance code in practice for listed SMEs in AIM. However, during the research phase, new laws came into place and accordingly, the researcher had to adjust. Therefore, only those variables have been selected which are specifically

mentioned in the QCA CG code and also related to the UK CG code to show a comparison.

- Another limitation is the results of this study that apply to listed SMEs in the UK, as the researcher was unable to test the whole population because more than half of the population does not fit the definition of SMEs. So, the researcher had to reduce the sample to particularly select the SMEs listed in AIM.
- In addition to this, the study used cross-sectional data. However, it would be interesting to see how variables react over a period of time.

5.6 Recommendations for Future Research

- It would be interesting to test other guidelines of the QCA CG code in relation to the FP of the listed SMEs; future researchers can expand the study by testing other guidelines of the QCA CG code.
- Further, this research was cross-sectional, as the researcher wanted to explore the effect of CG guidelines on the FP of the SMEs during the first year after the recovery from financial crises, i.e. 2015, as SMEs took longer than large firms to manage the financial crises. Meanwhile, for future research, it could be interesting to work on more recent data, especially from the year 2019 as from this year, many SMEs must have started to apply the QCA CG code.
- It would also be helpful for SMEs if a researcher conducted research on unlisted SMEs. Though they do not have the requirement to follow any CG code, the information would be helpful for them at least to start understanding and get familiar with the concept of CG. But a researcher needs to make sure that it may be difficult to collect the data as unlisted SMEs do not essentially need to publish all the details on their website; also, it would be extra challenging in terms of time and money.
- As per the requirements of the remaining guidelines of the QCA CG code, the researcher may think about using a mixed research methods approach to explain the impact of the QCA CG code on the financial performance of SMEs with many other variables.

5.7 Summary

This study assessed the possible impact of corporate governance variables on the financial performance of the SMEs listed in the Alternative Investment Market (a sub-market of the London Stock Exchange). The whole thesis has been summarised in this chapter. This chapter has been clearly stated above, and the answers to the research questions and objectives have been achieved. Additionally, hypotheses have been developed to test the association between the QCA CG code and financial measures (Tobin's Q and ROA). The main problem was that listed SMEs were ambiguous about the suitable corporate governance practices for their firms.

However, this study provides them with an unambiguous picture of the impact of practising corporate governance guidelines on the financial performance of their firms. This study has also made recommendations to SMEs about which corporate governance code, either the UK main code or the QCA code, is more suitable according to the results. This theory contributes in both ways, theoretically and empirically. Initially, it contributes to the body of knowledge by providing information about the association between CG variables and FP measures with the sample of AIM-listed companies. And empirically, this study provides recommendations to SMEs about how a financial variable behaves in response to a unit change in the CG variables. Also, this study specifies to SMEs which CG code is more appropriate to them according to the different nature and size of their firms, concerning the parameters of BOD.

This study is a useful reference for academic researchers and AIM companies as it will allow them to know how CG variables influence the FP measures, and then with the help of CG structure, SMEs can stabilise their FP. The suggested recommendations for SMEs and practitioners will provide benefit to them in the long run.

Critical Reflective Summary

This chapter will provide a short DBA journey and a description of my experience throughout the period.

I started my DBA journey after completing my MSc. in Financial Management in March 2017. According to the criteria for completing DBA, I had four modules to complete in the first year. In the first year of my DBA degree, I had two semesters containing two modules in each semester. In the first semester, I had to complete a Strategy into Action (SIA) module and Strategy Thinking and Value Management (STVM). Both the modules had to be completed by June 2017. In SIA, I had to prepare a consultancy report and in STVM, I had to select a business phenomenon and prepare an assignment on it while explaining the issue, analysing it and providing possible solutions for it. I cleared both the modules with good grades. I faced some issues in the beginning as I had never prepared a consultancy report before but with the guidance of Professor Robin, I did it on time and developed the research skills and learnt how business consultancy works, which is quite interesting as a career option.

Further, in the second semester, again I had two modules to complete, namely Leadership and Research & Methodology Proposal (RMP). The Leadership module was quite interesting to know yourself as in this module, I had to identify which type of leader I am. In addition to this, I had to make a Personal Development Plan (PDP) to show my personal development so far and plan for the future. On the other hand, the RMP module is the most important module among all the modules as the rest of the two years of my study depended on the RMP. I took sufficient time to decide the material I was going to use in this, about the research topic (aim and objectives), research area, methodology of research, ethical approval, and data analysis techniques. In this module, I had at least three lots of feedback on three drafts. In the last draft, my module leader gave me positive and motivating feedback, based on the justification of the problem.

Then the second year of DBA started which is a research phase and I started it by reading literature on CG practices and how it influences the FP of companies. While reading, I came to understand that something historical had happened that gave birth to CG practices and that was major corporate collapses that ultimately cause crises worldwide. Therefore, I paid attention to the initial development of CG and how developing countries take

initiatives to develop their CG structure. The next main step was to develop the theoretical underpinnings which helped me to find gaps in the literature as there was only one study I found which focused on SMEs listed in AIM (Afrifa & Tauringana, 2015c) and I have noticed with the series of his work that he is paying attention UK companies with different topics, however, remained in SMEs always (Afrifa, 2013a) (Afrifa, 2013b). I was proceeding well, and it took almost three months to read about the CG, based on which I created a layout of my literature review. It was the hard work of almost six months of writing, reviewing and making corrections.

Afterwards, finally, I moved to the research methodology chapter and started thinking about various methods, approaches, designs and among all of those, which was suitable to answer my developed research questions. My first two research questions were achieved by reviewing the literature review in depth. Further, I decided to find an association between CG variables and FP measures for which I needed to collect quantitative data. The one thing which made me decide on selecting the research method was the rules of CG according to which every listed firm has to publicise the information on their company regarding the board of directors, top management and their financial reports. As per the various literature when I developed my hypotheses, I was aware of a source from where I could get that information that offered secondary sources for which I decided to use quantitative methods and analysis techniques. I discussed this with the supervisor as well and she was in support of me as long as I could justify my choices.

The next step was to get ethical approval. My supervisor suggested asking the DBA programme leader (Dr Bobby Mackie) if I needed ethical approval for this study. And he confirmed that I didn't need ethical approval for this study. Then I was all clear to start collecting the data. The way I planned to collect the data, I needed access to one of the financial databases. I could have been more careful with the availability of the financial databases. I thought, UWS would have one, I can understand that it may not have been Bloomberg or DataStream but I thought at least they would have a subscription to FAME, as I got this impression from my previous university (Middlesex Library) that almost all universities have financial labs. I should have checked the availability of resources before to save my time and effort. But the real struggle started there; it was clear that UWS did not have Bloomberg or DataStream in the university.

I tried to approach my previous university and they refused to give me access as according to the policy of the university, access to the financial database was allowed to current students only. I tried a few other universities near to my area but they also refused. Then my supervisor tried to help me as her university (Cardiff Metropolitan University) has all the financial databases; she tried but again, there was the same problem that an outsider can't access them. Then the researcher and supervisor contacted LSE for a raw list of companies listed. And I got a list with more than 2000 companies from which I reduced it to my selected sample. Meanwhile, I tried to contact the British Library for access and started the procedure to be a free member there and have access to some of the business resources. Simultaneously, I started scanning companies from the list I got from LSE. Yes, I was delayed with all these hassles but with access to a financial database, I was on the move. However, the whole process of collecting data stopped for a while when I discovered that there was a development in the field of research and because of this I had to revisit the literature chapter and needed to modify the research questions as well.

By then, March 2019 arrived and it took almost two months to make desirable changes in the literature review and to modify the objectives and research questions. After doing this, I started collecting data again; at this time, I preferred hand-collected data. However, I was in regular touch with the British Library as if I got access, at least I would be able to triangulate the data. Meanwhile, I attended the 'Advances in Management and Innovation Conference' where I presented my research work and received valuable feedback from the audience. Further, I applied for a first-year academic extension for two main reasons: the development in the research field that meant it took quite a lot of time to rework the objectives and research questions and the issues in access to the financial database which made the data collection procedure very time consuming and complicated. Then the year 2020 came. I made every effort possible to complete my research on time as 2020 was an exceptional year. It did affect my studies but somehow, I managed it. After the data collection, Gretl software has been used to run the analysis. My university does provide SPSS software but in 2020, the university was working remotely and I did something wrong while installing it. It was very difficult to understand remotely what I had done wrong and how to fix it further. So, without wasting any time, I had to opt for another statistical tool that is free to download. However, I have to read its guide thoroughly, seen tutorials on how to use it and I ran the analysis. After analysis, it took almost three to four months to write Chapter Four about the data analysis and findings. And finally, I

concluded it within a month's time with specified answers to research questions and recommendations for SMEs. I have received feedback from my supervisor, assessor and second supervisor which were quite critical and helped me to improve my work.

Looking back, I count all the effort, hard work, and sleepless nights that made me stronger to complete it on time. I have learnt through my mistakes that to start the project you must ensure what resources you have to complete the project and whatever happens, you need to be ready to tackle the situation, you must be persistent and flexible according to the requirements of the project.

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Appendix A List of Companies Listed in AIM used as Data Set

Table A.1: List of Companies listed in AIM used as Data Set

GW PHARMACEUTICA	TISSUE REGENIX G	RAMBLER METALS A
AVANTI COMMUNICA	MANX FINANCIAL	ZINCOX RESOURCES
NEWRIVER RETAIL	MIDATECH PHARMA	OBTALA RESOURCES
SIRIUS REAL ESTA	ELAND OIL & GAS	NETCALL PLC
XCITE ENERGY LTD	ORIGO PARTNERS P	MERCIA TECHNOLOG
PLEXUS HOLDINGS	PLANT HEALTH CAR	LEARNING TECHNOL
QUADRISE FUELS	TAPTICA INTERNAT	TOUMAZ LTD
CRANEWARE PLC	LGO ENERGY PLC	PROTEOME SCIENCE
4D PHARMA PLC	REAL ESTATE INVE	IDEAGEN PLC
FEVERTREE DRINKS	BENCHMARK HOLDIN	FLOWTECH FLUIDPO
BOWLEVEN PLC	HYDRODEC GROUP	SCANCELL HOLDING
ROXI PETROLEUM P	FLOWGROUP PLC	APPLIED GRAPHENE
WANDISCO PLC	PALACE CAPITAL P	ATLANTIS RESOURC
CONYGAR INVEST	SOMERO ENTERPRIS	BRADY PLC
PARKMEAD GROUP	VICTORIA OIL & G	MURGITROYD GROUP
PANTHER SECS PLC	SILENCE THERAPEU	SOLID STATE PLC
GRAPHENE NANOCH	RURELEC PLC	BANGO PLC

AUREUS MINING IN	PROVIDENCE RESOU	SAN LEON ENERGY
VELOCYS PLC	LOK'N STORE GRP	KALIBRATE TECHNO
FIRST PROPERTY	ECKOH PLC	SUTTON HARBOUR
HORIZON DISCOVER	SOLGOLD PLC	IOFINA PLC
PRESIDENT ENERGY	FALCON OIL & GAS	RENEURON GROUP P
SABLE MINING AFR	PEOPLES OPERATOR	ANPARIO PLC
QUIXANT PLC	DOTDIGITAL GROUP	GULFSANDS PETROL
ECO ANIMAL HEALT	ACCSYS TECHNOLI	SOUND ENERGY PLC
FIRESTONE DIAMON	CHURCHILL MINING	IMPAX ASSET MANA
ITM POWER PLC	HALOSOURCE - DI	INTERCEDE GROUP
E-THERAPEUTICS P	CITYFIBRE INFRAS	JARVIS SECURITY
SERABI GOLD PLC	ANGLE PLC	EGDON RESOURCES
PETRONFT RESOUR	BRAINJUICER GROU	ILIKA PLC
B.P. MARSH & PAR	AMINO TECH PLC	EASYHOTEL PLC
SUMMIT THERAPEUT	MINDS PLUS MACHI	AVACTA GROUP PLC

Appendix B Numerical Distribution Frequency and Normality Tests

Table B.2: Numerical Frequency Distribution of BI

gret: frequency distribution

Frequency distribution for NED, obs 1-96
number of bins = 9, mean = 3.46875, sd = 1.43603

interval	midpt	frequency	rel.	cum.
< 1.3750	1.0000	5	5.21%	5.21% *
1.3750 - 2.1250	1.7500	24	25.00%	30.21% *****
2.1250 - 2.8750	2.5000	0	0.00%	30.21%
2.8750 - 3.6250	3.2500	22	22.92%	53.13% *****
3.6250 - 4.3750	4.0000	23	23.96%	77.08% *****
4.3750 - 5.1250	4.7500	11	11.46%	88.54% ****
5.1250 - 5.8750	5.5000	0	0.00%	88.54%
5.8750 - 6.6250	6.2500	10	10.42%	98.96% ***
>= 6.6250	7.0000	1	1.04%	100.00%

Test for null hypothesis of normal distribution:
Chi-square(2) = 6.143 with p-value 0.04635

Table B.3: Numerical Frequency Distribution of ACS

gret: frequency distribution

Frequency distribution for ACS, obs 1-96

	frequency	rel.	cum.
0	2	2.08%	2.08%
1	3	3.13%	5.21% *
2	34	35.42%	40.63% *****
3	47	48.96%	89.58% *****
4	9	9.38%	98.96% ***
6	1	1.04%	100.00%

Table B.4: Numerical Frequency Distribution of BS

Table B.5: Numerical Frequency Distribution of CEOD

Table B.6: Numerical Frequency Distribution of BGD

	frequency	rel.	cum.	
0	61	63.54%	63.54%	*****
1	26	27.08%	90.63%	*****
2	8	8.33%	98.96%	***
3	1	1.04%	100.00%	

Table B.7: Numerical Frequency Distribution of QRATIO

interval	midpt	frequency	rel.	cum.	
< 1.8050	0.90250	54	56.25%	56.25%	*****
1.8050 - 3.6100	2.7075	23	23.96%	80.21%	*****
3.6100 - 5.4150	4.5125	8	8.33%	88.54%	***
5.4150 - 7.2200	6.3175	6	6.25%	94.79%	**
7.2200 - 9.0250	8.1225	2	2.08%	96.87%	
9.0250 - 10.830	9.9275	2	2.08%	98.96%	
10.830 - 12.635	11.733	0	0.00%	98.96%	
12.635 - 14.440	13.538	0	0.00%	98.96%	
>= 14.440	15.342	1	1.04%	100.00%	

Test for null hypothesis of normal distribution:
Chi-square(2) = 112.232 with p-value 0.00000

Table B.8: Numerical Frequency Distribution of ROA

Table B.9: Normality test of QRATIO Model

Test for normality of Residuals:

Doornik-Hansen test = 88.0347, with p-value 7.64738e-020

Shapiro-Wilk W = 0.804669, with p-value 6.04257e-010

Lilliefors test = 0.175768, with p-value ~ = 0

Jarque-Bera test = 152.047, with p-value 9.62758e-034

Table B.10: Normality test of ROA Model

Test for normality of residuals:

Doornik-Hansen test = 24.8438, with p-value 4.02939e-006

Shapiro-Wilk W = 0.906783, with p-value 4.4626e-006

Lilliefors test = 0.0971107, with p-value ~ = 0.03

Jarque-Bera test = 130.2, with p-value 5.33995e-029

Appendix C Descriptive Results and Pearsons Correlation Matrix

Table C.11: Descriptive Results

	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum
NED	3.4688	3.0000	1.0000	7.0000
ACS	2.6458	3.0000	0.00000	6.0000
BS	6.2708	6.0000	2.0000	11.000
CEOD	0.072917	0.00000	0.00000	1.0000
BG	0.46875	0.00000	0.00000	3.0000
QRATIO	2.5517	1.5450	0.22000	14.660
ROA	-0.098136	-0.028340	-1.2020	0.40797
	Std. Dev.	C.V.	Skewness	Ex. kurtosis
NED	1.4360	0.41399	0.34167	-0.68174
ACS	0.85814	0.32434	0.043461	2.5612
BS	1.7136	0.27326	0.15444	-0.11430
CEOD	0.26136	3.5844	3.2853	8.7929
BG	0.69514	1.4830	1.3406	1.1022
QRATIO	2.4368	0.95497	2.2733	6.3953
ROA	0.23851	2.4305	-1.4382	4.1593
	5% perc.	95% perc.	IQ range	Missing obs.
NED	1.0000	6.0000	2.0000	0
ACS	1.0000	4.0000	1.0000	0
BS	4.0000	9.0000	2.0000	0
CEOD	0.00000	1.0000	0.00000	0
BG	0.00000	2.0000	1.0000	0
QRATIO	0.49700	8.7810	2.1600	0
ROA	-0.46318	0.20074	0.25150	0

Table C.12: Pearson's Correlation Matrix

Correlation Coefficients, using the observations 1 - 96					
5% critical value (two-tailed) = 0.2006 for n = 96					
NED	ACS	BS	CEOD	BG	
1.0000	0.5120	0.7777	-0.2042	0.3154	NED
	1.0000	0.4739	-0.0714	0.0695	ACS
		1.0000	-0.1151	0.3695	BS
			1.0000	-0.1322	CEOD
				1.0000	BG
QRATIO	ROA				
-0.0690	-0.1413	NED			
0.0047	-0.0122	ACS			
-0.0216	-0.0150	BS			
0.1819	0.0399	CEOD			
0.0062	0.0596	BG			
1.0000	-0.4152	QRATIO			
	1.0000	ROA			

Appendix D ANOVA Analysis

ANOVA Analysis of Board Size (BS)

Board Size less than 6

Table D.13: ANOVA Analysis of BS less than Six (QRATIO)

Analysis of Variance, response = QRATIO, treatment = BS:			
	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	1.54399	3	0.514663
Residual	105.945	26	4.07483
Total	107.489	29	3.70653
$F(3, 26) = 0.514663 / 4.07483 = \underline{0.126303}$ [p-value <u>0.9437</u>]			
Level	n	mean	std. dev
2	1	1.2	NA
3	2	1.795	0.57276
4	14	2.32357	1.4391
5	13	2.21385	2.5608
Grand mean = <u>2.20333</u>			

Table D.14: ANOVA Analysis of BS less than Six (ROA)

Analysis of Variance, response = ROA, treatment = BS:			
	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	0.222654	3	0.0742181
Residual	2.22286	26	0.0854947
Total	2.44552	29	0.0843282
$F(3, 26) = 0.0742181 / 0.0854947 = \underline{0.868101}$ [p-value <u>0.4701</u>]			
Level	n	mean	std. dev
2	1	-0.381125	NA
3	2	-0.25888	0.16781
4	14	-0.0317522	0.23544
5	13	-0.148353	0.35049
Grand mean = <u>-0.109067</u>			

Board Size between 6 and 9

Table D.15: ANOVA Analysis of BS between 6 and 9 (QRATIO)

Analysis of Variance, response = QRATIO, treatment = BS:

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	16.1281	3	5.37605
Residual	422.688	59	7.16421
Total	438.816	62	7.07768

$F(3, 59) = 5.37605 / 7.16421 = \underline{0.750404}$ [p-value 0.5265]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
6	23	3.08609	2.6319
7	23	3.10261	3.2711
8	10	1.759	1.5716
9	7	2.36857	1.4529

Grand mean = 2.80175

Table D.16: ANOVA Analysis of BS between 6 and 9 (ROA)

Analysis of Variance, response = ROA, treatment = BS:

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	0.0976162	3	0.0325387
Residual	2.85067	59	0.0483164
Total	2.94829	62	0.047553

$F(3, 59) = 0.0325387 / 0.0483164 = \underline{0.673451}$ [p-value 0.5717]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
6	23	-0.0569864	0.21579
7	23	-0.107952	0.24707
8	10	-0.0837075	0.16011
9	7	-0.187024	0.20519

Grand mean = -0.094283

Board Size more than 9

Table D.17: ANOVA Analysis of BS more than 9 (QRATIO)

Analysis of Variance, response = QRATIO, treatment = BS:

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	0.814017	1	0.814017
Residual	0.01445	1	0.01445
Total	0.828467	2	0.414233

$F(1, 1) = 0.814017 / 0.01445 = \underline{56.3333}$ [p-value 0.0843]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
10	2	0.415	0.12021
11	1	1.52	NA

Grand mean = 0.783333

Table D.18: ANOVA Analysis of BS more than 9 (ROA)

Analysis of Variance, response = ROA, treatment = BS:

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	0.0022218	1	0.0022218
Residual	0.00152224	1	0.00152224
Total	0.00374404	2	0.00187202

$F(1, 1) = 0.0022218 / 0.00152224 = \underline{1.45956}$ [p-value 0.4402]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
10	2	-0.0504817	0.039016
11	1	-0.108211	NA

Grand mean = -0.0697249

ANOVA Analysis of Board Independence (BI)

Board Independence less than or equal to 3

Table D.19: ANOVA Analysis of BI less than or equal to 3 (QRATIO)

```
Analysis of Variance, response = QRATIO, treatment = NED:

                Sum of squares          df          Mean square

Treatment                9.56772           2           4.78386
Residual                 227.082           48           4.73089
Total                   236.65            50           4.733

F(2, 48) = 4.78386 / 4.73089 = 1.0112 [p-value 0.3714]

Level          n          mean          std. dev

1                5          2.068          1.1086
2               24          2.38083          2.1436
3               22          3.18273          2.3552

Grand mean = 2.69608
```

Table D.20: ANOVA Analysis of BI less than or equal to 3 (ROA)

```
Analysis of Variance, response = ROA, treatment = NED:

                Sum of squares          df          Mean square

Treatment                0.0230825           2           0.0115412
Residual                 3.41077           48           0.0710577
Total                   3.43385           50           0.0686771

F(2, 48) = 0.0115412 / 0.0710577 = 0.162421 [p-value 0.8505]

Level          n          mean          std. dev

1                5 -0.0850613          0.27627
2               24 -0.0954241          0.31090
3               22 -0.0510977          0.20498

Grand mean = -0.0752869
```

Board Independence more than 3

Table D.21: ANOVA Analysis of BI more than 3 (QRATIO)

Analysis of Variance, response = <u>TobinsQ</u> , treatment = <u>NED</u> :			
	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	13.2417	3	4.4139
Residual	311.934	41	7.60816
Total	325.176	44	7.39037

F(3, 41) = 4.4139 / 7.60816 = 0.580154 [p-value 0.6314]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
4	23	2.69217	3.2810
5	11	2.66727	2.5823
6	10	1.57	0.96787
7	1	0.5	NA

Grand mean = 2.388

Table D.22: ANOVA Analysis of BI more than 3 (ROA)

Analysis of Variance, response = <u>ROA</u> , treatment = <u>NED</u> :			
	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	0.0230825	2	0.0115412
Residual	3.41077	48	0.0710577
Total	3.43385	50	0.0686771

F(2, 48) = 0.0115412 / 0.0710577 = 0.162421 [p-value 0.8505]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
1	5	-0.0850613	0.27627
2	24	-0.0954241	0.31090
3	22	-0.0510977	0.20498

Grand mean = -0.0752869

ANOVA Analysis of Audit Committee Size (ACS)

Audit Committee Size less than or equal to 3

Table D.23: ANOVA Analysis of ACS less than or equal to 3 (QRATIO)

Analysis of Variance, response = <u>QRATIO</u> , treatment = <u>ACS</u> :			
	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	5.08608	3	1.69536
Residual	534.53	82	6.51866
Total	539.616	85	6.34842
F(3, 82) = 1.69536 / 6.51866 = <u>0.260078</u> [p-value <u>0.8539</u>]			
Level	n	mean	std. dev
0	2	1.41	0.028284
1	3	1.81667	0.99761
2	34	2.60618	2.2260
3	47	2.69362	2.8324
Grand mean = <u>2.5986</u>			

Table D.24: ANOVA Analysis of ACS less than or equal to 3 (ROA)

Analysis of Variance, response = <u>ROA</u> , treatment = <u>ACS</u> :			
	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	0.0582595	3	0.0194198
Residual	5.13725	82	0.0626493
Total	5.1955	85	0.0611236
F(3, 82) = 0.0194198 / 0.0626493 = <u>0.309977</u> [p-value <u>0.8181</u>]			
Level	n	mean	std. dev
0	2	-0.16452	0.30126
1	3	0.022199	0.15435
2	34	-0.107488	0.27483
3	47	-0.0881125	0.23342
Grand mean = <u>-0.0937013</u>			

Audit Committee Size more than 3

Table D.25: ANOVA Analysis of ACS more than 3 (QRATIO)

Analysis of Variance, response = QRATIO, treatment = ACS:

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	3.67236	1	3.67236
Residual	18.988	8	2.3735
Total	22.6604	9	2.51782

$F(1, 8) = 3.67236 / 2.3735 = \underline{1.54723}$, [p-value 0.2488]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
4	9	2.35	1.5406
6	1	0.33	NA

Grand mean = 2.148

Table D.26: ANOVA Analysis of ACS more than 3 (ROA)

Analysis of Variance, response = ROA, treatment = ACS:

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	0.0142826	1	0.0142826
Residual	0.178468	8	0.0223085
Total	0.19275	9	0.0214167

$F(1, 8) = 0.0142826 / 0.0223085 = \underline{0.640231}$ [p-value 0.4467]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
4	9	-0.148868	0.14936
6	1	-0.0228933	NA

Grand mean = -0.13627

ANOVA Analysis of Board Gender Diversity (BGD)

Number of women on the board less than 2

Table D.27: ANOVA Analysis of BGD less than 2 (QRATIO)

```
Analysis of Variance, response = QRATIO, treatment = NOOfwmn:

                Sum of squares      df      Mean square

Treatment                2.79252         1         2.79252
Residual                 531.026         85         6.24737
Total                   533.819         86         6.2072

F(1, 85) = 2.79252 / 6.24737 = 0.446992 [p-value 0.5056]

Level      n      mean      std. dev

0          61     2.50246     2.6775
1          26     2.89385     2.0089

Grand mean = 2.61943
```

Table D.28: ANOVA Analysis of BGD less than 2 (ROA)

```
Analysis of Variance, response = ROA, treatment = NOOfwmn:

                Sum of squares      df      Mean square

Treatment                7.13547e-005         1         7.13547e-005
Residual                 5.25561         85         0.0618307
Total                   5.25568         86         0.0611126

F(1, 85) = 7.13547e-005 / 0.0618307 = 0.00115403 [p-value 0.9730]

Level      n      mean      std. dev

0          61    -0.104178     0.24631
1          26    -0.1022         0.25420

Grand mean = -0.103587
```

Number of women on the board more than or equal to 2

Table D.29: ANOVA Analysis of BGD more than or equal to 2 (QRATIO)

Analysis of Variance, response = QRATIO, treatment = NOOfwmn:

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	23.2221	1	23.2221
Residual	2.79369	7	0.399098
Total	26.0158	8	3.25198

$F(1, 7) = 23.2221 / 0.399098 = 58.1865$ [p-value 0.0001]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
2	8	1.32875	0.63174
3	1	6.44	NA

Grand mean = 1.89667

Table D.30: ANOVA Analysis of BGD more than or equal to 2 (ROA)

Analysis of Variance, response = ROA, treatment = NOOfwmn:

	Sum of squares	df	Mean square
Treatment	0.00203003	1	0.00203003
Residual	0.119196	7	0.017028
Total	0.121226	8	0.0151533

$F(1, 7) = 0.00203003 / 0.017028 = 0.119217$ [p-value 0.7400]

Level	n	mean	std. dev
2	8	-0.0507486	0.13049
3	1	-0.00295958	NA

Grand mean = -0.0454387